

**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

Exploring the Research Landscape of Social Innovation

**A deliverable of the project Social
Innovation Community (SIC)**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

It was mainly through global economic and social developments since the turn of the century that the area of social innovation has established itself as a research field. On the one hand, this research field is strongly linked to practice, as far as its thematic scope is concerned. On the other hand, both social innovation research and practice themselves are still two relatively fragmented areas with insufficiently connected actors and networks.

Against this background, the overarching aim of the project Social Innovation Community (SIC) is to create a 'network of networks' of social innovation actors by identifying, engaging and connecting researchers, social innovators, citizens, policy-makers, intermediaries, businesses, civil society organisations, public sector employees etc. SIC aims to deepen and strengthen different thematic communities, which we call 'networks', forge new connections between them, and additionally create new links to actors and networks which hitherto have not yet been included or recognised as part of the field of social innovation. Building on existing networks, SIC aims to further advance the field of social innovation as a whole in theory and practice.

In this report, we focus on what we call the SIC Research Landscape, the international field of social innovation research with its actors and networks, projects and initiatives, trends and topics, and achievements. The report mirrors the thematic structure used in SIC, with its different networks, and reflects upon these separately. It provides an overview of the current research landscape in Europe and beyond and offers key information regarding those who work within different thematic areas of social innovation, their research interests and the current status of their work.

The purpose of this report is to allow for insights into the complex field of social innovation research through relatively short and not entirely academic articles. These insights should help to better understand what social innovation research is about, how it is organised through networks and communities and how it is related to practice in order to support the emergence of an inclusive social innovation research community which transcends European borders and research disciplines.

The findings of the report can be used by all those who work in social innovation and are looking for new opportunities to get involved with a community, which is growing in a very dynamic way. Hence, one particular feature of this report is that it not only refers to usual suspects, but also reveals that there are important parts of the research landscape which – despite their relevance – are often not recognised as such.

The report demonstrates ongoing processes of community building in all thematic areas under review. At the same time, it makes clear that more possibilities are needed for researchers to work on social innovation. Funding provided by the European Commission has been crucial for successful development of the area of social innovation. Hence, further funding opportunities will largely determine the future of social innovation and its research.

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1 Introduction

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What is the state of the art in social innovation research? Although we can find scientific publications on social innovation dating back to the 19th century, only in recent years it has become an autonomous research field. For a long time, it was a matter of loosely – if at all - connected research efforts rather than of an area with common research interests, a shared knowledge basis and a self-conscious community of researchers. It was mainly through global economic and social developments since the turn of the century that scientific work on social innovation evolved into a research area. The recent boost that social innovation (research) has experienced in the European Union can largely be understood as a consequence of the failure of the Lisbon Strategy for Growth and Jobs and the financial crisis in 2008-2009: “the long-held belief that economic growth creates employment and wealth that goes on to alleviate poverty has been disproved by recent events, and the time has now come to try new ways of bringing people out of poverty and promoting growth and well-being not only *for*, but also *with* citizens“ (BEPA, 2011, p. 64).

In consequence, thanks to a growing number of projects, conferences, research initiatives and increasing collaborative efforts, the area of social innovation has further established itself as a research field. On the one hand, this research field is strongly linked to practice, as far as its thematic scope is concerned. Many research projects deal with very concrete practical issues in areas, such as education, health care or mobility. On the other hand, both social innovation research and practice themselves are still two relatively fragmented areas with insufficiently connected actors and networks. Many researchers mainly work in their specific research areas (under the ‘umbrella’ of social innovation) without connecting to the work done by their colleagues from other areas and hence not using the synergies that emerge in the highly diverse area of social innovation. The multidisciplinary nature of social innovation research offers an important potential for development of new research perspectives that would help to advance towards new responses to societal challenges. At the same time, such new perspectives would facilitate new approaches to social innovation practice. Through elaborating on an integrated concept of social innovation which includes all societal sectors, social innovation research would discover and show unexplored paths for practitioners to develop new collaboration and participation structures in order to find better solutions for manifold problems.

Against this background, the overarching aim of the project Social Innovation Community (SIC) is to create a ‘network of networks’ of social innovation actors by identifying, engaging and connecting researchers, social innovators, citizens, policy-makers, intermediaries, businesses, civil society organisations, public sector employees etc. SIC is delivering engagement, research, experimentation, learning and policy activities to better connect different thematic communities, which we call ‘networks’. SIC aims to deepen and strengthen these networks, forge new connections between them, and additionally create new links to actors and networks which hitherto have not yet been included or recognised as part of the field of social innovation. Building on existing networks, SIC aims to further advance the field of social innovation as a whole in theory and practice.

How the report was prepared

This report, prepared by a group of SIC researchers, focuses on nine different thematic areas within the SIC Research Landscape. Eight of these nine areas are the so-called ‘networks’, identified by SIC as central thematic fields to work towards a ‘network of networks’ of social innovation actors. The eight ‘networks’ with their abundance of social innovation initiatives are the main constitutive elements of SIC. Many different project activities are built around them. The thematic areas with their actor networks SIC is focusing on are the following: Public sector innovation, Digital social innovation, Intermediaries, Social economy, Cities and regional development, Collaborative and sharing economy, Community-led innovation, and Corporate social innovation. Therefore, in the context of the SIC Research Landscape report we are focusing on research related to these thematic areas with their communities (‘networks’). Additionally, the area of research on concepts and theories of social innovation is explicitly addressed within the SIC Research Landscape in order to deliver a more comprehensive overview on social innovation research. The formation of this research strand as an autonomous field within social innovation research has been crucial for the development of the area as a whole. Only through further work on conceptual clarity and theoretical foundation of social innovation it will be possible to establish social innovation research as a solid scientific area.

In the following, the reader will find nine thematic chapters written by researchers who represent different partner organisations of SIC. In order to prepare this report, the team of SIC researchers has used three main sources of information: desk research, an expert survey, and discursive “breakout sessions”. Five of such sessions were organised, some of them virtually, some of them as short discussion rounds at different conferences and workshops related to social innovation. These breakout sessions have helped to identify and discuss transversal research questions and topics, methodologies, with a focus on transdisciplinarity and researchers’ specific interests, thus also opening the debate for unusual research perspectives. Additionally, in the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey we asked international experts from Europe and beyond to share their perspectives on the international social innovation research landscape according to the nine thematic areas of this report. Altogether, 27 experts participated in the survey, thus making a very important contribution in order to draw a more complete picture of the SIC Research Landscape, allowing for more targeted discussions in and with the different social innovation communities and increasing the impact of research results.

The scope of the report

In this report, we focus on what we call the SIC Research Landscape, the international field of social innovation research with its actors and networks, projects and initiatives, trends and topics, and achievements. Drafting such a research landscape is a challenge in itself, since we rarely see purely academic actors, even less so networks. Hybridity is much more commonplace, with researchers working highly application-oriented, and practitioners using scientific methodology. Research efforts often involve actors from different societal sectors. While this situation is certainly a challenge when trying to

structure the highly fragmented research field of social innovation, we must acknowledge that this is part of the social innovation reality: social innovation research and practice are closely intertwined, and this link is crucial in order to understand the type of research in this area.

The report mirrors the thematic structure used in SIC, with its different networks, and reflects upon these separately. The report provides an overview of the current research landscape in Europe and beyond. It offers key information regarding those who work within different thematic areas of social innovation, their research interests and the current status of their work. We also ask about networks (in terms of concrete associations of organisations) that might exist in the respective field.

Many activities in social innovation research (and practice) are not necessarily taking place in or through formal networks. However, we can observe that research communities are emerging in different thematic areas. These communities are guided by complementary research interests, and the actors increasingly refer to one another in their work. Furthermore, in order to understand how scientists conduct research, the report addresses the methods employed, as well as the role of research in the thematic areas under review. Finally, the authors of every thematic chapter reflect upon the impact achieved by research. They outline both the strengths and the weaknesses of the research work done so far.

Utilisation of the findings in SIC and beyond

While all thematic chapters have the same structure, we must acknowledge that the nine thematic areas are quite diverse, and putting them into a too narrow scheme would not correspond to the reality of social innovation and its research. Moreover, we would run the risk of missing the unique properties of specific research areas. Last but not least, it is not only about research areas with different features and realities. It is also a matter of researchers who represent very different disciplines and research traditions. Therefore, the premise of this report is to make use of the diversity of social innovation research rather than to avoid heterogeneity.

What the reader finds here is not an attempt to map all research initiatives in social innovation. Nor have we sought to deliver a preferably complete literature review. Both exercises would go beyond the scope of this report and miss its purpose. Thus, the purpose of this report is to allow for insights into the complex field of social innovation research through relatively short and not entirely academic articles. These insights should help to better understand what social innovation research is about, how it is organised through networks and communities and how it is related to practice in order to support the emergence of an inclusive social innovation research community which transcends European borders and research disciplines.

On the one hand, the knowledge generated through this report will be used directly in the Social Innovation Community project. The work on the report has helped to better understand the state of the art of research done in the different networks, to reflect the progress made in the SI research community, the

potential of research for the social innovation community as a whole, and outline further steps necessary to further improve the impact of research on SI practice, as well as suggest priority areas for future social innovation research. It has also helped to identify specific “hot topics” which are currently emerging and which will be addressed by SIC in separate workshops. The results also lay the foundation for a roadmap of social innovation research which will be developed at a later stage of SIC. Additionally, the results will inform other work packages, e.g. the WP Learning in terms of new knowledge, skills and competences needed to implement and diffuse a new social innovation culture. It will be used in the evaluation of the Experimentation WP, and for the master classes as well as the learning materials repository in the WP Policy.

Even more importantly, the findings of the report can be used outside the SIC project, by all those who work in social innovation and are looking for new opportunities to get involved with a community, which is growing in a very dynamic way. Hence, one particular feature of this report is that it not only refers to usual suspects, but also reveals that there are important parts of the research landscape which – despite their relevance – are often not recognised as such. Different actors and networks are active in the field of social innovation without identifying themselves as part of it (in this regard, the Expert Survey was also particularly important). However, an explicit focus on social innovation beyond individual disciplines is needed. A systematic approach to innovations which are not technological and not necessarily about creating economic value would help to address societal challenges in a more targeted manner. It would also support the creation of links to social innovation practice across all societal sectors. Therefore, one central purpose of this report is to make more visible the potential of social innovation as a transdisciplinary field of action.

This task is important, as the international social innovation research community is still highly fragmented. On the one hand, diversity – due to its nature of representing many different areas and topics – enriches the debate and the development of the research field. On the other hand, it makes community building a challenging task. Through this report, we seek to better understand this international research community and to identify links which would help to become a community of researchers who know each other and work on joint research initiatives, but also to better connect social innovation research and practice.

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2 Social Innovation Research on Concepts and Theories

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2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter will highlight main developments in social innovation research on concepts and theories, focusing mainly on the last five years. Through the formation of this research strand as an autonomous area within the field of social innovation research, the whole field has been significantly influenced, establishing itself as a scientific area. Without working on conceptual clarity and theoretical foundation of social innovation it is becoming increasingly difficult (if not impossible) to deal with specific thematic areas. For this reason, our report on the social innovation research landscape in Europe and beyond starts with this topic, which connects to the subsequent eight chapters.

The main conclusion of this chapter is that progress has been made with respect to a clearer understanding of social innovation, research groups are increasingly interlinked, while contrasting theoretical concepts are being discussed and provide the basis for more and more extensive empirical work. Both theoretical and empirical efforts have played an important transversal role for the development of this field.

In 2013, a first systematic attempt to provide an overview of findings of the European Union's research projects on social innovation was undertaken by the Canadian researchers Jenson and Harrisson. By comparing 17 research projects funded in FP7 and its predecessors FP5 and FP6, the report "focuses on how these projects address 'social innovation' in terms of theory, methodology, policy areas, actors, and level of analysis with the aim of bringing the results to the attention of policymakers, wider groups of stakeholders and the broader public in a comprehensive way" (Jenson & Harrisson, 2013, p. 5). Regarding "the increasing demands coming from policymakers and practitioners alike for social innovations and the emerging possibilities for new research avenues on social innovation, including in Horizon 2020" (ibid.) such an overview can be of great value. The report also helps to foster "the engagement of the European research community in a continuous exchange of ideas and best practices for analysing social innovation and in the promotion of networking among researchers" (BEPA, 2014, p. 37).

While the review delivers valuable information and demonstrates not only a quantitative, but also a qualitative increase of social innovation research in the European Union in recent years, the authors conclude that some of the most urgent questions remain unanswered: "Although social innovations pop up in many areas and policies and in many disguises, and social innovation is researched from a number of theoretical and methodological angles, the conditions under which social innovations develop, flourish and sustain and finally lead to societal change are not yet fully understood both in political and academic circles. However, in particular in the current times of social, political and economic crisis, social innovation has evoked many hopes and further triggered academic and political debates." (Jenson and Harrisson, 2013, p. 5)

Four years later, we can say that the central questions mentioned by Jenson and Harrisson have been addressed by a new generation of research projects, many of them funded by the European Union, and

by a considerable number of scientific publications. In a collective effort, social innovation research on concepts and theories has further established itself as an autonomous research field with an emerging community of researchers.

While at the end of the 20th century only a few researchers and research groups were working on social innovation, in recent years, social innovation has received increasing recognition as a topic of policy and research in many parts of the world (Howaldt et al., 2016): “Today, there are lots of groups of many sorts in many countries that promote social innovation and several governments have adopted political strategies to develop social innovation. This is a signal of change as well as of an opportunity to change” (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). This growing community of researchers is addressing the topic in journals and edited volumes, showing an explicit focus on conceptual and theoretical social innovation research (e.g. Franz et al., 2012; Moolaert et al., 2013; Cajaiba-Santana, 2013; Howaldt et al., 2014; Pue et al., 2016; Daggars et al., 2016; Ayob et al., 2016; Klein et al., 2016; Domanski et al., 2016), and at joint conferences (e.g. Vienna 2011, London 2013, Vienna 2015, Brussels 2017). Hence, a notable achievement in this regard has been the formation of a community of researchers (certainly with a number of sub-communities) which transcends the limits of individual disciplines and research traditions. For the first time in history of social innovation research, we see scholars working together in projects, publishing within the same volumes and participating in the same conferences who did not even know each other personally only some years ago.

In the following, we focus on the development of social innovation research on concepts and theories as research area, but also explicitly in terms of emergence of a community of researchers, which is a central topic for the project Social Innovation Community (SIC), which aims at building an international community of all those who work in the area social innovation. In order to better understand and describe this Research Landscape, we use the three main sources described in the introduction to this report: desk research, an expert survey and a breakout session.

2.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

As we have shown above, social innovation as a research field is relatively new. This is even more the case of social innovation research on concepts and theories. We can say that this research area is still in formation, mainly influenced through international research funded by the European Union. Projects such as SI-DRIVE, TRANSIT, TEPSIE, LIPSE, SIMPACT or CrESSI, all of them started not before 2012, explicitly engaged (or are still engaging, as some of them finalise in 2017) with social innovation research on concepts and theories. These projects were to some extent prompted by the intent to develop a clearer understanding of social innovation. From various angles, they have contributed and worked on the theoretical foundations of the concept.

In addition, we can say that with the European Commission (EC) exploring how social innovation might be a concept to overcome the economic crisis, there was a crucial impulse for social innovation research on concepts and theories in order to evolve into an autonomous research area in Europe. In consequence, the first features of a community of researchers in this area became visible thanks to research projects funded through EC's central research programmes FP7 and Horizon 2020.

The road was paved for social innovation to become part of EC's agenda after a high-level workshop, with president Barroso personally participating, which was organised in Brussels in January 2009. In the following months and years, the agenda setting was largely influenced by the work of BEPA, led by Agnès Hubert, and especially its report "Empowering people, driving change: Social innovation in the European Union" (BEPA, 2010). The report concludes with a series of recommendations and one of them is the following: "Develop a general theory of social innovation to conceptualise and define the value of the field" (BEPA, 2011, p. 137). Consequently, the European Commission started designing calls within its funding programmes in order to advance making social innovation an important pillar of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth which would imply a better understanding of social innovation and hence support the efforts of social innovation research, explicitly including further development of its theoretical foundations.

The first project to address this issue in the most targeted manner was TEPSIE ("Theoretical, Empirical and Policy Foundations for Building Social Innovation in Europe" 2012-2014). Its aim was mainly to prepare the way for developing tools, methods and policies which would be part of the EU strategy for social innovation. Hence, the purpose was "to strengthen the foundations for other researchers, policy-makers and practitioners to help develop the field of social innovation"¹. TEPSIE undertook different mapping exercises, reviewed theories, models and methods and identified gaps in existing practices and policies. Finally, the project pointed towards the priorities for future strategies. While TEPSIE's work certainly contributed to further understanding and theoretical foundation of social innovation, the definition of social innovation used in the project is quite similar to the normative definition used by the European Commission, which understands social innovation as an innovation social in its ends and its means. Hence, according to TEPSIE's definition, social innovation is about "[...] new solutions (products, services, models, markets, processes etc.) that simultaneously meet a social need (more effectively than existing solutions) and lead to new or improved capabilities and relationships and better use of assets and resources. In other words, social innovations are both good for society and enhance society's capacity to act" (The Young Foundation, 2012, p. 18).

In contrast, the large-scale research project SI-DRIVE: Social Innovation – Driving Force of Social Change (2014-2017) defines social innovation as "a new combination or figuration of practices in areas of social action, prompted by certain actors or constellations of actors with the goal of better coping with needs and problems than is possible by using existing practices" (Howaldt et al., 2014, p. 9). While the

¹ <http://www.tepsie.eu>

definitions address new or better solutions in the process dimension of social innovation, they differ in their interpretation whether the impact created is desirable or not, and whether a normative or analytical perspective is more appropriate for understanding social innovation. As of now, the majority of research builds upon a variant of one of these two approaches.

SI-DRIVE, which is coordinated by TU Dortmund University, focuses on three main objectives (Howaldt et al., 2014):

- integrating theories and methodologies to advance understanding of social innovation,
- conducting a global mapping of social innovations (which addresses different social, economic, cultural, historical and religious contexts in eight major world regions),
- developing policy recommendations (as a process based on discussion with policy-makers and practitioners on the basis of in-depth analysis and case studies in seven policy fields).

SI-DRIVE research ambitions go beyond the goals of previous projects as its work is not only aimed at better understanding social innovation through theoretical and empirical research, but seeks to answer the question of how social innovation relates to social change. Thus, it puts the research topic of social innovation in a wider context, emphasising its meaning for society as a whole.

Another important characteristic of SI-DRIVE is that it does not limit its geographical scope to Europe, but explicitly underlines the necessity of investigating social innovation as a phenomenon, which is increasingly emerging on global scale. The project's consortium as well as its advisory board include partners from more than 30 countries and all continents.

In parallel to SI-DRIVE, another large-scale research project called TRANSIT, coordinated by DRIFT from the Netherlands, aims at developing a Transformative Social Innovation Theory of middle-range with a focus on empowerment and change in society. The project is structured around the four thematic areas of governance, social learning, funding and monitoring and focuses on the micro-level of local and transnational initiatives in Europe and Latin America as well as the role of macro trends in society (e.g. financial crisis, climate change, ICT-revolution), referred to as 'game changers'.

In TRANSIT's research approach the theory of Transformative Social Innovation is formulated "in a dynamic and iterative process that builds on existing theory, grounds the emerging theory in in-depth case studies and tests it through a meta-analysis of survey data. In this process, the research team continuously interacts with social innovators, social entrepreneurs, policymakers and scientists in a number of workshops applying and reviewing the emerging theory. Further outputs of this process include working papers, training tools, policy and practice briefs for social innovators, entrepreneurs, researchers and policymakers"².

² www.transitsocialinnovation.eu

Since the beginning, the SI-DRIVE and TRANSIT projects have both developed a close exchange and co-operation which has significantly contributed to the development of a community of researchers who work on social innovation concepts and theories. Concretely, this cooperation mainly concerns the organisation of joint scientific events such as workshops and conferences and participation in publications. SI-DRIVE and TRANSIT's project partners have increasingly come to the fore as leading institutions in the area of social innovation research on concepts and theories. In the following, we briefly present some of the institutions which have particularly contributed to the development of social innovation research on concepts and theories as well as to the formation of an international community in this field.

The Centre for Social Innovation³ in Vienna (Zentrum für soziale Innovationen, ZSI) was founded in 1990 and is one of the first organisations with an explicit focus on social innovation research from both a European and global perspective. ZSI uses a transdisciplinary approach in different areas of action. The centre's work combines research, consulting, network coordination and education into an overall concept. "ZSI generates, disseminates, and applies knowledge and skills in thematic areas that relate to meeting the grand societal challenges of our time. In these thematic areas, ZSI acts on different spatial levels from local to global." The Centre is organised along three departments: Work & Equal Opportunities, Research Policies & Development and Technology & Knowledge. ZSI has actively participated in development of social innovations in different policy areas and its work has been important in order to make social innovation visible as a central topic of societal development far beyond the borders of Austria.

The Young Foundation⁴, based in London, is a centre for social innovation, which engages with government, business and the community to build new movements, institutions and companies that tackle the structural causes of inequality. Its work covers a range of contemporary issues including health, ageing, education, communities and housing, youth leadership, and wellbeing. The Young Foundation works across the UK and internationally. Its activities include research, creation of new organisations and supporting others to do the same through capacity-building programmes and investment for social ventures. Since 2008, the Young Foundation's work has been important in shaping European policies on social innovation, entrepreneurship and investment. It has participated in major pan-European projects on social innovation including TEPsIE, TRANSITION, MD and SI-DRIVE. It has also played an important part in efforts to consolidate the many different networks, projects and research activities that have emerged around the concept of social innovation in recent years.

TU Dortmund University (TUDO), with its social research centre Sozialforschungsstelle⁵ (sfs), is one of the oldest and one of the largest social research institutes in Germany. Its research areas include Labour and Education in Europe, Services and Societal Change and Sustainable Shaping of Technology

³ www.zsi.at

⁴ www.youngfoundation.org

⁵ www.sfs.tu-dortmund.de

and Organisation, among others. With social innovation being its main topic, sfs has been working on academic research on social innovation, having its focus on the field of theory and methodology development. Through its participation in international research projects, such as SI-DRIVE (lead partner) and SIMPACT, Sozialforschungsstelle's work has been focused on understanding the international dimension of social innovation and its theoretical concepts and investigating social innovation as new social practices and their imitation processes in order to better understand how social innovations diffuse in society. Against this background, the centre has been working on an analytical concept of social innovation and on its theoretical foundations with a special focus on social practice theory.

The Dutch Research Institute For Transitions⁶ (DRIFT) at the Erasmus University Rotterdam is well-known for its work in the field of Sustainability Transitions and Transition Management. It combines research on sustainability transitions, policy, governance and (social) innovation, with consultancy and training programmes for governmental institutions, businesses and intermediary organisations. DRIFT has been involved in local, national and international projects concerned with health, youth, urban planning, energy, water, food and various other sectors. DRIFT approaches social innovation as a broader societal process that tackles urgent societal challenges, not only through market and state actors but also, and especially, through civil society. The institute has two main objectives: advancing transition theory and influencing transitions towards more sustainable pathways.

SINNERGIAC Social Innovation⁷ is a research centre, established in 2012 and promoted by the University of the Basque Country as part of the strategy of the EUSKAMPUS – Campus of International Excellence. Located in San Sebastián, SINNERGIAC was set up as a knowledge organisation organised around an interdisciplinary team that is headed by university researchers and also consisting of other professionals who are specialised in training practices as well as intervention and knowledge transfer in the area of social innovation. SINNERGIAC's particular competence has been development of methodologies to measure impact of social innovations.

Beyond the European borders, we can find two outstanding social innovation research centres in Canada, a country with a long tradition in this area. The Centre de recherche sur les innovations sociales⁸ (Center for research on social innovations – CRISES) is an inter-university and multidisciplinary research centre based in Montreal. It brings together about sixty researchers, each of whom has an affiliation with one of the following eight institutions: Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Université du Québec en Outaouais (UQO), Université Laval, Université de Sherbrooke, Concordia University, HEC Montréal, Université de Montréal and Université du Québec à Chicoutimi. CRISES was founded in 1986 by Benoît Lévesque and Paul R. Bélanger. Since 2001, CRISES has been a regroupement stratégique (strategic alliance) funded by the Fonds Québécois de Recherche sur la Société et la Culture (FQRSC). The members of CRISES come from a variety of disciplines: anthropology, geography,

⁶ www.drift.eur.nl

⁷ <http://www.sinnergiak.org>

⁸ <http://crises.uqam.ca/>

history, mathematics, philosophy, industrial relations, management sciences, economics, political science, sociology and social work. They study and analyse innovation and social change in three complementary areas: territory, quality of life and work and employment.

The Waterloo Institute for Social Innovation and Resilience⁹ (WISIR) seeks to generate trans- and interdisciplinary knowledge about social innovations and the social innovation processes (the dynamics of learning, adaptation and resilience). The institute's approach is to pursue collaborative research and projects that bridge University of Waterloo departments, involve researchers from around the world, and engage those beyond academia. WISIR seeks to mobilise this knowledge through a range of new curriculum offerings and training opportunities – both within and outside of a university setting, including the Graduate Diploma in Social Innovation. WISIR researchers are focused on three related research areas: cross-scale transformations in complex systems, indigenous innovations, and new theories and methods in social innovations.

In the US, Stanford University's Center for Social Innovation¹⁰ was founded in 1999. It expanded the work of the Stanford Graduate School of Business to a larger audience of executives in different parts of the world through research, education, and community outreach. The Center participated in the launch of a number of academic centers for social innovation around the world and the creation of the White House Office for Social Innovation in the United States in 2009. Located at the same university, the Stanford Center on Philanthropy and Civil Society (Stanford PACS) develops and shares knowledge to improve philanthropy, strengthen civil society and effect social change. It has become particularly well-known in the international social innovation research community thanks publishing the Stanford Social Innovation Review¹¹ (SSIR).

Most of institutions described above (especially those from Europe) act as partners in different research projects. Some of them are also organised in the European School of Social Innovation¹² (ESSI). ESSI was founded in October 2011 in the aftermath of the first global scientific conference on social innovation: Challenge Social Innovation, held in Vienna, in September of the same year. The conference adopted the Vienna Declaration on the most relevant topics of social innovation research¹³. In its introduction the declaration stipulates: "The tracks of international research on innovation demonstrate that the technology-oriented paradigm – shaped by the industrial society – does not cover the broad range of innovations indispensable in the transition from an industrial to a knowledge and services-based society: Such fundamental societal changes require the inclusion of social innovations in a paradigm shift of the innovation system." Based on this assertion, ESSI was formed to assist and enhance a holistic concept of innovation and to create new spaces for social innovation research built on concepts and theories.

⁹ www.wisironline.ca

¹⁰ <https://www.gsb.stanford.edu/faculty-research/centers-initiatives/csi>

¹¹ <https://ssir.org/>

¹² <https://www.essi-net.eu/>

¹³ http://www.net4society.eu/_media/Vienna-Declaration_final_10Nov2011.pdf

Another milestone in the development of an international community of researchers in this field has been the creation of the European Public & Social Innovation Review¹⁴ (EPSIR), edited by SINNER-GIAK Social Innovation. This external double-blind peer reviewed and interdisciplinary biannual journal carries theoretical and empirical articles, case studies and provocative papers to disseminate new knowledge, practices and experiences in the public and social innovation fields. EPSIR's editorial board includes a number of representatives of Europe's leading institutions in social innovation research (on concepts and theories). It is the first attempt to establish a European scientific journal on social innovation.

Starting from the Vienna Conference "Challenge Social Innovation" in 2011, a new conference format has been developed bringing together the global research community on social innovation. There have been a number of conferences (organised by a network of partners in London 2013 and Vienna 2015 and Brussels 2017 in a biannual cycle with an explicit focus on concepts and theories building the core of an upcoming scientific community in the field of social innovation. At the same time, the International Social Innovation Research Conference¹⁵ (ISIRC), an annual format, which has achieved sustainability organising its 9th edition in 2017, is just recently becoming a conference dedicated to social innovation research in a broader sense, not limited to the topic of social entrepreneurship, as it used to be at the beginning.

Altogether, we can say that after a long period of almost non-existent or largely neglected conceptual and theoretical debate, contours of an autonomous research field (and its community) are becoming visible. Without a doubt, social innovation research on concepts and theories is still far away from becoming an established research field, such as e.g. Innovation Studies (for the development of that scientific field, see Fagerberg and Verspagen, 2009). However, with a common research object, a shared knowledge basis and a working communication structure, it has already started developing some of the key features of such a scientific field with a community of researchers. Finally, it will very much depend on the further evolution of the scientific debate, which is the topic of the next section.

2.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

Social innovation research relates to different areas, eight of them presented in this report. There is a huge diversity of research strands which enriches the debate on the one hand, but also a remarkable fragmentation of social innovation as a research field which has made its development a difficult issue, on the other hand. Hence, as one of the experts who participated in the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey (2017) put it, it is not about having one scientific concept for social innovation, but "what is

¹⁴ <http://pub.sinnergiak.org/index.php/esir/index>

¹⁵ <http://www.isirconference.com/>

important is the recognition of social innovation as a scientific field”. One important difference between the current situation and the turn of the century is that such a field has become widely recognized.

Another important difference lies in the emergence of approaches, which are not normative in their understanding of social innovation (Rüede & Lurtz, 2012). Increasingly, in scientific debates, a normative comprehension of social innovation, which focuses on added value in sense of 'doing good action in and for society', and a sociological approach, which defines them as a creative, collaborative and targeted change of social practices, are facing each other (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). This debate has been crucial in moving further social innovation research on concepts and theories. It has been through the introduction of the analytical, non-normative perspective that social innovation has been increasingly understood as a scientific topic. Although there is still a strong presence of normative approaches in social innovation research, growing awareness of the ambiguity of social innovations as novel solutions, which can have positive impact on certain target groups while disadvantaging others, is an important development compared to earlier days.

Therefore, in recent years the debate about how the 'social' in social innovation is understood has been an important driver for the development of this research field, but also particularly for social innovation research on concepts and theories. This debate is not entirely new as there have always been different understandings of 'social'. Some scholars tended to define it through social relations, while others understood 'social' in terms of societal impact (Ayob et al., 2016). However, what was largely missing was an explicit focus on the innovation itself. While most research was focused on the changes introduced as a result of a social innovation, one important question remained disregarded for a long time: what does an innovation consist of?

Building on the works of German scholars such as Zapf (1989) and Gillwald (2000), but also referring to US American authors like Ogburn (1964) and Brooks (1982), Howaldt and Schwarz (2010) introduce a sociologically grounded concept of social innovation, with the new manifesting itself not “in the medium of technological artefacts, but at the level of social practices” (Howaldt et al., 2010, p. 34), thus emphasising that there is “an intrinsic difference between technological and social innovations” (Howaldt, Kopp and Schwarz 2015, p. 17), which has to do with the nature of technological innovations as artefacts and of social innovations as – intangible – social practices. Social innovations are defined as “targeted new combination or new configuration of social practices” (Howaldt, Kopp and Schwarz 2015, p. 36). At the same time, Howaldt and Schwarz (2017) emphasise that normative approaches such as, for example, the Capabilities Approach can also contribute to further theoretical foundation of social innovation.

During the first decade of the century, Mulgan et al. (2007) had introduced a concept of social innovation with a significant normative element, referring to “innovative activities and services that are motivated by the goal of meeting a social need and that are predominantly developed and diffused through organisations whose primary purposes are social” (p. 8). This definition of social innovation, which can be found within the second most highly cited publication on social innovation in the period 2004-2008

(Ayob et al. 2016, p. 645) is interesting in at least two regards. First, it has largely influenced the social innovation debate in both research and practice, with the European Commission adopting this perspective and defining social innovations as “innovations that are both social in their ends and in their means” (European Commission, 2010). Secondly, it locates social innovations in the ‘social’ sector, understanding it as domain of NGOs, social enterprises and other non-profit organisations, thus putting less focus on other societal sectors, namely government, economy and academia.

Hence, alongside with the debate on normative and analytical concepts and definitions, advancing towards a systemic understanding of social innovation has become another central topic in social innovation research on concepts and theories. Moving the field further towards a comprehensive and integrated concept, which includes all societal sectors and actors, different research areas and fields of application, has been an important task of the project SI-DRIVE. “Theoretical Approaches to Social Innovation – A Critical Literature Review”, the first constitutive publication of the research project SI-DRIVE, analyses different concepts related to social innovation and shows how according to these multiple foci social innovation is related to social change (Howaldt, Butzin, Domanski, & Kaletka, 2014). The review reaffirms the assumption that the concept of social innovation cannot be limited to one focus, be it social entrepreneurship or social economy, and demonstrates that widening the perspective is crucial for understanding social innovation. Hence, it makes an important contribution in terms of liberating social innovation from the silo of the third sector and opening it up to other areas of the society. Furthermore, it emphasises the necessity for research and practice to acknowledge the different rationales and interests that diverse actors from different societal sectors usually have when participating in innovation processes.

The global mapping of social innovation initiatives conducted in the framework of SI-DRIVE demonstrates that social innovation processes and the underlying resources, capabilities and constraints correspond with the actors and sectors of the social innovation ecosystem (Howaldt et al., 2016). This includes a new role of public policy and government for creating suitable framework and support structures, the integration of resources of the economy and civil society as well as supporting measures by science and universities (e.g. education for social innovation performance, know-how transfer). The main questions evolving from SI-DRIVE’s theoretical review are: How can we enhance the ‘innovation capacity of society’ and ‘how can we empower citizens’? Which resources and capabilities are necessary for the development of social innovations? How can these resources and capabilities be used for diffusion, adaptation and imitation of innovations?

The absence of a comprehensive innovation policy, which includes social innovations and not only technological innovations, corresponds with what some consider to be the ‘low maturity status’ of the social innovation ecosystems. While social innovation initiatives and practices have drawn a lot of attention within the last years in the different world regions, being imitated by manifold actors and networks of actors and diffused widely through different societal sub-areas, the ecosystem of social innovation “is in very different stages of development across Europe, however. In all countries, though, the ecosystem

is under development and there are a number of important factors enabling the development of social innovation, including important support and impetus from the EU” (Boelman & Heales, 2015, p. 7). One of the major challenges will be the development of these ecosystems.

This also raises the question of the role of universities in social innovation processes. The marginal engagement of research and education facilities is in strong contrast to their essential role as knowledge providers in classical innovation processes and as one actor of the triple helix model. That means that currently we find an uncompleted ecosystem of social innovation (quadruple helix) with one important pillar missing. It will be a major challenge for the development of social innovation to ensure a much higher involvement of research and education facilities. This also includes the question of new modes of knowledge production and scientific co-creation of knowledge aiming at an integration of practitioners and social innovators in the innovation processes (Howaldt et al., 2016).

The results of the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey confirm this view. One of the experts emphasises the importance of acknowledging the link between higher education institutions and civil society-based organisations for knowledge mobilization “as a condition for the co-building of a knowledge favouring creativity and Social Innovation”, adding that according to research findings knowledge “for social innovation must result from the merging of different types of knowledge (academic, citizen-based, professional...)”.

It has become increasingly evident, that while one approach in social innovation research on concepts and theories focuses on novel solutions (including technological innovations) for solving specific problems of vulnerable social groups, another approach places social innovations in a broader context, with new solutions which can be relevant for the society as a whole or its different parts. This leads us to another central topic in social innovation research on concepts and theories: the relation between social innovation and social change. This is the central theme of both large research projects, SI-DRIVE and TRANSIT. Through its publication “Theoretical Approaches to Social Innovation”¹⁶, SI-DRIVE provided a multidisciplinary literature review of existing theoretical and conceptual strands on social innovation and its relationship to social change, thus formulating, multidisciplinary hypotheses, research foci and questions. Here, a recourse to the work of Gabriel Tarde highlights the importance of social innovations “as a central element of a non-deterministic explanation of social change and a key element of social transformation processes. Since Tarde places the practices of imitation – and its laws – at the centre of his theory of social development, reference to the associated micro foundation of social phenomena provides vital input into an integrative theory of innovation.” (Howaldt et al., 2014, p. 26). According to this, a social innovation theory must examine the manifold and varied imitation streams, and decode their logics and laws. “From this perspective, the focus is always on social practice, since it is only via social practice that the diverse inventions etc. make their way into society and thus become the object of acts of imitation. Social practice is a central component of a theory of transformative social change, in

¹⁶ https://www.si-drive.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/D1_1-Critical-Literature-Review.pdf

which the wide variety of everyday inventions constitute stimuli and incentives for reflecting on and possibly changing social practices.” (Howaldt et al., 2014, p. 26)

TRANSIT’s work seeks to understand the transformative potential of social innovation. According to the project’s approach, “societal transformation is shaped and produced by particular patterns of interaction between social innovation, system innovation, game-changers and narratives of change” (Avelino et al., 2014, p. 8). TRANSIT analyses how individual actors, initiatives and networks “contribute to this process through different forms of governance, social learning, resourcing, and monitoring” (ibid.). The idea is to integrate this model into a social-theoretically grounded perspective on social change, understood in terms of transformation of social practices.

Among research topics that need to be further addressed, experts who participated in the SIC Research Landscape Survey and in the breakout session, mentioned the following:

- A longitudinal understanding of the life spans of social change organisations and their interplay with the institutional environments, for example with regards to institutional conditions (regulation etc.) for effective governance and financing of social innovation;
- Institutional theory – particularly how various societal and local Influences shape the feasibility of social innovation;
- Understanding social innovation organisations as hybrid organisations that seek to combine potentially conflicting goals, and how such tensions can be harnessed;
- A theory of social innovation that picks apart all stages of the innovation process, from the nature of the social problem, its formulation, and the development and reception of the solution and its scalability;
- The relationship between social innovation on the one hand and technical and commercial innovation on the other hand;
- The role of markets as well as policy;
- Methodological solutions on the impact measurement of SI (Combining various methodological approaches such as SRI/Social Return on Investment, Social policy experimentation);
- With an increasing importance and wide acceptance of social innovation, more and different actors are becoming involved in social innovation processes, including institutionalisation processes, making power relations in an increasingly contested field are an emerging field of research.
- Ambiguities of social innovation are still largely neglected as a research topic and need further scrutinising.

2.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

Social innovation research on concepts and theories often consists of case studies and therefore has a strong qualitative element. Usually it relies on desk research and interviews. However, the mapping

method, sometimes involving relatively high case numbers, has increasingly become an important element of social innovation research, also allowing for quantitative analyses, such as SI-DRIVE's global mapping of 1005 social innovation initiatives.

Another example is BENISI¹⁷ (Building a European Network of Incubators for Social Innovation). Its mapping includes more than 300 cases – categorised by six societal trends – from around 30 countries: “As the opportunities for scaling is a leading question in BENISI's approach, the scaling trajectory is another important criterion for the categorisation of the cases. The approach is based on the theoretically grounded framework by Weber, Kröger & Lambrich (2012) and distinguishes between four kinds of trajectories, namely (1) capacity-building (scaling alone, no need for adaptation), (2) branching (scaling alone, adaptation necessary), (3) dissemination of knowledge (scaling with partners, no need for adaptation) and (4) affiliation (scaling with partners, adaptation necessary).” (Pelka and Terstriep, 2016, p. 8). A comprehensive overview of mapping methodologies in social innovation research has been provided by Pelka and Terstriep who analyse 17 international projects. Within this exercise, “mapping refers to a variety of understandings of visualization – not all of them apply a spatial dimension, but envisage to ‘map’ qualitative aspects of the observed social innovations” (Pelka and Terstriep, 2016, p. 3).

The results of this mapping of social innovation maps reveal that there is little orientation towards the dimension of target groups or users of social innovations: “While many of the applied definitions of social innovation comprise specific target groups as a component, the distinct mapping approaches do not actively involve these in the mapping activities.” (Pelka and Terstriep, 2016, p. 12) Furthermore, most mapping activities do not include reflections on impact social innovations. Finally, “the majority of mapping efforts apply qualitative methods and in particular case studies for data collection resulting in small-N (mostly below 300 cases). We find the collection of quantitative data to be an exception in recently finalised and ongoing mapping activities. Combining qualitative and quantitative data in mixed method research designs by means of triangulation has the potential to enhance the validity of the data collected.” (Pelka and Terstriep, 2016, p. 13)

2.5 IMPACT

As demonstrated above, the taking-up of social innovation in policies at the EU (but in some cases, also national levels) enabled social innovation research to be conducted in different areas. Although, the impact of the most recent generation of research projects on practice and also especially on policy through concrete policy recommendations cannot be assessed yet, establishing the link between social innovation research on concepts and theories is an achievement itself. There is a bigger awareness among practitioners and policymakers regarding the importance of social innovation in addressing

¹⁷ <http://www.benisi.eu/>

grand societal challenges. Empirical data available through extensive research initiatives make social innovation indispensable on policy agendas and constitutes an important basis for further action.

As one of the experts who participated in the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey (2017) put it: “By clarifying the specific characteristics of social innovations, their actual and potential contributions to society and the way that existing markets, policies and institutions’ influence of social Innovation, research has already opened for a much more conducive policy environment, while diffusing information and inspiring especially young people around the world to engage in social Innovation In practice.”

It has not been only an increasing awareness of social innovation in practice and policy, but also in science. Theoretical and conceptual discussion has intensified, with more attempts to systematise diverse activities, to achieve better theoretical foundation of the term from different theoretical perspectives and establish it as an analytical concept with a clear defined object of study based on interest in knowledge (e.g. Pol & Ville, 2009; Mulgan, 2012; Moulaert et al., 2013; Cajaiba-Santana, 2013; Howaldt et al., 2014; Pue et al., 2016). Consequently, the social-theoretical foundation of the term for the purpose of a comprehensive social innovation theory – as an important part of a theory of social change or social transformation process – is more and more in focus of research interest (Franz et al., 2012; Nicholls et al., 2015, Klein et al., 2016).

Certain progress in scientific debate on social innovation in recent years has also made the topic more attractive for other (related) research fields. Hence, the need for focusing on social innovation can be detected in areas such as Innovation Studies or sustainability and transition research. This trend can be observed through publications and conferences. For example, the “European Forum for Studies of Policies for Research and Innovation” (Eu-SPRI), a renowned international network in the area of Innovation Studies, has repeatedly included tracks on social innovation in the programme of annual its conference. Another significant issue is that social innovation is less and less perceived as a synonym to social entrepreneurship. It has become “a valuable concept in social policies, in general (health, labour market, education, etc.) as well as in economics (workplace innovation)”. In addition, through social innovation research conducted in recent years, relevant knowledge has been generated regarding importance of partnerships between stakeholders to set up social innovations as well as necessity of linking policies to successfully contribute to social change.

However, we must acknowledge that it is still debated in research and practice, what exactly makes an innovation a social innovation, under which conditions social innovations develop and lead to social change. It is controversially discussed what 'social' means, but also the meaning of 'innovation', its substance, its realisation, its function and its impact (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Nevertheless, as Ayob et al. (2016) put it, “the fact that social innovation is contested, conceptually imprecise and used in ways which we may see as disagreeable should not dissuade us from engaging with the concept” (p. 636). At the same time, in the civil societal and political discourse still dominates the position, that social innovations are mainly socially desirable solutions, lifestyles and projects and prac-

tices, initiated and carried out through bottom-up activities, new social movements and/or social entrepreneurship activities. As we have shown above, in the scientific engagement with the topic, normative and non-normative approaches and thus different, partially inconsistent and mainly descriptive definitions are facing each other. In consequence, there are significant issues of interpretation, as well as inconsistent understanding in both political and scientific institutions.

Certainly, many research questions still remain unanswered. Nevertheless, the conceptual debate has significantly advanced in recent years, making social innovation a contested concept. Although social innovation cannot be defined in a merely normative way and the sociological perspective emphasises that that social innovations are not 'good' per se, but ambivalent in their impact, both normative and analytical concepts can mutually enrich each other regarding the theoretical foundation of the concept. For example, such a perspective can help advance towards further conceptualisation and analysis of social innovation as a generative mechanism of transformative social change (Archer, 2015).

Within the framework of the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, it was also emphasised that social innovation research on concepts and theories must run in parallel to social innovation practice in order to enable induction/deduction, with theories providing a conceiving and conclusive frame and empirical research measuring successful implementation and practices for up-scaling. Social innovation research has not succeeded in getting deeper insights into the various impacts of social innovations.

Regarding the impact of social innovation research on (social) innovation policy, one important task will be to develop a clear language in order to communicate research findings on a topic, which is still largely unknown to many policy-makers and those who work with them. Furthermore, development of a social innovation research agenda in Europe (CoSIRA, 2016) remains a huge challenge. On the one hand, such an agenda is highly dependent on funding provided through the European Commission (which has already diminished in this area after a boom some years ago), on the other hand, the fragmentation of the social innovation research community with different goals and concepts is an obstacle on the way towards a joint social innovation research agenda.

2.6 CONCLUSIONS

With the European Commission discovering social innovation as an important topic for overcoming the economic crisis, social innovation research on concepts and theories received a crucial impulse in order to evolve into an autonomous research area in Europe. In consequence, the first features of a community of researchers in this area became visible thanks to research projects funded through EC's central research programmes FP7 and Horizon 2020. The formation of a community of researchers (certainly with a number of sub-communities) which transcends the limits of individual disciplines and research traditions has been a notable achievement in this regard. A growing community of researchers is ad-

addressing the topic research on concepts and theories in journals and edited volumes and at joint conferences.

Hence, after a long period of almost non-existent or largely neglected conceptual and theoretical debate, contours of an autonomous research field and its community are becoming visible. With a common research object, a shared knowledge basis and a working communication structure it has already started developing some of the key features of such a scientific field with a community of researchers. With such a community, which is explicitly dedicated to social innovation research on concepts and theories, the conditions for the entire research field to move forward have improved. Against this background, it can be expected that social innovation research will be able to better contribute to meeting grand societal challenges. In addition, through an identifiable community of researchers, exchange with policy-makers and all those involved in social innovation practice will become more targeted. Research projects such as SI-DRIVE and TRANSIT have played a central role in moving forward social innovation research on concepts and theories. Also, increasing debate on more normative and more analytical perspectives of social innovation has been an important driver of this research field, showing new possibilities for developing a concept, which combines both views.

Regarding the main target of the project Social Innovation Community (SIC), which seeks to build an international community of all those who work in the area social innovation, we can say that, first, a community of researchers working together on social innovation research on concepts and theories is now existing and keeps on growing, second, this community is generally well connected to actors and communities in practice and policy and third it is also directly linked to diverse thematic areas, labelled as networks, presented in the following eight chapters of this report.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
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3 Public Sector Innovation

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3.1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing complexity of Governance processes to address complex societal problems involving public organizations, private actors, and the civil society has been a recurrent topic in the last two decades, opening the door to the importance of Public Sector Innovation in recent years. Whereas private sector innovation is related to the capacity of private organizations and actors to create private value, innovation process inside the Public Sector are associated with the creation of public value in different arenas: policies, services, public infrastructures, public management, etc. (Moore, 2005). Thus, Public Sector innovation is most interested in, and related with the production of social (satisfaction of social needs, social cohesion, social capital), political or economic values (growth and employment programs, transparency, effectiveness and efficiency in public sector finance, etc.) inside the public sphere (Moore, 2005; Torfing, 2016, p. 35).

According to Geoff Mulgan (2007), *“Public Sector Innovation is about new ideas that work at creating public value. The ideas have to be at least in part new (rather than improvements); they have to be taking up (rather than just being good ideas); and they have to be useful”* (Mulgan, 2007, p. 6).

Christian Bason (2010) defines Public Sector Innovation *“as the process of creating new ideas and turning them into value for society. It concerns how politicians, public leaders, and employees make their visions of a desired new state of the world into reality. The concept of innovation therefore places a large-sharp focus on whether the organization is able to generate and select the best possible ideas, implement them effectively, and ensure they create value”* (Bason, 2010, p. 34).

To achieve public value for society, the public sector needs to interact and engage with a diversity of actors, including social entrepreneurs, social innovators, and third sector organizations, as well as the private sector, service users, citizens and communities (Bazurli et al., 2014). This is the path to find new solutions to social and economic challenges, new solutions that should be created “with the people” and for the public good of “the people” (Bason, 2010, p.8). It is in this context where social innovation comes into play as an excellent ally. As defined by Harry & Albury (2009), *“social innovation is innovation for the social and public good”* (Harry & Albury, 2009, p. 16). This is the stage where social innovation meets public sector innovation; a stage where network governance and governing networks can find a mutual space of interaction as an answer to social and political complexity.

3.2 NETWORKS & THEMATIC SCOPE

Governance Networks are conceived as *“more or less stable patterns of social relations between mutually dependant actors, which cluster around a policy problem, a policy program, an/or a set of resources and which engage, are sustained, and are changed through a series of interactions”* (Klijn & Koopperi-

an, 2016, p. 21). These networks deal with complex decision making processes in different areas: public infrastructure works, urban regeneration, social security, healthcare and social services, policy implementation and law enforcement, or the management and prevention of natural disasters, crisis, etc. (Klijn & Koopperian, 2016).

These networks can be initially conceived as networks involving Government, businesses, and the civil society or more precisely networks that are integrated by public servants, policymakers, policy advisors, practitioners, private companies, non-profit organizations, social entrepreneurs, social innovators, academia, experts etc., coming from different Public Administrations (Supranational, State, Region, Locality) from the same or different countries; a complex setting of interactions where these diversity of actors share information about different approaches and methodologies through complex decision making processes in order to find innovative solutions to wicked social, political, economic and problems. We can find an example of this kind of networks in the **Australian Public Sector Innovation Network**, created in 2009, to assist and engage different public servants who would apply innovative methodologies to the planning and design of public services; or the **Government Innovators Network**, located in the J.F.Kennedy School of Government at Harvard University.

At the European level, we can find some examples of potential networks and institutions at supranational, national, regional, and local levels.

In the supranational level we can locate the following:

1. **OECD Observatory of Public Sector Innovation (OPSI)**, chaired by Canada and France, collects, analyses and shares different innovative experiences and ideas of PSI from all over the world, giving guidance and practical advice to different countries on how to innovate inside the public sector. <https://www.oecd.org/governance/observatory-public-sector-innovation/about/>
2. The **European Public Administration Network (EUPAN)** that is “an informal network of the Directors General responsible for Public Administration in the Member States of the European Union, the European Commission and observer countries”, which is mainly focused on “improving the performance, competitiveness and quality of European public administrations by developing new tools and methods, in the field of public administration, based on the exchange of views, experiences and good practices among EU Member States, the European Commission, observer countries and other organisations.” <http://www.eupan.eu/>.
3. The **European Institute of Public Administration** established in 1981 in Luxemburg and Barcelona, which provides training and high quality services of public officials to manage EU affairs. <http://www.eipa.eu/>.
4. **Design for Europe Public Sector Section** is focused on the growth of a community of practice around innovation and design in the public sector, by empowering networks, prioritizing the needs

of users to improve public services, and increasing the capabilities of public servants. Design for Europe also seeks to gather examples of best practices, by sharing different ideas, cases, and experiences across different sectors and disciplines. It works along Nesta, the 27eRegion (see below) and the Estonian Design Center. <http://designforeurope.eu/>

5. The **EUCLID network** was created in 2007, and is located in London. It is focused on building networks by reducing the gap between the civil society, practitioners and European Institutions, looking for impact on European policy design and peer learning strategies in the fields of capacity-building, social innovation, social entrepreneurship, and responsible research.

Operating at national level in the European context we can also find interesting examples in the form of specific agencies or social enterprises, which could become potential participants in the configuration of a PSI community. At this level we can find:

1. **My Society:** MySociety is a non-profit social enterprise created in the UK in 1996, which is focused on the use of online technologies to engage civil society in the design of public policies, empowering citizens through the use of participatory tools in the form of digital open platforms, democratic monitoring tools, etc. (<https://www.mysociety.org>).
2. **Governance International**, is a non-profit organization funded in 2002 in Birmingham, UK, that works in the delivery of tools, training, research, and peer learning around the world, transforming public services based on international good practice (<http://www.govint.org>).
3. **Kennisland** is an organisation located in Amsterdam and founded in 1999, which works with governments, businesses, knowledge institutions and social organizations, in different areas such as the innovation of public sector policies through more effective and efficient policy strategies, and social experimentation activities (social lab approach) involving, engaging and empowering citizens along government initiatives, among others. Kennisland is also focused on social innovation, as a way of creating new solutions that can improve public value in different social areas, through open collaborations with other organizations (www.kl.nl).
4. The **27eRegion** was created in France in 2008 to work along with the French Regional Governments in the innovation and re-examination of the ways in which public policies are created and implemented, especially at the Regional Government Level. The approach to the co-creation and co-design of public policies is tackled through the potential social innovation actions focused on a user centred perspective working with citizens on the re-definition and delivery of public services (<http://www.la27eregion.fr/>).
5. **Mindlab** is a cross-governmental innovation unit located in Copenhagen, Denmark and founded in 2002. This unit is integrated by different representatives of the Danish government. Mindlab is focused on the creation of innovative social solutions, acting as an incubator, which develops and or-

ganises different projects and experiments working together with public servants, citizens, and businesses in the identification of social problems and the development of policy recommendations (<http://mind-lab.dk/>).

In these contexts, the concept of Public Sector Innovation has grown wider due to the fact that the ultimate user (**bottom-up**) of public services and public policies are citizens, and that the innovation of public policies in a specific country or in the EU context, for example, is something that has an effect not only on its citizens, but also on other public and non-public organizations involved in their cross-country governance structure.

From an organisational point of view, these approaches to Public Sector Innovation have reflected upon these two conceptions: that the source of innovation and the construction of any type of innovative network in the public sector needs to come from a **top-down** conception and, therefore, be based on the sole inclusion of public servants, policymakers, practitioners and other experts; or, by contrary, that the importance of “users” (Von Hippel, 2005) in the development of any sort of innovative approach to public services from a **bottom-up** perspective, is a crucial input for an effective and successful change in the delivery of public services by raising their quality, reducing costs, and increasing transparency, openness, and participation, among other factors.

As a result, a hierarchical top-down bureaucratic approach towards innovation and governance in the public sector simply does not work. Increasing complexity between government interests, public organizations, private actors, non-public organizations, and citizens, requires the merging of both top-down and bottom-up approaches, when thinking about the construction of a community or “network of networks” in Public Sector Innovation. The delivery of public services and the setting up of policy goals has to adapt to different contexts globally and locally, and consequently the building and scope of a community of Public Sector Innovators in a European Context should be **multi-level** (European, national, regional, local), and **cross-country** oriented.

3.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

The dominant research topics addressed by the majority of the mentioned networks are oriented towards a bottom-up perspective and are mainly focused on the improvement of innovation governance methodologies and the reform of the public sector through collaborative innovation and interactive governance approaches (Torfing et al., 2012; Torfing 2016). These approaches generally involve a diversity of actors including social innovators and social entrepreneurs, citizens, public administrations, practitioners, civil servants, etc. Public Sector Innovation can be manifested in many different types innovation. According to Jacob Torfing (2016) we can divide Public Sector Innovation into (Torfing, 2016, p. 37):

1. **Service innovation:** new forms of services such as new training or unemployment programs, or delivery of services through digital-platforms, ICT, etc. This can also include the diffusion and scaling up of good practices, public procurement measures in the form of new regulations that can favour innovation inside the public sector and in public services.
2. **Organizational innovation:** new ways of organizing public bureaucracies through smart regulation such as the creation of specific agencies, empowerment of local governments, new methodologies to participate and co-create with citizens, creation of horizontal structures, etc.). These may also include public-private partnerships and new methods of collaborative governance.
3. **Policy innovation:** new objectives and assessment tools for the creation of new policies (e.g. active aging, preventive healthcare, workplace innovation, etc.), monitoring impact approaches, or increased organizational and institutional learning.

In the field of Public Social Policies the growing importance of third sector organizations has been crucial. The creation of new solutions and approaches that can respond efficiently, effectively, and transparently to the citizens' needs through the generation of public value, is a factor that has gained interest among public authorities, civil servants and practitioners. These needs have been expressed in the form of social policy challenges that have to be tackled. According to the Expert Group Report *"Powering European Public Sector Innovation: Towards a New Architecture"* (2013) on Public Sector Innovation developed by the European Commission:

"There are two huge challenges that European governments face in redefining how they can complement the private sector and the market in order to create public value and enhance employment and incomes: how to integrate 'the social' and how to enhance public entrepreneurship. Public services will have a strong cooperative and networked basis to them. However, the path towards the next public governance model is not straightforward: First, we do not know precisely what forms the new model will take, given vastly different national, economic and social contexts. Second, we do not know exactly what it will take to get there. The first is a question of what a 'social' model of governance entails in practice; the second is a question of how to orchestrate the innovation process itself" (European Commission, 2013, p. 31).

The complexity of the process of innovation and the influence of contextual historical and socioeconomic factors in the different countries and regions, is certainly an important challenge when trying to diffuse and scale-up good practices in the form of new governance models or social innovations in the Public Sector. Another fundamental gap in this arena is *"how to combine the legal obligation of governments to provide equal service standards to all citizens with diverging needs of citizens"* (European Commission, 2013, p. 32). In this sense, the importance of customising, adapting, and addressing different needs for different kinds of contextual circumstances affecting a diversity of citizens is growing more difficult. The

application of Big Data and e-governance mechanisms are important approaches that will help attending future needs in different fields such as: ageing population, unstable employment and uncertainty, health, environmental and sustainability challenges, social exclusion, poverty, education, etc.

Another important factor is that unresponsive regulatory frameworks hinder the capacity to experiment in different contexts. Moreover, funding for internal innovation, especially social innovation, continues to be tied to departmental budgets in many instances. In addition, there is still a shortage of risk capital for external, private-sector innovators to invest in the development of innovative public sector solutions. In this context, the inclusion of private sector organisations in collaborative governance approaches to innovation in the public sector is also crucial.

Some results of the **expert survey** also indicate there is an interest to know more about the specific factors that trigger and facilitate innovation in the public sector due to the bureaucratic nature of this one, which has traditionally rejected and resisted any innovative approach towards change. Other observations wonder about the sustainability and institutionalization process of innovations in the public sector, how can they be diffused and what kind of impact they have from a power relations perspective.

As a result, future research approaches to PSI and SI need to consider how they bring all these issues to the public arena by answering to different questions:

1. How exactly do we link social innovation to Public Sector Innovation?
2. What factors come into play when Public Organizations resist change?
3. How can we make Public Sector Innovation sustainable inside public organizations?
4. How can social innovation influence and help change social policies?
5. What are the drivers and barriers that affect the application of social innovative approaches to change and improve the Public Sector and Public Policies?
6. How do we identify and make use of social innovations and how can they influence social policy?
7. What kind of participative methodologies, tools, and impact measures can we identify in this process?

According to Christian Bason (2010) *“increasingly governments are recognizing the key role of social innovation” (...)* *“the rise of this interest within government is a sign that non-governmental or “third sector” organizations play a key role in society” (...)* *“ Governments collaborating effectively with social innovators have in many ways the same incentives for collaborating with business-but also different ones in some respects. Because third sector organizations are value-*

based and normative, rather than profit-maximising, they hold both additional potential and other types of barriers than firms” (Bason, 2010, p. 97).

Third sector organizations, social entrepreneurs and social innovators can acquire different perspectives and a more profound knowledge on the nature and contextual factors of social problems due to the fact that they deal with these problems on their daily bases, and as addressed by Bason, they are guided by different interests and rules not tied to bureaucratic processes (Bason, 2010). These handicaps can contribute in a big way to the process of co-creation and co-design of policymaking by contributing through a more clear and focused vision of the nature of contextual social challenges and their possible solutions.

3.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

The role of research in application of SI to PSI, therefore, needs to be conceived from a joined public service user (bottom-up input) and top-down output approach based on the creation of collaborative and participative perspectives to the innovative design and delivery of public policy and public services by Public Institutions and Administrations. In this context, it is important to mention Chris Ansell’s (2000) theoretical conception of the “networked polity” as an extension of democratic institutions through an inter-organizational and an intergovernmental network of actors based on different principles that are common to most European Policy Programmes: a bottom-up approach to policy-making based on public-private partnerships and programmed strategic actions which are supported by EU funded policy programs.

There are other similar theoretical approaches that can be mentioned such as “collaborative governance”; “public-private governance”; “networked governance”, “multi-stakeholder governance”; “New Public Governance” or “platforms for collaborative innovation”, among others (Torfing et al., 2012; Cartensen & Bason, 2012; Sorensen & Torfing, 2015; Klijn and Koppenjan, 2016; Torfing, 2016). Also, the creation of new tools and instruments for public and societal engagement in governance processes can be of great importance social innovations and social innovators can help public servants and public administrations, as well as social organizations, entrepreneurs, citizens, etc., to co-create, co-design, co-implement, and co-assess these policies through a networked approach. For example, the Toolkit on Public Engagement in Science developed in the context of the H2020 project Public Engagement Innovation (see <https://toolkit.pe2020.eu/this-toolkit/>) has been a useful attempt for the promotion of Public Engagement policies, measures and initiatives.

Most of the methodologies that are used in PSI are qualitative, such as:

- Interviews with users

- Workshops and interactive sessions based on co-production tools. These co-production tools may include the mapping of existing and new forms of innovation, the focus on activities with higher impact, experimentation and testing with users to scale and apply solutions, etc. Co-assessment, co-design, and co-delivery are important steps in this process.
- Focus groups
- Ethnographic studies and participatory observation
- Interactive Labs with public servants to define and develop needs and actions

The use of surveys and the co-design of key performance indicators to monitor progress are also useful methodologies. Other interesting methods involve critical analysis, funding measures directed to the selection and evaluation of certain portfolio of innovations, prize money (e.g. *Innovations in American Government Award* or the *European Public Sector Awards*) to the best social innovations, or practice programs with a group of organizations to conduct and co-create a structured innovation process focused on the innovative development of solutions to social challenges.

3.5 IMPACT

Important milestones have been reached through different European Research Projects and other initiatives having an important impact on the connection between Public Sector Innovation and social innovation:

1. The SI-DRIVE policy briefs on Education and Lifelong Learning, Social Innovation and Employment, Health and Social Care, or Poverty Reduction and Sustainable Development among others (seven in total) are important results that can help identify gaps, barriers, and challenging social needs in the design and implementation of public policies. The different sections that are included in these briefings can help us identify challenges, foresight results, significant policy issues and recommendations that can serve as important guides to track and map key factors inside public policy (www.si-drive.eu).
2. TEPSIE's Guide for Policymakers on "Growing Social Innovation" (2015) identifies the different sources of social innovation and potential facilitators of social innovation through the identification of the main components of a social innovation ecosystem that is supportive of social innovators and socially innovative organizations. These include framework conditions for the establishment of funding measures, procurement, new legal frameworks, measuring impact, capacity building methodologies, citizen engagement, digital technology, or increased support networking, among others (www.tepsie.eu/).

3. The collection of 20 transnational Networks that were studied in the TRANSIT (Transformative Social Innovation Theory) project can serve as interesting case studies or possible assets to be considered in Public Sector Innovation (<http://www.transitsocialinnovation.eu>).
4. “Design for Europe” project based on Public Sector Innovation to help build capabilities in the European Public Sector where Nesta, the 27e Region and the Estonian Design Centre are participating, is an interesting example project focused on identification of best practices, building networks and the use of tools and resources. Also involving NESTA, it is important to mention the I-Teams Report (2014) “Teams and Funds Making Innovation Happen all over the World” (designforeurope.eu).
5. Another important outcome is the LIPSE research project “Learning From Innovation in Public Sector Environments”, coordinated by the Erasmus University of Rotterdam, which studies the drivers and barriers of successful social innovations in the public sector. Comparative case studies on co-creation and citizen involvement in social innovation, literature reviews on PSI, Public Sector Innovation Indicators, or innovative outcomes of public private partnerships can be found (<http://www.lipse.org>).
6. The Co-production toolkit designed by Governance International for the improvement of public outcomes (<http://www.govint.org/our-services/co-production>).

Important weaknesses and shortcomings can be found in the monitoring impact of social innovations and their influence in public policies, and the creation of social innovation indicators. How do we evaluate public sector initiatives, and know which social innovations can have a major impact inside the public sector?

Although the SIMPACT (simpact-project.eu) and TEPSIE projects have had an explicit focus on measuring the social impact of welfare investment, outcome tools, and the construction of ex-ante impact approaches to social innovation investment measures, there is still a lot of unknown aspects in the design of quantifiable mechanisms to measure and monitor SI. Moreover, there is a knowledge gap on how the public sector can successfully evaluate the impact and implementation of new policies, government programs, the internal efficiency and transparency of their departments, as well as their internal management.

Applying and building measurable and tangible economic indicators and tools to analyse the impact of social innovation might not be the most appropriate answer to quantify and assess public value. It is not clear if we can apply economic indicators based on public investment measures, business angels, risk capital initiatives, etc., to tangibly guide the policy decision making process when addressing social policy. There is still a lot of ground that needs to be covered in this aspect.

3.6 CONCLUSIONS

Public Sector Innovation and social innovation are concerned with the collaborative creation and development of innovative solutions to social problems through the public engagement of a diversity of actors to create public and social value. This collaborative innovation approach can take the form of new public policies, new services, new forms of organization and internal management of the public sector, or new legislation and regulatory frameworks. These solutions can have multiple expressions and are dependent on contextual socioeconomic factors and regulations making innovative social problem solving a complex and interconnected process.

The importance of Governance Networks that can build, share, and diffuse knowledge on best governance practices and public sector innovations is also key to the achieve, sustain and institutionalize some degree of change in public sector organizations. Throughout this chapter we have reviewed some of the most relevant topics inside public sector innovation and their connection to social innovation and network governance approaches in Europe. We have also gone through some of the most relevant research projects relating public sector innovation and social innovation, and have taken a close look to some of the most important challenges to innovative social problem solving.

Moreover, along the elaboration of the present research landscape on Public Sector Innovation, we have reached some important conclusions about the possible dimension and scope of a potential Public Sector Innovation Network, its possible drivers and barriers, its main topics of interest, and the different methodologies that could be applied for the generation of knowledge and ideas in relation to its potential challenges and needs.

Regarding this matter, the implementation of new methods and approaches to policy making and public policies is necessary. The focus on co-creation and co-design methodologies to find innovative solutions to social problems and needs, can build a positive change in the governance model of the public sector, and the ways in which it generates public value with and for the people.

A governance network of this nature should be open to a wide range of actors, agents, and organisations, from public servants, policymakers and practitioners, to social innovators, public institutions, non-profit organizations, service users (citizens), social entrepreneurs, etc. Horizontal approaches are better than unilateral top-down or bottom-up perspectives.

Amongst the most important topics to be discussed and dealt with by such a network we stress out the significance of funding measures, procurement platforms, new legal frameworks, measuring and monitoring impact of SI and PSI, capacity building methodologies, citizen engagement and participation, digital technology and ICT, or increased support for the networks.

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**SOCIAL
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4 Digital Social Innovation

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4.1 INTRODUCTION

Digital Social Innovation according to the central study of the field, is "a type of social and collaborative innovation in which innovators, users and communities collaborate using digital technologies to co-create knowledge and solutions for a wide range of social needs and at a scale and speed that was unimaginable before the rise of the Internet" (Bria et al., 2015, p. 9).

It covers such technologies as open data infrastructures, knowledge and co-creation platforms, decentralized social networking, free software and open hardware, wireless sensor networks and others. For the purpose of this chapter, we need to distinguish between the concept or phenomenon of digital social innovation and the mapping and stocktaking project conducted for the European Commission (DSI4EU, 2017). When talking about the project, we use the acronym DSI whereas digital social innovation is used for the phenomenon at large. In order to remain open for *unusual suspects* it is important to keep the wider context in mind although this report cannot cover all the *open, virtual, Internet- and community-based* projects and initiatives that address social needs.

While the reports of the DSI project argue that there is limited knowledge on digital social innovators, organisations and activities, this mostly applies to the explicit heading of DSI. Virtual or online communities, (digital) networks of innovation, or open source initiatives have been investigated for decades under varied terminologies by varied technical and social science disciplines and also transdisciplinary approaches. Recently, internet science is emerging as a term for the study of internet-based social activity, and indeed, the *academic arm* of much digital social innovation. Even before the scope of social innovations increased through internet use, many digital social innovations have their roots in a longer tradition of *alternative media* and the appropriation and development of technology by various social movements and cultural avantgardes (Toret & Caleja, 2015).

As in other fields of social innovation, the boundaries between research and practice, the technological and the social, professionalism and activism, institutions and social movements are permeable. There is also an overlap between digital social innovation and social innovations in other areas that make use of digital technologies to further their purposes – in line with the ubiquity of digital technologies, digital elements may be found in most kinds of social innovations. In particular, digital social innovation overlaps with the domain of the sharing or collaborative economy. Platforms and networks also proliferate across societal domains. For example, the P2P Foundation, established in 2006, presents itself as a digital community also engaged in offline action (P2P Foundation, 2017). Arguably, after the originally 'digital' social innovations of open source, knowledge sharing platforms and social webs many of the recent digital social innovations and networks multiply their interactions and interfaces with the material world: integrating hardware, connecting neighbours in cities to share tools and skills, using crowdsourced data in disaster relief or supporting sustainable mobility or low-cost healthcare (Banerjee et al., 2016).

This report chapter is based on three sources:

- desk research (chiefly conducted in August/September 2016) with a particular focus on the European and European-funded landscape of dedicated digital social innovation project, creating an overview of projects, subjects and research practices and methodologies;
- a virtual breakout session on digital social innovation for which nine experts in the field registered but eventually, only three took part;
- and, to compensate, a series of informal interviews and conversations with ZSI project partners on hot and emerging research subjects at the DSI fair 2017 in Rome and the Captor consortium meeting.¹⁸

However, this report cannot provide an overview of the wider current debates on digitalisation, its societal impacts, and the socially innovative ways of addressing them, as they are pursued under headings of future of work, of the welfare state, the knowledge or platform economy, and so on. Indeed, there is a striking gap between the subjects of digital social innovation and digitalisation at large which appears to require more and wider social innovations, and the subject of digital social innovation itself. Where obvious connections to these subjects can be made, they are pointed out.

4.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

A key network under the explicit heading of DSI is represented on the website of www.digitalsocial.eu. It started as a mapping and stocktaking project conducted for the European Commission's DG CONNECT by a consortium of innovation, research and cultural organisations: British Nesta, Spanish ESADE's Centre for Innovation in Cities, the French Centre Pompidou's IRI Institut de Recherche et d'Innovation, the Dutch Waag Society, and British FutureEverything. This study has developed into a platform, which in March 2017 covers 813 projects of digital social innovation and 1,220 organisations (www.digitalsocial.eu). It is the obvious starting point for SIC's development of a Social Innovation Community of networks in Digital Social Innovation.

However, other projects and platforms are also relevant and can only be addressed briefly. The CHEST project is another FP7-funded project with an aim to "support the rapidly growing European community of technology and social entrepreneurs to advance ideas that focus on the use of digital technologies (such as open data, open knowledge, open hardware, and open networks) to deliver solutions to key societal challenges" (CHEST, 2017). This is run by a consortium of Italian IT service providers Engi-

¹⁸ We thank Johannes Klinglmayr of the Center for Mechatronics in Linz, coordinator of the ASSET project, Pauline Melis of the Waag Society and Christian Voigt, head of ZSI's "Technology & Knowledge" department. A special thank you is due to TUDO's Marthe Zirngiebl for her concise insights. All errors and misinterpretations are ours.

neering Ingegneria Informatica SpA and MagentaLab, PNO consultants, greenapes.com, a platform for sustainability, the European Institute for Participatory Media (EIPCM), the Scottish NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde, Fundacion Ciudadana Civio and Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya. The core of the action was a repeated call for ideas and initiatives that could receive up to EUR 60,000 seed funding to develop and prototype their ideas. Winners have been apps and platforms in areas of learning and education, environmental observation and data gathering, health, participation, payment, public procurement, recycling and crowdmapping and the funding of social innovation. In addition, CHEST provides online learning, a platform for ideas, and a network analytics tool for beneficiaries to assess interactions on the platform.

The D-CENT project (for Decentralised Citizens Engagement Technologies), funded by FP7 and finalized in 2016, focused on “developing the next generation of open source, distributed, and privacy-aware tools for direct democracy and economic empowerment” (D-CENT, 2017). It covered the tools for collaborative policy-making, voting and budgeting that were piloted in Finland, Iceland and Spain, developed a block chain toolkit to manage *social currency*, trust, rewards and reputation. Through the W3C it is also involved in the development of open social-web standards with a global outlook.

An interesting instance of digital social innovations developing further digital social innovations are the Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation (CAPS) funded in the EU FP7 and Horizon 2020 programmes but not continued from 2018 (CAPS projects, 2017). They are “ICT systems leveraging the emerging ‘network effect’ by combining open online social media, distributed knowledge creation and data from real environments (‘Internet of Things’) in order to create awareness of problems and possible solutions requesting collective efforts, enabling new forms of social innovation. Collective Awareness Platforms are expected to support environmentally aware, grassroots processes and practices to share knowledge, to achieve changes in lifestyle, production and consumption patterns, and to set up more participatory democratic processes.” (CATALYST, 2017). In this report, we present a selection of CAPS that are close to the above definition of digital social innovation.

Some examples are supporting a *maker culture* of open software and hardware, manufacturing and sensor technology (Le Roux, 2015). Make-It emphasises decentralized production (Make-It, 2016, p. 33) and MakingSense has a focus on sensor technology and environmental awareness and involves research institutions (MakingSense, 2017), the emerging *labs* of community innovation and manufacturing, other networks of learning and education, and also technology and engineering businesses for example in 3D-printing. Some of the research institutions are well-known players in DSI and European social innovation at large (such as Dutch TNO and the Waag Society, the Danish Institute of Technology, Brunel University or ZSI – Centre for Social Innovation).

CAPS called netCommons (netCommons, 2017) or MAZI (MAZI, 2017) directly promote and support community-based, bottom-up networking and communication. MAZI offers a *do-it-yourself* toolkit for building local wireless networks that are used in local communities, urban gardens and cooperative

housing projects in Berlin, London, Zurich and by the *nomadic* initiative UnMonastery. An initiative bridging both projects is Zurich-based Nethood, established in 2015 by scientists and engineers that combine expertise in IT, engineering, urban planning and non-profit management. A decided aim of these initiatives is the bridging of *digital* and real-life networking, local contexts and the urban environment under the heading of *hybrid cities*.

Another new CAPS starting in 2016 is ChainReact (ChainReact, 2016). It is notable and somewhat exceptional in that it brings collaboration and community participation to the investigation of corporate networks and supply chains. It aims at improving information on irresponsible corporate behaviour and allowing citizens and activists as stakeholders and potential purchasers to identify adverse societal impacts, react to them and transform them. To do this, it combines databases, a tool for activists to share information and the analytic capabilities of wikirate.org. The consortium represents existing initiatives such as opencorporates.org, and wikirate.org as well as Warsaw and Cambridge Universities.

Open4citizens and Empatia are CAPS that address city governance. Open4citizens aims to reduce the perceived “gap between the opportunities offered by the abundance of open data and the citizens’ capability to imagine new ways of using such data” (Open4Citizens, 2017) through co-design processes and Open Data Labs piloted in Copenhagen, Karlstad, Rotterdam, Milano and Barcelona. Empatia is a platform for the management of “Multi-channel participatory budgeting processes” (EMPATIA, 2017) in a consortium of university departments and research organisations in both IT and public administration and IT and consultancy businesses with expertise in public budgeting. It extends the regional reach of the CAPS investigated in this paper by its strong Portuguese presence and also involves a Czech IT partner.

Other CAPS develop digital tools for the internet itself. NEXTLEAP aims to create “next generation decentralized, secure and privacy-enhanced internet protocols” (European Commission, 2017), and CATALYST offers tools for *collective intelligence*, that is, large-scale public debate, mapping arguments, selecting ideas in open innovation, and online analytics of platforms and debates. These tools were tested by such diverse networks as Ashoka, Edgeryders, Loomio, the OECD, OuiShare, the CHEST project and the University of Naples (Sigma Orions, 2017).

Compared with the initiatives investigated by the DSI report, the CAPS extend their network a little further both regionally and with regard to knowledge and expertise. Still, digital social innovation is the domain of some Nordic, British, Dutch and also South European institutions, and the city pilots mirror that distribution.

The academic side of CAPS and other similar research is establishing itself in the emerging internet science. Its most recent conference volume describes internet science as “an interdisciplinary field that explores the sociotechnical nature of the Internet through the lenses of Computer Science, Sociology, Art, Mathematics, Physics, Complex Systems Analysis, Psychology, Economics, Law, Political Scienc-

es, and more. Internet Science aims to bridge these different views and theories, in order to create a more holistic understanding of the Internet and its impact on society" (Bagnoli et al., 2016, p. V). Internet Science and its INSCI conference series grew out of the FP7-funded European Network of Excellence in Internet Science (EINS).

The DSI study (Bria et al., 2015) is based on a previous crowd mapping of digital social innovation projects, covers some 6022 collaborative projects and 992 organisations and also conducted a network analysis. It reports the following patterns of actors and activities: 193 projects, the largest share are social enterprises or charities and foundations, 182 organisations are businesses, 153 are grassroots organisations and networks, followed by 118 academic and research organisations and 55 public sector and government organisations active in DSI (Bria et al., 2015).¹⁹ The DSI network analysis reports that "social innovation in Europe is currently done by a few large actors in concert with a large mass of smaller organisations, but the majority of social innovation actors in Europe are disconnected from these networks." (ibid., pp. 54f) The largest DSI communities are (unsurprisingly) grouped around the respective partners in the DSI project – but they cover only 28% of the DSI sample. They cover open hardware and networks with the Waag Society in the centre; collaborative economy around ESADE, the IRI, European Institute for Participatory Media and Institute for Network Cultures. A community around Nesta is technologically diverse and focuses on funding, acceleration of digital social innovation and open democracy. The Open Data community is grouped around FutureEverything and various city councils. The DSI partners are also found in the network as important bridging organisations, together with others such as Fondazione Mondo Digitale, Forum Virium Helsinki, Swirrl, Open Knowledge Finland, BetterPlaceLab or Alfamicro. Some new and generally less centrally networked organisations are also found in bridging positions. From this analysis the DSI report concludes that the large networks have successfully scaled DSI and reached the stage where large and complex networks are `scale-free` and show a power-law distribution which "is thought to be a sign of efficiency and resilience" (ibid., p. 56).

As this research concentrates on the European context and is funded by the European Commission it focuses on Europe with occasional mention of Latin American initiatives, in particular in democratic deliberation (Toret & Caleja, 2015). Internet science also connects with US-based research. Nordic and South European and also Dutch and British organisations play prominent parts across the different types of organisations. In these regions, we also see municipalities eager to pilot and co-create democratic and political digital social innovations. *Continental* (and even more Eastern) European (NMS) actors in digital social innovation appear to be both less visible and less connected.

¹⁹ Outside the world of European-funded networks, there are several other grassroots mapping exercises of SI projects which partly also collaborate with CAPs. A selection is documented here: <http://www.shareable.net/blog/open-source-recipes-to-make-social-innovations-more-shareable>

4.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

While the concept of social innovation (SI) in general has been maturing and evolving during the recent years, the concept of digital social innovations requires some differentiation and a more comprehensive taxonomy. Although there is a mutual penetration of material and digital social innovations and practices there may still be a difference in perspectives depending on the starting point: a material or real-life social innovation that benefits from digital services and products, compared to a digital social innovation that reaches out to the wider social world. The actual imagination and definition of (digital) social innovations often depends on actors' background and/or domain context. (Digital) Social Innovation (DSI) thus a multi-faceted concept that would benefit from a better positioning and definition. In this regard, for the fundamental idea of DSI, basic research has still to be done.

Currently DSI is mostly found in applied research and development activities. *Hot topics* of applied research in DSI mostly focus on the ways in which long-standing social innovations could benefit from using digital technologies, could become reality or be revitalised by complementary or enabling digital services or practices, e.g. neighbourhood networks, car sharing, e-mobility, affordable health care services, smart city infrastructures, smart farming, digital inclusion of older people and socially disadvantaged persons (e.g. Bühler & Pelka, 2014; Eckhardt, Kaletka & Pelka, 2016) and people from remote areas, mobile and ubiquitous lifelong learning concepts. A key issue of DSI is the fact that people more and more move seamlessly between and across their *physical* and *digital* lives. Dual user experiences have an impact on the social aspect of innovations since they strongly connect to the various aspects of engaging users.

However, in the view of the experts interviewed in the breakout session and other meetings, these digital social innovations, like other SI initiatives are facing the limitations of sustainability and upscaling. Starting as voluntary initiatives and/or funded projects, the challenge is to both develop the digital social innovation and a business model, institutional attachment or other mode of sustaining it. Obviously, in a dynamic technological environment, networks, platforms, databases require ongoing updating, maintenance and upgrading, and experts point to the limitation of volunteerism, but also at the fact that younger professionals and commercial start-ups increasingly take an interest in the social benefits of their activities.

There is also a gap between digital social innovation research and current initiatives and debates on digitalisation at large (or industry 4.0 in the German-speaking countries, see Kopp, 2016) which is considered more of a challenge to societies and may require complementary or compensating social innovations. These may concern reinvigorating the welfare state to better include freelancers, crowd workers and the technologically displaced; enhancing worker voice and participation and union power as employment becomes more discontinuous, virtualised and globalised; revitalising professional and high-quality media for meaningful democratic discourse and debate; educating both younger and older citizens in digital, political and social competencies well beyond marketable skills. These developments

are likely to need higher-scale and more systemic interventions than individual digital and social innovations and initiatives - but the complementarities and mutual expectations of political reform, citizens' self-empowerment, and social innovation require elaboration among and beyond existing networks and platforms of sharing, peer-to-peer, commons or *alternative* economies. For example, the *unconditional basic income* is frequently cited as a way of addressing technology-induced mass unemployment, *Responsible Research and Innovation* needs to be contextualised and applied to new digital developments, and algorithmwatch.org, an initiative by computer scientists addressing the societal impacts of big data and algorithmic decision-making, argues in favour of wider, more critical research, and differentiated regulation.

The risks of digital innovations or indeed, digitalisation, are also mostly outside the scope of digital social innovation research. From our interviews with experts from various fields, the well-known challenges of social innovation emerge in digital social innovation as well:

- What are the darker negative sides of the gradual introduction of intelligent, smart, digital technologies in urban development, for citizens and for local economies?
- How can social innovations be professionalised and rendered sustainable beyond volunteering or discontinuous project work, and how can resources be mobilised where markets or commercial exploitation fail?
- How and why does social innovation require which kind of leadership and/or participation?
- How to effectively engage users in the social part of digital innovation activities? How to distinguish actual empowerment of users and citizens and simple, cost-cutting self-service? What incentive scheme(s) to adopt to maximize participation? How to leverage existing digital tools to foster participation? How to integrate old and new tools to perform digital social innovation?
- Digital participation processes already exist. How can these processes be strengthened and related to actual policy development and innovation? How can they be rendered inclusive beyond self-recruitment of the digitally educated?

These questions emerge since both digital and analog social innovation as independent concepts have gained in importance. The topic has emancipated itself from social entrepreneurship and expanded to other areas of research. On the one hand, social innovation is considered as a normative concept, i.e. social innovations are good for society or part of broader transition movements, on the other hand, social innovation is understood as new social practices of which the ultimate outcomes remain unknown. While social innovation is widely acknowledged, insights in how the diffusion and institutionalisation of social innovation can be measured remain to some extent still vague.

From our interviews with experts in the field of digital social innovations the following hot topics were emerging on their research agenda:

- proper design of incentives and motivation to digital participation

- Integration of digital social innovation tools within digital tools of everyday use. The proliferation of platforms, apps and digital material on social innovation clashes with the growing requirement of simplifying and merging the *digital social innovation* experience within the pre-existing activities and tools already familiar to the majority of users (with regard to social media in particular but not exclusively).
- Citizen science and democratisation in the sense of training citizens to collect environmental data, such as air quality, and use this data to pressure local authorities. In addition, working together to collect this data enhances social cohesion.
- Reassembling and recycling existing concepts such as gamification, crowdsourcing, citizen science, data analytics, location-based services and mobile devices to contribute to a seamless user experience when those approaches and techniques are applied to realize digital social innovation systems and applications.
- Digital inclusion of older people, socially disadvantaged persons and people from remote areas (infrastructure, educational offers, alternative offers)
- Awareness of the need for lifelong learning in an increasingly digitalized society.
- Providing opportunities for lifelong learning, but also developing models of how to integrate these opportunities into everyday life.

Some of these questions open up fields of tension: cheaper self-service and self-administration by end-users versus the complexities of meaningful and improved co-creation of services; meaningful democracy and deliberation versus distributed data delivery (of opinion polls or environmental or health data); seamless integration of digital social innovations versus the predominance of platforms dominated by commercial interests, digital democratisation versus the persistence of exclusive mechanisms of "the iron law of oligarchy" (Passig, 2016) and so on.

Furthermore ZSI organised a breakout session on Digital Social Innovation. This aimed to identify one or several emerging *hot topics* for digital social innovation that participants considered interesting, important and promising in providing insight into useful and effective ways of digitally addressing societal challenges.

The main results of the breakout session can be summarised in three points 1) currently hot topics of interest in DSI, 2) challenges which are being derived from the listed topics and developments and 3) the economical dependency when talking about the sustainability of digital social innovation:

- 1) Topics and Movements in digital Social Innovation: A hot and cross-cutting topic of Digital Social Innovation can be summarized as an *openness movement* in the development and use of technologies as well as in the process of scientific work overall. Citizens are increasingly involved in scientific projects (e.g. local people are equipped with sensors to measure air quality or their own health and to systematically collect adequate data). Topics such as citizen science, crowdsourcing, maker movement, grass root activities, collective awareness platforms and responsive technology are cur-

rently widely discussed. Technology and (real-time) data are about to be open and shared, meaning that everyone interested can participate or make use of the technology or (live) data provided by science, governance and even industries (e.g. health or food industry) This is expected to change societal modes of regulation, coordination and participation - but raises questions of responsibilities, service quality and revenue distribution.

- 2) Challenges of digital social innovations: The *openness movement* has to deal with a lot of new challenges. Questions arise such as: How could we open up technology in specific sectors (e.g. big health or food industries as well as the increasing start-ups) and for special interest groups (e.g. maker movement)? Who is getting access rights to (open) data? How to give power to end-users? How can I trust the accessed data and information? What about the ethical principles that are materialised with technology or the algorithms steering it (e.g. self-driving cars)? How to influence and understand the ways in which technology is embedding or even creating norms and values in our society?
- 3) Sustainability of digital social innovation: When talking about innovations, the aspect of resource dependency cannot be overlooked and experts take different, more or less entrepreneurial views: We can talk about something as a social innovation only if it is successfully established in the market or a non-market field of use (inventions becoming innovations only if they are taken up). Even if the social aspect gets higher attraction and people like to work for a higher goal than just for a living, innovations need resources to maintain and update them.

In general, digital social innovation research in the European research landscape is frequently embedded and interlaced with the development of actual technology, the piloting and upscaling, and also with the building of further networks for digital social innovation. This is mirrored in organisations' activities.

Type of organisation	How are they supporting DSI	Case study examples
Government and public sector organisations	Providing funding for experiments / R&D Providing non-financial resources (i.e. opening up public data sets) Delivering or partnering with DSI services	Open Vienna Meiraha CitySDK
SMEs and large businesses	Delivering services Providing funding for experiments / R&D (particular the case for large Telco organisations)	Patients like me Github
Academia and research institutions	Analysing trends and movements Providing new (fundamental) technologies and methodologies	DECIS network Arduino
Social enterprises, charities and foundations	Stimulate multi-disciplinary research and innovation Connecting top-down and bottom-up movements Amplifying weak signals Supporting grassroots movements	Avaaz Ushahidi CKAN
Grassroots movements	Engaging, facilitating and expanding communities Democratizing access to emerging technologies	Smart Citizen Kit TOR Chaos Computer Club

Figure 1: Types of organisations and their DSI activities (Bria, 2014, p. 28)

Figure 1 presents activities as they were found in the DSI crowd mapping exercise. A closer look shows that the different types of organisations are interlaced through joint projects, relationships of collaboration, service and support or advocacy, in similar ways as social innovation initiatives at large as investigated in the SI-DRIVE project (Howaldt et al., 2016). Grassroots movements engage, facilitate and expand communities. They may develop technologies themselves and/or provide platforms or services to other digital and non-digital initiatives. They also aim to influence policy with particular aims of democratizing access to technology, ensuring privacy and net neutrality, and empowering individuals. Some grassroots movements have established non-profit organisations or charities of their own similar to the *older* open source communities, (O'Mahony, 2007) or are supported by others. Otherwise charities and foundations stimulate and support various initiatives and projects, fund them directly or support fundraising activities, or coordinate social movements and protests. Such organisations play a central part in the European institutionalization of digital social innovation of which DSI and its follow-up pro-

jects are an example. Digital social innovations, technologies, tools and methodologies are also developed by research or academic institutions. Others conduct research on these innovations that is often transdisciplinary and collaborative. Businesses may deliver services, frequently on top of open source technologies or open innovation models with uses in both non-profit and for-profit contexts. Companies may also fund R&D and digital social innovation developments, sponsor initiatives and awards, or, formally or informally, contribute staff, code or hardware to digital social innovation. Governments and public bodies similarly provide funding or data sets (Open Data), procure services or partner in their delivery. They also open themselves to changing and new forms of deliberation, decision-making and resource allocation through piloting tools of participation and digital democracy. A recent study on open research data (Kroop et al., 2016) is screening international and national (Austria's) activities and initiatives to open government-funded research data to be (re-)used by any interested person. The hope is to stimulate a creative industry and new (social) businesses by (re-) using such open (research and governmental) data.

The CAPS described here, the networks and initiatives they represent, as well as the CHEST project's award winners and beneficiaries address particular issues and often very physical challenges through digital social innovations: environmental awareness, city policies health, education and mobility issues. Some organisations, like Nethood, explicitly emphasise that *hybridity*. Low-cost and distributed hardware and software, open platforms such as the Arduino Physical Computing environment, sensors, and also the smartphones and tablets used by citizens and schoolchildren are combined with crowd-based modes of data gathering, political expression and interaction. Attention is also paid to the use of blockchain technologies well beyond monetised environments, for alternative, regional or project-specific currencies or to reward citizens for political engagement (Roio & Sachy, 2015).

Academic subjects and research questions stay closer to the home base of internet technologies and impacts: "In particular, Internet Science asks crucial questions like: How do people behave in the Internet? Are they changing their lifestyle and how? Can the Internet promote sustainability, cooperation, and collective intelligence? Can it support open democracy and policy making? How can the awareness of possibilities and dangers of the Internet be promoted? What about topics like intellectual property, privacy, reputation, and participation? What are the juridical aspects of the Internet? What about arts and humanities in general?" (Bagnoli et al., 2016, p. V)

The subjects covered in the most recent conference thus are

- Collective Awareness and Crowdsourcing platforms
- Collaboration, Privacy, and Conformity in Virtual/Social Environments
- Internet Interoperability, Freedom, and Data Analysis
- Smart Cities and Sociotechnical Systems" (ibid.)

The resulting wealth of information presents its own challenges of overload, redundancy and poor quality that are addressed in other projects: CATALYST for example develops tools for the crowdsourcing of arguments and online deliberation that structure and summarise debates, provide analytics feedback on

the progress of the debate and tools for voting on contributions and ideas. It thus aims to address the shortcomings of established platforms for large-scale and still high-quality public debate: unstructured and poor quality debates, lack of insight into the logical structure of arguments and lack of support for the development and refinement of ideas (De Liddo & Buckingham Shum, 2014). However, the mapping and structuring of arguments is not automated: it requires considerable work by moderators and facilitators to provide participants and themselves with structured maps on debates, and making sense of the *dashboard* of network analytics in a debate will require considerable skill and experience.

Similarly, the D-Cent project builds on the development of technologies for organising and democratic deliberation that are used in social movements, and in municipal and national experiments of participatory decision-making in Spain, the Finnish Open Ministry and Iceland's Better Reykjavik. It has analysed the online practices of social movements and conducted discourses with internet theorists and activists. The participants are thus very aware of the interrelationships between the web and local aspects of the new *social network movements* such as Occupy, the Egyptian and Tunisian revolutions, the Gezi protests in Turkey and the 15M movement in Spain.

Research, technology development, scientific observation and practice thus combine in both layers and loops. As platforms and tools are proliferating, research is conducted into their uses and further tools are developed to overcome their deficiencies. The outlook of the respective projects varies with their emphasis on technology and tools versus the tools' embeddedness in a wider political context.

4.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

From this overview, it becomes clear that research is closely tied in with other activities of digital social Innovation and researchers themselves are moving back and forth between actual investigation, facilitation and networking and technology use and development. Research methods frequently aim to answer to the challenges of abundance: This is obvious in the huge amounts of data and information generated in conventional and innovative web-based networks and platforms, but also in the number and variety of initiatives, tools and platforms, and *platforms of platforms*. Crowdsourcing and mapping methodologies shift data collection partly to initiatives themselves - but obviously should not let us conclude that this saves the efforts of data quality assurance and data cleaning. Network analyses are probably among the most common methodologies. However, the DSI network analysis also shows that crowd-based data gathering remains close to projects' own networks and contacts, thus mirroring rather than extending established networks. Beyond the straightforward network analysis as in the DSI project, some research brings big data analytics into social innovation - with an explicit aim of democratising these tools that are conventionally associated with established large organisations and commercial use. With the increasing complexity of the analysis, visualisation techniques also play an increasing part.

The use of qualitative methodologies is more limited. Purely interpretive or reconstructive case study methodologies are rare. Arguably, conventional social-science case study designs in the context of digital social innovation morph into co-design, participatory and action research setups that actively enter the dynamics of the field, accompany use cases or contexts, and are likely to take facilitating or reflecting roles beyond scientific observations. This is probably in line with the wider development of the social sciences towards more transdisciplinary and application-oriented modes of operation. However, in-depth analysis and careful and interpretive reconstruction of narratives, discourses and the longer histories and biographies of projects may still offer insight into the contradictions, limitations and possibilities of innovation and collaboration, be it digital or analogue. The constructivist, pragmatist and ethnographic approaches to technology are also well equipped to complement or counterbalance the frequent cognitivist and *solutionist* biases of digital social innovation: the assumptions that conflictual, value-based and frequently emotional discourses and arguments can be mapped, structured and rationally decided upon, or that technical solutions in themselves solve social problems (Morozov, 2014).

With the wide ranges of disciplines and trans-disciplines involved in digital social innovation, an actual integrating theory is hard to identify. Cascading or spiral-shaped models of innovation are commonly used: For the DSI project, the "Open Book of Social Innovation" (Murray, Caulier-Grice, & Mulgan, 2010) provides the background, and the Catalyst project bases its model of *collective intelligence* on a sequence of collective sensing → collective sense-making → collective ideation → collective decision → collective action.

Almost by definition, digital social innovation has more of an implicit theoretical background in theories on the collaborative potential of the internet and its related modes of collaboration developed in concepts of Networks of Innovation (Tuomi, 2002), "commons-based peer production" (Benkler, 2006, p. 60), and with roots in the earlier theories on the democratic and do-it-yourself potential of *new media* from Bertolt Brecht onwards (Holtgrewe, 2004). However, in recent years this potential is seen more ambiguously as issues of exploitation and commercialization of user-generated content, fragmentation into *walled gardens* and NSA surveillance come to the fore (Morozov, 2012; Zittrain, 2009). Still, digital social innovation retains a certain technological optimism, aiming for citizens' empowerment and democratization to draw even with the economic and commercial potential of value creation. The D-Cent project, again, is notable in its explicit engagement with contemporary political and social science theories of the internet and of networked social movements which also feed into debates and discourses pursued within the project (Bria & Primosig, 2015).

4.5 IMPACT

The output of digital social innovation consists in a wide range of software tools and hardware and software infrastructures, toolkits and platforms as well as reports, stocktaking exercises and analyses of use and implementation contexts. These tools are frequently piloted and used in other virtual, hybrid and non-virtual communities, platforms and networked organisations, labs and also municipalities and government agencies. The actors in digital social innovations thus are exchanging, circulating and configuring their own and each other's products and building further digital innovations upon them. Open source, in the sense of an intellectual property (or commons) regime and a wider programme of free circulation and improvement of knowledge and technology, remains an important principle enabling these exchanges and reconfigurations.

Guides and Manuals on conducting social innovations are rather found in the domain of the share economy (e.g. www.shareable.net). Lilian Ricaud outlines an explicit transfer of the principles of open source (software or hardware) to the dissemination and transfer of social innovation practices at large, coining the term of "open social innovation" (Ricaud, 2014) and drawing on the metaphor of cooking recipes (*recettes libres*) to explicate, reuse, copy and improve social Innovations. Ricaud suggests a standardised mode of documenting social Innovation practices. Since there are several documentation platforms already and the workload of usable documentation is not to be neglected, the suggestion amounts to a protocol linking content of different platforms rather than another platform. Otherwise, there is a body of research reports, academic papers and conferences that appear to converge around the heading of *internet science*.

However, the availability of tools, platforms and knowledge does not guarantee their wider use and accessibility beyond the existing networked and highly knowledgeable communities - an experience known from the earlier generations of open source projects (Brand & Holtgrewe, 2010). We cannot yet be sure that grassroots initiatives in various domains and use contexts easily find the tools for coordinating, deliberating and reaching out, unless they have digital expertise on board already. For example, the dashboards to monitor public debates shown by de Liddo and Buckingham Shum will require some skill and contextualisation to be useful to moderators or participants (De Liddo & Buckingham Shum, 2014) - and may suggest a governability of such debates that is at odds with the open-ended, embodied and inclusive deliberation of social movements.

The D-Cent project has an explicit political agenda to support a "multitudinous re-appropriation of the political, economic, and communicative spheres" (D-Cent, 2014, p. 4) that are expropriated or eroded by powerful state and corporate actors. It thus arrives at a decisive political programme: ensuring a technological internet basis of open standards, universality and the construction principles of web 1.0, "more equilibrated information ecosystems" that do not just multiply information tools and channels but also assure information authentication, trust, focus and also openness to deviating viewpoints. Neither technologies nor states or companies are regarded simply as opponents but rather as terrains of con-

testation and struggle: “the sociotechnical nurturing of autonomy, not only through free (thereby adaptable) software development but also of the competences and incentives required for its growth within activist collectives, is paramount” (Toret & Caleja, 2015, p. 72).

The DSI study and network emerges as a large and influential stock-taking project that proves that it has indeed been conducted by central actors in the field and thus contributed to the institutionalization of DSI on a European level. Based on this centrality, it draws some clear conclusions for European policies of digital social innovations: to promote and increase the DSI network, foster connectors between the (sub-)communities and in particular connect the *long tail* of smaller networks and initiatives that are less connected would need more connections, “to gather all the disconnected organisations to a single European network and encourage new communities where there are currently none” (p. 56) – possibly less through a reiteration of current projects but through looser mechanisms such as recommendation systems. This approach focuses on growth and scaling of social innovations and is based on the Young Foundation’s model of seven stages of innovation (Murray et al., 2010), with the corresponding policy goals to support all phases.

The *digital*-specific argument outlined in the DSI report is one of uneven but complementary development (cf. paragraph 0): top-down digital innovations aim at pan-European technology platforms and the creation of a European Digital Single Market, but are “business driven with little attention to societal challenges or to the inclusion of civil society and bottom-up approaches” (European Union, 2015, p. 58). The report thus emphasises bottom-up approaches that explicitly harness the possibilities of the internet’s network effects to address societal challenges, encourage citizens’ participation, and improve sustainability and collective wellbeing (ibid., p. 59). A similar argument is made by Kopp (2016) with regard to the top-down and large-industry-driven character of the German *Industry 4.0* debate. This complementarity needs to be fostered by policies that support and nurture digital social innovations to realise the network and scaling potential of the technology for societal good.

However, this might promote an overly harmonious and selective picture. Certainly digital, and hence knowledge-based and space-independent social innovations lend themselves to scaling and widening their scope in more obvious ways than local innovations relying on face-to-face interactions, for example in the social services. Tools and platforms that scale and can be reused are certainly efficient, promise network effects and may save efforts of *re-inventing the wheel*. However, they may not be as comprehensively effective. Firstly, fitting and adapting toolkits, knowledge bases and skills to new and different local contexts may require more effort than originally expected. Secondly, the good or best practices expected to scale may be more contingent upon their respective contexts than is immediately obvious. This hints at the complex interrelationship of a *practice* or a *case* with its context – an ongoing methodological and theoretical challenge in social-science based studies of social innovation that is increasingly coming to the fore as these studies become more transnational and transdisciplinary. Thirdly, scaling a recognized good practice or innovation may create lock-in effects and crowd out other, localized or different efforts that still would have other impacts, contributing variety or learning oppor-

tunities. This points to the element of uncertainty in all innovative practices: you never know what might develop instead of what you are currently developing. However, these aspects are not merely obstacles to digital social innovation that could be overcome through a logic of *more and better* networks, faster scaling etc. Rather, they give reasons to complement efforts at scaling digital social innovations with those nurturing variety, niche strategies and localised efforts, complemented by mutual learning. Arguably, policies that balance scaling and variety make sense in the economic sphere as well: both commercial and societal innovation ecologies (and the spheres where they are overlapping) are likely to benefit from bottom-up initiatives that aim for participation and democratization alongside the solving of technological and societal problems.

4.6 CONCLUSIONS

The subject of digital social innovation is thus hardly distinguishable from its European institutionalisation. We are seeing a wide range of developed and developing networks, platforms and efforts of integration, but also evidence of some St Matthews' effects (Merton, 1968) - *to those that have shall be given* - and disparities between regions and access to networks.

However, investigating the projects already funded and supported by European means inevitably has a selection bias towards the more 'successful' ones as the acquisition of such funding already requires a certain amount of resources and contacts. With the embedding of digital social innovation in the real world chances increase to open up that network and possibly extend or scale initiatives further – but this will require dedicated efforts that are not just one way. Beyond further efforts at stocktaking and networking, more proactive outreach and in-depth research into remoter and isolated initiatives may provide further insight and compensate for the risks of existing and successful networks to become more exclusive than an *open* programmatic would suggest. This is less a matter of good intentions but of social-structural mechanisms that apply in the real world as well as in digital contexts (Passig, 2016).

The 'gaps' thus require dedicated research - even though the investigation of non-existing initiatives is obviously difficult. Those that exist may just be less visible. They may be 'too successful' in developing businesses right away, 'too busy' to invest resources in visibility and networking (a mentality not unheard-of among committed programmers and other tech-minded people), or 'too local' (a variation of 'too busy'). Hence, the increasing interactions of digital social innovations with non-digital life, society and its challenges are most likely good news even if they contribute to a less clearly delineated field. However, this will increasingly bring further challenges: users with diverging degrees of expertise and engagement, inequality, inclusion of disadvantaged groups and a mutable empowerment between digital social innovations and non-digital life. One area of societal challenges that appears strikingly disconnected from digital social innovation is the ICT sector itself. The more political projects are seeing challenges in the dominance of commercial platforms (that are mostly US-based) and the current asymmet-

rical and volatile divisions of labour and power between European, US-based and Chinese information and communication technology and platform providers. These tensions in the political economy may create risks to European sustainable and inclusive growth as well as opportunities. Connecting discussions on social innovation with those on contemporary political economies would provide deeper insight into the genesis of needs and challenges to social innovation.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

5 Intermediaries

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5.1 INTRODUCTION

Social innovation intermediaries are those organisations that provide support to social innovators. This support takes a number of different forms including providing skills, space, knowledge, networks and funds. Intermediaries are an important element in the drive by national and international actors to foster, scale and accelerate social innovation and therefore have been enabled by funds and policy.

Research has been an important part of developing the case for social innovation intermediaries and has helped to define the processes by which innovations can be supported. Intermediaries have played a significant role in highlighting where social innovation needs greater support and in suggesting how to strengthen the ecosystem at large. Work by intermediaries on issues such as social financing and incubation has been influential in policy decisions that have facilitated the rise of social innovation and the building of social innovation infrastructure.

However there are still significant gaps, particularly in robust evidence of the impacts of social innovations and intermediaries. This chapter focuses on defining the 'research area and its community and considering where and how there is scope to strengthen the research frameworks used to understand social innovation. We will also explore some of the challenges that are present in developing impact assessment in this field and look at the outcomes of previous attempts to do this. In addition, this chapter considers how research can be used as a tool to widen the social innovation community, helping to define new spaces in which social innovation can or does act, and helping to identify new actors working as intermediaries in this space. Further it can help us to ensure that concepts, findings and best practices are embedded into the sector and into policy.

5.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

Intermediaries are those organisations that have a role to play in supporting social innovations and facilitating their growth. Intermediaries provide support as diverse as funding and social investment, accelerator programmes, incubation, provision of space for research and development, access to mentors and coaches, networking and in some cases vital 'hand-holding' for innovators who are aiming to grow their ideas into viable ventures. One prominent model for doing this is through social Innovation 'labs' (Westley et al., 2015). The definition of social innovation intermediary that we have adopted for this report as follows:

"Intermediaries are individuals, organisations, networks, or spaces which connect people, ideas, and resources. They can take a variety of forms – some incubate innovations by providing a

‘safe’ space for collaboration and experimentation; some connect entrepreneurs with the supports they need to grow their innovations; and others help to spread innovations by developing networks and collaborations” (Murray, et al., 2010).

Table 1 below presents a typology of social innovation intermediaries and lays out the different roles that are fulfilled by intermediaries (Shanmugalingam et al., 2011).

Table 1: Typology of Social Innovation Intermediaries

<p>Intermediaries that provide expertise, people and networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best practice sharing platforms • Community developers • Design intermediaries • Innovation platforms • Investor readiness providers • Leadership accelerators • Physical incubators • Pro-bono networks • Social entrepreneurship schools • Social innovation venture labs • Social venture capital funds • Social venture networks • Specialist social enterprise consultancies • Support brokers
<p>Intermediaries that provide marketing and distribution channels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bidding platforms • Commissioning advisors • Social venture directories

Intermediaries that support innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Commissioning advisors• Competitions/ Advisors• Design intermediaries• Innovation platforms• Social innovation venture labs
Intermediaries that monitor the impact of social ventures	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Evaluation standardisation platforms• Impact measurement consultancies• Performance indices
Intermediaries that provide finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Community developers• Community share issue brokers• Crowd-sourcing platforms• Grant makers• Innovation/challenge funds• Micro-funding• Philanthropic networks• Social impact bond providers• Social investment brokers• Social lenders• Social venture capital funds

Social innovators require a broad range of different kinds of support but there are also different approaches that people can take to supporting social innovation. Work by Frances Westley and Sam Laban (Westley et al., 2015) focuses on social innovation as a response to problems that arise in complex systems and notes that there can be different emphases to the ways in which social innovation support

is offered. Approaches include whole systems approaches which focus on aspects such as organisational behaviour, group dynamics and process design. By comparison a design approach is informed by the design thinking and focuses more heavily on aspects such as prototyping solutions, and technical production.

Examples of prominent social innovation intermediaries include organisations such as the Toronto SI Center, The Australian Centre for Social Innovation (TACSI), and Social Impact Lab, in Germany. However, examples of intermediaries go beyond this. There are many different actors who fulfil the role of social innovation intermediaries: they include governments, quasi-autonomous non-governmental organisations (QUANGOs), non-governmental organisations (NGOs) (like charities, foundations and trusts), CSOs and private sector actors. Government actors can play an important role in increasing the variety of kinds of support available to social innovation intermediaries. By putting in place policy or funding that enables social innovation intermediaries they can help to build markets.

An example of this is the development of Big Society Capital in the UK which is an entirely new model of support for social business enabled by government policy, backed up with significant financial investment. For the purposes of this network we would conceptualise Big Society Capital as an intermediary because they support social innovation by providing funds, they are unusual in that they provide wholesale finance to other intermediaries, they also provide other functions such as advocating on behalf of social investors and 'market building'. As such, they are an important intermediary element of the social innovation ecosystem.

Many EU projects have viewed the building of social innovation networks as a clear objective, these include: BENISI, which seeks to build a Europe-wide network of networks of incubators for social innovation; Transition, which looks to understand transnational scaling of social Innovations; and Social Innovation Europe (SIE) which looked to build and streamline the field of social innovation in Europe. All of these projects set -up networks in order to facilitate knowledge sharing between social innovation intermediaries. Additionally networks like DESIS have also benefitted from public funds, including from the EU. Table 2 below lists the different kinds of intermediary networks as well as the aims and origins of these networks.

Evident from this table is the extent to which networks of intermediaries are frequently transnational. In addition to these transnational networks there are also national and regional networks examples include: Sociale Innovatie Netwerk Nederland, the Forum for Social Innovation Sweden, and the Andalusian Network of Living Labs. This suggests that it may be possible for intermediaries research to attain both good geographical spread and some depth into particular contexts. This increases opportunities to learn from the activities that these networks currently engage in and understand the extent to which the needs and wants of intermediaries differ at different scales.

Table 2: Types of innovation networks

Network type	Examples of these types of networks	Location	Description	Initiators/ Facilitators	Objectives
Accelerator Networks	Social Innovation Accelerator Network (SIAN)	EU	These networks include organisations that provide accelerator support and individuals with an interest or an active role in venture acceleration	Examples of initiators include European projects like Benisi, SEISMIC.	These networks aim to help identify, promote and scale up social innovation by encouraging learning, skill and resource sharing and collaboration between accelerators
	Social Innovation Accelerators in Cities (SIAC)	EU			
	Accelerator Assembly	EU			
Incubator Networks	Impact Hub Network	Global	These are networks of incubators who provide physical space, resources, and connections for people.	Examples of initiators of these projects include the EU Transitions Project, EBN themselves who also supported the development of ESIIN.	The objective of these network is to facilitate the exchange of knowledge around good practice between social innovation incubators.
	European Social Innovation	EU			
	Incubator Network (ESIIN)	EU			
	IDIN Innovation Centre Network	Global			
	European Business Network	EU			
Lab Networks	European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)	EU	There are a number of labs that engage in innovation experimentation and practice. This networks brings together these actors at various levels, national and international.	Innovation labs networks are facilitated by a variety of actors including NGOs, Governments, and the EU.	The objective of these networks is to ensure learning and support between labs, mitigating the worst effects of replication of efforts.
	DESIS	EU			
	Unicef Innovation Lab Network	Global			
	Andalusian Network of Living Labs	Spain			
Funder Networks	European Business Angel Network	EU	These networks represent funders and investors who are looking to provide resources for social entrepreneurs and innovation.	These networks are facilitated on a largely non-profit basis and are frequently funded by public money and foundations. E.g. GIIN is funded by actors like the Rockefeller Foundation and UKAID	The objective of these networks is to ensure that funders of social innovation feel supported and guided in the process of investing/capitalising/funding.
	Global Impact Investing Network (GIIN)	Global			
Innovator/ Enterprise Networks	EUCLID Social Enterprise Network	EU	These networks are people who innovate. These networks are intermediaries, due to the support and guidance that they provide to	These are funded by a variety of different actors, private companies (often through CSR), governments, other public funding, foundations, and NGOs.	The objective of these networks is to try and foster social innovators by providing a supportive network of innovators that facilitates the sharing of
	Global Social Entrepreneurship Network (GSEN)	Global			

	Ashoka	Global	social innovators.		knowledge, skills and resources.
	Irish Social Innovation Network	Ireland			
	The Italian Social Innovation Network (I-SIN)	Italy			
	Sociale Innovatie Netwerk Nederland	The Netherlands			
	The iNnovation Network (iN)	UK			

There are a number of fields where organisations functioning as social innovation intermediaries are springing up, with few links to the wider social innovation community. Many of these draw on social innovation tools and processes, - such as by organising activities in ‘labs’ or using ‘challenge funds’ to foster solutions for specific problems. They are not currently involved in social innovation networks and would have much to benefit from and offer to the broader social innovation community. Meaningful engagement with these kinds of sector-specific actors is a key aim of the network.

In housing there are a number of organisations and networks fostering housing innovation including Batigiére²⁰, Eurhonet²¹, networks of housing organisations, and actors such as and SHIRE²², a network within Manchester Metropolitan University aimed at sharing knowledge within the social housing sector.

In international development, Government, INGOs and CSOs are offering a number of forms of intermediary support including incubation, acceleration and challenge funds. Examples of networks of intermediaries in this space include The UNICEF Innovation Lab Network²³ and the IDIN Innovation Centre Network²⁴.

As well as the above networks there are other ‘unusual suspects’ performing this kind of intermediary role including: The NHS England Innovation Accelerator, the Ogunte-led ‘Make A Wave’ pre-incubator programme, the Building and Social Housing Foundation Innovation Awards, the Barclays Social Innovation Lab, and the Mondragon Team Academy.

²⁰Batigiére is a French network of social housing organisations which promotes equal opportunities, economic development and attempts to foster social ties through innovation
²¹Eurhonet is a network of 32 public and social housing companies which attempts to share knowledge and best practice around housing innovation
²² SHIRE is a newly developed network within Manchester Metropolitan University that seeks to share knowledge within the social housing sector in order to explore ways to contribute towards better housing and stronger communities.
²³ The Unicef Innovation Lab Network is a collection of UNICEF innovation labs which all share good practice and research around the acceleration and incubation of international development projects
²⁴ The IDIN Innovation Centre Network is a network within the International Development Innovation Network (IDIN) which is designed to help innovation centres to support local innovators and connect them to resources, education and training

5.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

We need to understand how social innovation develops, progresses, and is hindered or enabled in order to be able to support it effectively. As such research related to social innovation broadly is relevant and important to intermediaries.

“...social innovation is not really a field yet, it is a set of new interests that are deeply grounded in tradition” (Westley, 2013).

The field of social innovation has been rapidly developing its theoretical basis. Research related to social innovation intermediaries comes in three main forms:

- Theory development (exploration)
- Practice development (experimentation)
- Impact assessment (evaluation).

In practice, many research projects encompass more than one of these elements in their work on social innovation.

There are numerous definitions that are utilised by this community ranging from the broad:

“...an “innovative” program or service is a new or different way to address a societal problem or pursue a charitable mission that is more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than prevailing approaches” (Salomon et al., 2010).

To the more prescriptive:

“...an initiative, product or process or program that profoundly changes the basic routines, resource and authority flows or beliefs of any social system. Successful social innovations have durability and broad impact. While social innovation has recognizable stages and phases, achieving durability and scale is a dynamic process that requires both emergence of opportunity and deliberate agency, and a connection between the two. The capacity of any society to create a steady flow of social innovations, particularly those which re-engage vulnerable populations, is an important contributor to the overall social and ecological resilience” (Westley, 2008).

A lot of work has been done in order to try to develop a consistent definition of social innovation, most notably by the Tepsie project (TEPSIE, 2014b) which synthesised definitions of social innovation:

“We define social innovations as new approaches to addressing social needs. They are social in their means and in their ends. They engage and mobilise the beneficiaries and help to

transform social relations by improving beneficiaries' access to power and resources." (TEP-SIE, 2014a)

Research topics relevant to this area/community tend to fall under three broad questions. These are:

- 1. What is social innovation and how can intermediaries support social innovation?**
 - a. What are the methods by which we can scale social innovation?
 - b. How can we most effectively provide acceleration, incubation, design (etc.) services?
 - c. How can different types of funding foster different kinds of social innovation?
 - d. How can new actors (government, private sectors) become intermediaries?
 - e. How can different actors effectively collaborate to foster innovation?
- 2. What are the barriers and drivers of social innovation, where are the gaps in the social innovation ecosystem and how can they be addressed?**
 - a. What barriers to innovation intermediaries exist in, for example, policy, the market etc.
 - b. How can policy instruments be used to facilitate social innovation intermediaries?
 - c. How do regulatory frameworks impact upon social innovation intermediaries?
 - d. What gaps are there in the market place and how can this be addressed?
- 3. What are the impacts of the work of social innovation intermediaries?**
 - a. How can we effectively monitor the performance of intermediaries?
 - b. How can we come to understand their impacts?
 - c. What tools and methods and frameworks can be applied to the field?

To some extent each of these questions are being addressed by researchers, in many cases through existing EU funded projects, but also at the national level and within academic and other research institutions. There are now many social innovation research institutions that look at how to foster social innovation through intermediaries. Table 3 represents examples of EU projects and where they attempt to deal with these questions:

Table 3: Projects that address questions relevant to the Intermediaries Community

Question	Projects	Locations
What is social innovation and how can intermediaries support social innovation?	BENISI (Consortium Project)	EU
	Transitions (Consortium)	EU
	SIMPACT (Consortium)	EU
	INNOSERV	EU
	WILCO	EU
What are the barriers and drivers of social innovation, where are the gaps in the social innovation ecosystem and how can they be addressed?	SI-DRIVE (Consortium)	Transnational
	Tepsie (Consortium)	EU
	SIMPACT (Consortium)	EU
	SELUSI	EU
What are the impacts of social innovation and social innovation intermediaries?	GECES Social Impact Measurement Sub-Group	EU

	SIMPACT (Consortium)	EU
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If we consider the above projects it appears that whilst there is a consistently building theoretical basis for social innovation the experimental and evaluative sides of research could be considered less well developed. Some of the most notable gaps are around impact assessment.

As we have already discussed, there are many fields where the tools, methods and language of social innovation are being used but which do not necessarily engage with social innovation concepts and frameworks. Many of these fields have their own theoretical and methodological approaches and their own research questions. In international development, for example, there is a considerable body of literature that looks at the creation, implementation and evaluation of new programmes and new practices, which could be of considerable use to those who research social innovation intermediaries.

Because of the focus around social innovation research at the EU level some of the most influential social innovation research institutions are located in Europe or are in some way associated within Europe. It is also the case that research around social innovation intermediaries has frequently been aligned with the priorities of European funding. However social innovation research is not evenly distributed across Europe or globally. Countries like Italy, Germany, the UK and the Netherlands can be seen as examples of states with a diverse range of actors who do research that is relevant to social innovation intermediaries. This demonstrates a clear need to spread the learning from existing research more widely and also presents opportunities for those who do social innovation research to learn from what may be occurring elsewhere.

However it could be argued that social innovation research has a particular character, often heavily focused around entrepreneurship or the programmatic, that perhaps makes other forms of social innovation less visible. There have been attempts to be more inclusive in how we talk about social innovation, by looking for example at issues such as Jugaad innovation. However these is also a need for the concept of social innovation to go beyond this and become more inclusive to agency exercised in ways not in line with western social innovation narratives (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

5.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

Social innovation, SI research and the role of intermediaries are interlinked and co-dependent. Research around intermediaries necessarily builds from work on social innovation. Developing frameworks and clarifying understanding on social innovation enables SI intermediaries to deepen their understanding of the needs of ventures and innovators, the contexts in which they operate and therefore directly contribute to improving the quality and the relevance of the support they provide.

Social innovation research has a number of different roles including:

- The theoretical framing of social innovation, pushing the boundaries of our understanding of social innovation, conceptualising participation, action and practice as well as conceptualising 'supportive' bodies and the roles of intermediaries.
- Analysis of social innovation support, understanding roles, gaps, and ecosystems.
- Understanding the function and impacts of support.

Social innovation has often been conceived of as a 'practice-led field' (The Young Foundation, 2012) and the idea was characterised as a 'quasi-concept', by Jane Jenson, one with an *"indeterminate quality that makes it adaptable to a variety of situations and flexible enough to follow the twists and turns of policy that everyday politics sometimes makes necessary"* (Jenson, 2015).

However there is a slowly building theoretical basis for social innovation. Research and particularly research around intermediary support for social innovation can often engage with theories that explore the nature of social change.

Important theoretical dimensions to work around social innovation and social innovation intermediary support focuses on social practice theory (SPT). This is explicitly used as a theoretical basis within the SI-DRIVE project, attempting to understand how social practices come to create emergent social innovation (Howaldt et al., 2014). SI-DRIVE also invokes Tarde's work (ibid.) on social interaction and diffusion in order to explore the nature of practices and the diffusion of innovation. The desire to go beyond the programmatic and look at the practices that drive social innovations is a clear theory based direction that social innovation is moving in.

A structuration perspective (Giddens, 1984) has also been used in order to build a greater understanding of social innovation. Heiskala (2007) understands social innovation as existing within the sphere of regulative, normative and cultural structures and also considers changes in social practices as a crucial aspect of social innovation.

Another theoretical approach present in social innovation research rests with Institutional Theory (Dorado, n.d.) which bears parallels to Foucauldian conceptions of governance in its understanding of socially constituted and negotiated orders. It emphasises the creation, disruption and maintenance of institutionalised social structures that govern behaviour. This has been instrumental in the development of a typology of social innovation (incremental, institutional and disruptive) based on the extent to which social innovation challenges social norms and orders.

In addition to these more sociological theories around social innovation there is also social innovation research that bases itself out of 'creativity research' and research into entrepreneurship and management. These, perhaps, take more of a traditional innovation research perspective.

The theoretical basis for social innovation continues to build and inform both research and practice. Importantly different approaches to understanding social innovation and the role of intermediaries call for many different kinds of methodological approaches. Examples of approaches used in research include:

Approach	Benefits
Case Study Approach	A case study approach is more a methodology than a method and is most suitable to those circumstances in which cases are dispersed and therefore sampling can be very onerous or challenging. Additionally they are often the prescribed methodology to explore phenomena that are highly dependent on their social context. This is clearly the case in social innovation and therefore this has meant the case study approach is relatively popular when attempting to draw general lessons about social innovation and social innovation support. Transition is one example of a project that utilises a case study approach to understand social innovation support.
Ethnographic Approach	Increasingly there is an acknowledgement of the benefits of an ethnographic approach to looking at social innovation and support for social innovation. This stems from attempts to understand the driving forces behind social innovation. It broadens concepts of social innovation to look at practices and the meanings behind the actions that people take. This allows phenomenon to be explored and understood as determined by and determining of the social, allowing for a more holistic understanding of social innovation.
Action Learning Approach	Action learning is a form of research and learning that is often present in organisational contexts. Action learning is an approach in which curiosity, inquiry and reflection are used in order to appraise a situation, learn and improve processes. This is both an exploratory and evaluative approach to research.
Quasi-Experimental Approach	A non-randomised approach to experimental design, often a pre-post baselined methodology. This makes them easier to implement than the randomised control trial. However they are not as robust and do not have the same level of internal validity that you would find in a randomised trial and therefore baseline variations may be present.
RCT Approach	There is an increasing emphasis upon demonstrating quantifiable impact. This means a focus on analysing programmes using methods that can give effect sizes. This approach can lead to policy makers being able to make comparative cost-benefit analyses and this is valued in a context of diminishing resources and increasing demand. It has been present in health for decades and is increasingly advocated for by actors like the Behavioural Insights Team (BIT) in the UK.
Systematic Review	The systematic review is an approach which analyses an existing evidence base in order to give a balanced appraisal of the effectiveness of a particular intervention or class of interventions. It sometimes utilises meta-analysis in order to do this. This is an evaluative rather than explorative approach.

Methods

The methods utilised across these approaches range from qualitative approaches such as interviews, observation, focus groups etc. to quantitative approaches including randomised control trials (RCTs), meta-analysis and quantitative surveys.

There are a number of general impact assessment methodologies which fall in to the field of quasi experimental approach. These are often developed by institutions, including (but not limited to) social return on investment (SROI), Social Impact Assessment (SIA), the Human Impact and Profit (HIP) Scorecard and IRIS metrics. These often involve methods including score-carding and matrix-ing. There are a number of different methods that are beginning to have more traction within social innovation research.

Participatory methods have long been an important dimension to social innovation research and within this co-production and co-design are important elements. Alongside this there is a growing interest in the use of ethnographic methodologies to explore, more holistically, the process of social change and the drivers of social innovation. From the perspective of intermediaries participatory action research (PAR) has become an important tool for building better supportive frameworks for social innovation. Co-production and co-design too are increasingly used to understand tensions and barriers to innovation and bring together disparate voices and build stronger solutions informed by a variety of different experiences.

From a very different perspective the rise of behavioural insights in the UK and the USA has provided another perspective to social innovation research, one that is heavily informed by behavioural sciences and which frequently utilises highly quantitative experimental and evaluative techniques. This approach has not yet permeated significantly across the intermediaries sector at large, in part because of the resources and capabilities required to consider innovations in this way, however some of the actions of the UKs 'Behavioural Insights Team'²⁵ could be seen as taking on the role of the intermediary, through the experimentation of innovative solutions to tackle social issues.

²⁵ The Behavioural Insights Team is an organisation owned jointly by the Cabinet Office of the UK Government, NESTA and it's employees. It's a social purpose company that looks to use insights from behavioural science to evaluate innovative processes and practices in order to enact social change.

5.5 IMPACT

There have been a large number of products and resources produced in order to help intermediaries to understand how to scale up and support social innovation. Many of these have been produced by intermediaries themselves and are informed by their experiences.

One of the major outputs from social innovation research projects has been the networks of intermediaries created by projects like BENISI and SIE. European projects and initiatives have created such resources for social innovation intermediaries; examples of this include the European Social and Investment Fund's 'Toolkit for supporting social innovation with the ESIF'. In addition, NESTA has a number of resources available such as toolkits and practical guides to providing intermediary support²⁶ including ones focused on randomised control trials for innovation, investment in social ventures, challenge prizes and prototyping frameworks. Toolkit approaches are highly developed in social innovation research.

A significant output from the Transitions project has been the 'Social Innovation Journey (SIJ) Toolbox'. This project experimented with different forms of incubation and one of the major outputs was the creation of a tested method for incubating social innovation. This was then analysed through a case study based report. Both Le Centre de Recherche sur les Innovations Sociales (CRISES) and the EU funded SI-DRIVE projects have created significant databases of social innovation case studies which are used to analyse the driving forces of social innovation. These are resources that have significant potential for analysis.

A significant strength of the outputs from SI intermediary research is their usability. In addition to research reports there are a number of products that are designed to help people understand the practicalities and improve the quality of intermediary support. Toolboxes, curricula and networks are key outputs of social innovation intermediary research. The focus is on both the production and use of knowledge.

One of the ways in which this 'usability' is fostered is by making work available. Innovation intermediary resources are frequently open-source, particularly when they have received public funding. The SI-DRIVE database for example will be made publicly available and contains more than a thousand cases of social innovation which can then be analysed further by new parties. This allows the work to have even greater impact and longevity beyond the project providing further resources for researchers. The Young Foundation's 'Social Business Model Canvas' has been made creative commons and therefore is an example of work by social innovation intermediaries translating into an output that can be used widely. The NESTA toolboxes are freely available on their public website.

²⁶ Available at <http://www.nesta.org.uk/resources>

The usability and availability of this research means that there are good practice models available to those who are looking to provide an intermediary role. This has the potential to increase the impact of social innovation intermediary research in two ways:

1. By encouraging the spread of these tools and methods to new markets;
2. By increasing competition within existing markets.

One of the weaknesses of social innovation intermediary research lies in the lack of consensus practitioners have of how to appraise intermediary support in ways that are generalizable or comparable across contexts.

"There are still challenges in terms of what can be considered an acceptable "evidence-base" for success around social innovation, and techniques for evaluation and impact are not necessarily accepted against more established methodologies such as cost benefit analysis or RCT's." (Penny Hagen)

A large number of research projects utilise a case study approach in order to understand what works in supporting social innovation and this is understandable given that social innovations are frequently dispersed and their development is often highly context dependent. Therefore many of the outputs are built, to some extent, from experience and context based knowledge. The limitation of this approach is in the ability to make claims about the direct impacts of intermediary support.

A BEPA report (Hubert, 2010) from 2010 highlights some of the problems of demonstrating quantified impacts in this field. These include the difficulty of developing indicators that will effectively proxy into models to indicate impacts on complex social problems and the lack of a culture of ex-post impact evaluation. Whilst the GECES Social Impact Measurement Sub-Group attempted to build a framework of evaluation for social impact the final report (GECES, 2014) found that further work is required to come up with a set of frameworks and tools by which social impact can be measured. The SIMPACT project developed a toolbox of methods and indicators which can be used to try and understand the impacts of social innovation. Whereas there is progress being made in evaluative approaches to social innovation research this is still under development.

5.6 CONCLUSIONS

From a research perspective one of the key functions of a potential 'Intermediaries Network' will be to broaden the pool of people who are engaging with social innovation ideas and helping to widen our understanding of who intermediaries are. This network directly addresses the criticism that social innovation sometimes operates within a 'silo culture'. It will help to build links and share tools, methods and approaches in order to foster knowledge.

This network will enrich the social innovation research landscape of the future by incorporating new theoretical ideas and fresh models of working. In addition, we hope that by sharing the processes, tools and methods of social innovation beyond the 'usual suspects' could spread the benefits of SI to new sectors and new actors.

In terms of the current research landscape, exploratory research into areas relevant to social innovation intermediaries has been facilitated, in part, by the funding that the European Union has made available for social innovation research, particularly within the FP7 and the Horizon 2020 funding schemes. This funding has been instrumental in providing a basis to social innovation research and has pushed the scope of exploratory, experimental and evaluative research. From the perspective of the 'Intermediaries Network' our role will be to ensure dialogue across these different projects and across research 'scales'. The 'Intermediaries Network' has an important role to play in research because it can help to facilitate a broadening of scope for social innovation researchers. By incorporating new and more unusual actors we can facilitate the developments of new tools and methods for research.

However there is further work to be done in expanding the theoretical basis for social innovation, and in understanding the development of innovation, where innovation comes from, how it can be effectively supported and by whom. In addition there is a need to consolidate our understanding of how we can understand impacts, the outputs from the SIMPACT project will be important in further developing our understanding of how to do this effectively. Social innovation is still a new research field, but it is also one that has received support in its early development. This has been important for ensuring that there is the time and space to understand and improve processes, however, as with many fields an evidence base is required for intermediaries in order to demonstrate the important role that they have to play in forging more effective and efficient solutions to social problems.

Effective evidence bases engage with a wide variety of different experimental and evaluative methods in order to build up a picture of a field. It is important, then, that research on social innovation intermediaries continues to utilise a number of different methodological approaches in order to be able to understand many dimensions of social innovation and intermediaries.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

6 Cities and Regions Development

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6.1 INTRODUCTION

In the current debate on social innovation the perspective that works on integrating the social content and social cohesion in innovation processes is one of the most prominent and promising and relies on the research question about how social innovation is a productive domain when applied to context-based initiatives of territorial development ²⁷ (Moulaert et al, 2013). Specifically, the perspectives developed by authors like Moulaert, Nussbaumer, Sekia, MacCallum, Martinelli, González, etc. claims that the integration of social elements on the territorial development approach (such as the valorisation of local culture, aspects related to networks, the use of “intangible” elements facilitating a more inclusive territorial development processes, etc.) is something valuable and innovative in that field when it combines social and economic aims.

Two are the dimensions on which the territorial development approach for social innovation can be considered innovative with respect to the paradigm of Regional Learning (Capello & Lenzi, 2016) as well as the one of Territorial Innovation Models (Moulaert & Sekia, 2003): i) the pivotal role of the governance of the territories and the social relations that characterise them; ii) the tension to satisfy needs that are not met by the market through empowering local actors.

On the one hand the territorial development approach put at the center of the social innovation processes the model of governance of the local contexts going beyond hierarchical procedures lead by the public administration to introduce new open, participatory and experimental policy making. On the other hands, close to the human development concept from UNDP (2011), the approach relates to the satisfaction of basic needs (Moulaert & Ailenei, 2005; MacCallum et al., 2009; González et al., 2010). Social innovation brings empowerment to local actors in the community. As a result, collective visions and intentions as a fundamental element for collective change and the development of new capabilities for transformation are elaborated (González et al., 2010).

Moulaert and Nussbaumer (2008) define three elements that characterize the territorial development approach for social innovation. The first one is the role of the local level to develop learning processes that can answer the needs or challenges of individuals. The second one refers to the impacts of these learning processes as agent that can trigger the generation of capabilities and competences on individuals through bottom-up and participative modes. Finally, they argue that collective learning processes can facilitate the integration of the social perspective in economic development approaches (Moulaert & Nussbaumer, 2005; 2008).

²⁷ The results synthesized in this document are based on the triangulation of three different sources of information: the literature on the topic, the results of the SIC breakout session conducted in Brussels last October 25th in collaboration with a workshop organised by JPI urban Europe on Urban governance; the questionnaires distributed to accomplish a Delphi survey as subtask in the implementation of T2.1.

Collaboration is a critical condition for developing these learning and social innovation processes. Collaboration (Camarinha-Matos and Afsarmanesh, 2006) is developed in networking frameworks where communication happens through horizontal flows and democratic procedures (communitarian networks; Moulaert & Nussbaumer, 2005). To this extent, territorial development is conceived as a grounded process in 'spatialised' communities, taking inequality into account in the spatial and social distribution of disadvantage. This is especially key when dealing with action-research on hyper-diverse and contested neighbourhoods. So conceived, processes of territorial development have different sites of actions: one of the most solicited is cities and within them its smaller components.

Traditional state-driven top-down revitalisation strategies have resulted in lot of cases in new urban dynamics and tensions, gentrification processes and social exclusion. In Europe ethnic concentration in neighbourhoods' overlaps with situations of social exclusion and deprivation, thus increasing the complexity of hyper-diverse cities. In most cases it is possible to witness a stalled urban regeneration investment across many European cities and disadvantaged neighbourhoods (Arapoglou, 2012). In addition to this phenomenon the crises of municipalities and public administration mainly caused by cuts in the budgets and difficulties in facing new societal challenges are producing barriers in the way in which cities and their authorities design, produce and deliver their services (Deserti & Rizzo, 2015).

Even if some scholars have argued that some cities-based and mixed community programs have led to wider economic transformations of cities, social polarisation and state-led gentrification (Moulaert et al, 2013); in Europe urban contexts (and neighbourhoods within them) have become a privileged unit of observation and policy intervention for social innovation (Concilio & Rizzo, 2016; Ostanel, 2014). In some cases cities-based initiatives have been key to producing social cohesion, and transforming power relations and socio-spatial inequalities (Oosterlynck et al, 2013).

It was in 2011 when the report, ***Cities of Tomorrow – Challenges, visions, ways forward*** (European Commission, 2011) inspired the idea of opening innovation processes to citizens and intended to support a long wave of social innovation in cities. A few years later in fact, the first ***URBACT Capitalisation report*** (2015) pointed out the strategic role of cities as a catalyst of social innovation. The report demonstrated how social innovation is playing a twofold pivotal role in the process that bridges more traditional forms of city governance towards more participatory ones, as well as innovative approaches, especially in the time of crisis, to address major societal challenges.

Focusing on participative approaches (Deserti & Rizzo, 2014), an impressive number of EU cities have used participative techniques for a wide range of problems. Some of the most interesting developments are happening in the area of service design. Cities and regions are experimenting with new policy, methodology and tools that support participation by projects of co-production and co-design. From citizen involvement in the research of a solution for the problems which affect them to hackathons and competitions to develop new services or apps that make citizens projects possible.

6.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

What role could EU cities and regional networks play in supporting this new wave of changes in cities and municipalities? And how can research centers in the field of social innovation support the sustainable development of cities and regions?

To be effective, social innovation should not be considered as a tool box that could provide rapid solutions to pressing problems ((Moulaert et al, 2013) but a highly contextual matter that need to be deeply analyzed within particular institutional and spatial settings. To this extent, territorial development is conceived as a grounded process in 'spatialised' communities, taking inequality into account in the spatial and social distribution of disadvantage. This is especially key when dealing with action-research on hyper- diverse and contested neighbourhoods.

Networks plays a fundamental role since they are the natural intermediaries between people and territories, cities and regions and the national and EU government level to present and include city needs and have city priorities be reflected into policies, recommendations and programmes of future development. Networks quite often are intermediaries between cities and research centers on social innovation for the development of joint research projects and activities. Even though a consistent number of cities and regions networks are active in Europe with a pan-European orientation and vision, currently, we can observe that a specific network on cities and social innovation does not yet exist. Moreover, social innovation is an emerging topic and an interest of almost all networks.

The landscape of the European networks on cities and regions includes: generalist networks, those that focus on cities as complex entities that deal with transversal issues at a different scale from urban planning to neighbourhood revitalisation, from migration to family policy. These networks aim to represent their members at different governmental levels and to influence the policies and the contexts at different levels with respect to their priorities and needs. Objectives of these networks are redefined every time depending on the changes in the challenges they face. Examples of these networks include: Eurocities, ENoLL, Eurotowns, ICLEI, the Covenant of Majors, Intercultural Cities Network, REVES the network of cities of social economy²⁸, Polis network, and EU cities and regions networks for innovative transportations²⁹. Specialised networks focus on specific city needs, problems or challenges. These networks aim to represent their members interest at different governmental levels with respect to their societal issues that shape their identity and their intents.

In this analysis, we have decided not to consider this category but to adopt a criterion that allows us to distinguish networks with respect to their degree of commitment to social innovation. These networks are still not aware about the potentiality of SI in relation to their mission and they can be considered unusual suspects (those that have still discover SI or that do not show interest in it). Among them, it is

²⁸ <http://www.revesnetwork.eu/wp>

²⁹ <http://www.polisnetwork.eu/about/about-polis>

possible to list: European smart cities³⁰; energy cities³¹; connecting cities, networks aiming to build up a connected infrastructure of media facades, urban screens and projection sites to circulate artistic and social content³²; Future cities, European network to face climate change³³; IRPE European network of cities and water³⁴; and the European Social Network (ESN).

Some specific initiatives and Commission programmes are also really active at the intersection of cities/regions and social innovation. Among them, two are of particular interest since they are active in transferring SI knowledge from research to everyday urban and territorial development practices.

Urbact II is a EU initiative (jointly financed by the ERDF and the Member States) that enables cities to work together to develop solutions to major urban challenges, re-affirming the key role they play in facing increasingly complex societal changes. URBACT helps cities to develop pragmatic solutions that are new and sustainable, and that integrate economic, social and environmental dimensions. It enables cities to share good practices and lessons learned with all professionals involved in urban policy throughout Europe. URBACT II comprises 550 different sized cities and their Local Support Groups, 61 projects, 29 countries, and 7,000 active local stakeholders.

European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on Smart Cities and Communities has the general aim of coming up with innovative solutions to the major environmental, societal and health challenges facing European cities today.

The Citizen Focus action cluster brings together partners who are interested in fostering citizen participation in the fields of ICT, mobility and energy in cities. It is reflected in project proposals for creating ICT platforms for crowd funding and collaboration and also in the creation of apps and services by citizens themselves to solve the issues they have identified in their cities.

Many organisations, institutes and departments around Europe have now been established to research the concept of social innovation. Although none of them is formally devoted to study and research Urban Social Innovation, many of the research projects carried out by these actors are experimenting or observing social innovation for cities and territorial development. What follows is a first attempt at collating such a list:

- Skoll Centre for Social Entrepreneurship, Oxford, UK;
- Stanford Centre on Philanthropy and Civil Society, USA;
- Centre for Social Innovation, Vienna, Austria;
- Fondazione Ugo Brodolini, Italy;

³⁰ <http://www.smart-cities.eu>

³¹ <http://www.energy-cities.eu>

³² <http://connectingcities.net>

³³ <http://www.future-cities.eu>

³⁴ <http://ierpe.eu/articles.php?lng=en&pg=157>

- Institut für Soziale Innovation, Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg, Germany;
- Centrum für Soziale Investitionen und Innovationen, Heidelberg University, Germany;
- Dasra, India;
- Sinnergiak Social Innovation, Basque Country;
- Tilburg Social Innovation Lab. Netherlands;
- NESTA, UK;
- INSEAD Social Innovation Center, Spain;
- The International Research Center for Social Innovation (CERIIS), LUISS Guido Carli University and by ItaliaCamp, Italy;
- The Centre for Social Innovation at Cambridge Judge Business School, University of Cambridge.

The main areas of research of the organisations and institutions mentioned above are the following:

- social innovation and open innovation;
- social entrepreneurship;
- social economy;
- social innovation sustainability;
- SI measurement;
- SI development models;
- social enterprises; and
- SI impacts.

Each of these areas has its own relevance in the contexts of the cities and regions network. But the relative new trend in the field of research relevant to be mentioned here is the emerging of Urban Social Innovation as a research theme in many Department of Urban Studies and Planning, as well as in the Department of Design where it quite often represents a new typology of projects for experimenting new urban planning trajectories as well as for experimenting with service design for the ideation of new public and collaborative services (Concilio & Rizzo, 2016).

Within these research centers, the main issues under investigation are:

- new participative governance;
- open policy experimentation;
- new participatory planning;
- citizens cultural and behavioural changes;
- municipalities cultural changes;
- resilience and sustainable everyday cities;
- new public and collaborative services; and
- new digital agendas.

6.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

Few but relevant reports have underlined over the last years the relation between social innovation and the cities and regions development.

The report ***Cities of Tomorrow – Challenges, visions, ways forward*** (European Commission, 2011) made the following recommendations and links between the cities of tomorrow and the development of social innovation, affirming that:

“Creativity and innovation are part of the standard toolbox of a city that is attractive and competitive. However, the concept of a ‘creative milieu’ is sometimes restricted to specific social groups: workers from the knowledge or leisure industries, artists, etc. But in the context of economic and financial crisis, social innovation offers an opportunity to widen the public space for creativity and innovation” (p. 38).

“To properly exploit social innovation, cities face the challenge of rescaling governance and articulating social innovation projects and strategies with their overall investment strategies. One way of doing this is to focus attention on public opinion about urban amenities and on adjusting priorities according to recommended changes – even if they’re not spectacular – or to use wider participatory processes, such as participatory budgeting, foresights involving citizens, etc. (p. 96)”

The report ***Social innovation in cities*** (Urbact II, 2015) a few years after looks at social innovation from the point of view of cities. Social innovation is intended to mean innovative solutions, new forms of organisation and new interactions to tackle social issues:

“In order to promote and benefit from social innovation, cities need to change their governance systems and open the process to all actors: from the administration to citizens including NGOs and other stakeholders. These changes in city governance are themselves a form of social innovation. The innovation resides in the fact that governance is not seen as an isolated process, separate from reality and citizens, but seeks to experiment with new working methods within the administration together with stakeholders and citizens. (p. 7)”

The ***Fondazione Brodolini Report*** (Sgaragli, 2015) focuses on a new developmental and economic model in which cities are configuring themselves as new ecosystems of innovations:

“This is social innovation in action where, increasingly, new emerging services are created by social entrepreneurs, motivated not by profit, but by an ambition to tackle inequality and disadvantage. In this new paradigm, civic authorities also play a key role – enabling, supporting and providing the trust that acts as the glue in collaborative settings. At its root is a belief in the power of the crowd – people power – and the importance of tapping into the only resource that is not diminishing – human resource. Harnessing this power is the key to mobilising social innovation in our cities, and to tackling the shape shifting challenges we face” (Sgaragli, 2015, p. 152).

The Milano councillor for innovation interviewed in the report declared: “Social innovation is distinctive both in its outcomes and in its relationships, in the new forms of cooperation and collaboration that it brings. The city is the place where phenomena take place with greater intensity, therefore there is the necessity to design and adopt new working practices and new legal instruments to encode new ideas – products, services and models – that simultaneously meet social needs effectively” (Sgaragli, 2014).

The URBACT online chat session³⁵ on barriers to SI in cities (30/09/2014) has developed an interesting summary of the main obstacles to be overcome to establish a supportive policy environment for SI in cities.

Some approaches to overcome obstacles and barriers are: the different forms of financial support that may be particularly relevant to social purpose organisations that can also be relevant at the city level include:

- grants for early stage development;
- prizes for social innovation;
- debt instruments;
- patient capital;
- social investment funds;
- crowdfunding;
- loans;
- social impact bonds;
- venture philanthropy.

And non-financial resources include:

- incubators;
- safe spaces for R&D (e.g. labs for social innovation) ;
- business development support (e.g. accelerator programmes) ;
- mentoring and coaching;
- peer to peer support;
- professional services of various kinds including: legal advice, marketing; services, fiscal and accounting services, HR and governance advice, and strategy/organisational development advice.”

Other key elements emerge from the already quoted URBACT II report *Social Innovation in Cities* as fundamental for establishing a vivid SI ecosystem in cities, which are:

- the need of support for the generation of new ideas;
- the role of co-production;

³⁵ Retrieved 02/05/2016 from: http://www.sustainable-everyday-project.net/urbact-socialinnovationincities/files/2014/07/Chat-session-report_Trícia-Hackett.pdf

- the impact of smart finance;
- the potential of new service co-produced delivery models;
- the value of unusual suspects; and,
- the prerequisite of a strong evidence base.

These and other reports (Pelka & Markmann, 2015) by discussing the main obstacles and barriers to SI also suggest the area of research that must be deepened in order to produce positive impact on the take off and diffusion of SI as a form of innovation.

In the following, the main topics or areas of research to enhance the inclusion of SI as an asset of sustainable development for cities and regions are listed: the capacity building of citizens as well as policy makers and public actors to implement SI; the design of the policy for social innovation; and the conduction of real experiments and pilots of SI. Many examples exist at regional as well as cities level of policy that are supporting the development of laboratories and R&D initiative for the introduction of the culture of innovation for territorial and urban development. These infrastructures take different shapes, have different aims and playing different roles: living lab, fab lab, open labs, co-working spaces, creative cities labs, makes-pace (Battisti and Sandro 2014; Schachter et alii, 2012, Concilio and Rizzo, 2016, Rizzo et alii, 2013, Rizzo et alii, 2015) For example, Slimmer Leven in Eindhoven has created a new emergency service for the elderly. Amersfoort in the Netherlands is encouraging its officers to become 'free-range civil servants' and go out into the community and listen. The results are already visible in their work on a new park located on the site of a derelict hospital and on sustainable food. They have recognised the need to transform themselves and the way that they work in order to transform their city.

Policy Design

Cities should develop an appropriate knowledge base to implement social innovation. Many of the problems cities have to deal with are much more complex than they appear at first sight. It is crucial to collect evidence about the real situation and explore the underlying dynamics of development (Concilio et al., 2014). In order to identify the problems correctly and gain the proper depth of insight, cities should involve stakeholders in the provision and evaluation of data and the ongoing monitoring of the consequences of interventions.

At the same time, cities should acquire knowledge on how to conduct new participatory processes aiming to build collaborative services. This involves a process of participative rethinking or re-envisioning the 'opportunity structures' available to cities in the light of a realistic assessment of both short-term and long-term trends. In this sense, cities are ideally placed to reconnect with local citizens and bring together all stakeholders to ensure a total resource mobilisation more closely aligned with real needs.

Building bridges between bottom-up levels of experimentation and policies is the main research issue in this area. Until now, few attempts have been done: the experiment of Mind Lab in the Netherlands; the

project of la 27eme region in France, and UK policy lab. All these three intermediaries have been established by governments, which are using design and design methods and tools to design policy and aiming to produce collaborative policy by combining data and knowledge with evidence based information from projects and citizens.

In 2007, La 27eme Region was created as a laboratory of the new policy in the digital age. It has two objectives: to promote the production and exchange of innovative ideas between the regions, and give policymakers and citizens the elements to understand the possibilities offered by the digital age and technology. It works on a wide range of themes that are central to current and future regional policy.

The Rhône-Alpes Region (FR)³⁶ puts employment and anticipation of change at the centre of its regional strategy for economic development and innovation. In their efforts to secure (future) jobs, they integrate workplace innovation, social dialogue and support to the social economy as key elements (OECD, 2011).

Emilia Romagna is a context rich of SIs among many examples that could be mentioned here many authors affirm that the spread of SI in this Italian regions depends on the high attitude to cooperate in Emilia Romagna, the level of density on entrepreneurs; the degree of innovation that many regional norms show (Emilia Romagna Region SIC case study).

Focusing on a new developmental and economic model, cities and regions are configuring themselves as new ecosystems of innovations(Sgaragli, 2014) where authorities and governments not only are in charge of developing the policy that can best support the ecosystem but are the main actors in leading the demand and the process of innovation.

Design of the SI experimentation

More european cities seem to embrace experimentation than before. The drivers for this include the redundancy of the status quo for existing services, in the light of financial cuts and rising demand. As a consequence, municipalities need to learn new ways of working and producing their services (Deserti & Rozzi, 2015). Creating the right conditions for experimentation includes providing space for the design, prototyping and evaluation of new products and services. Cities have different ways of doing this. In this area of research, the most interesting results are coming from the application of the design thinking approach to the development of new public sector projects. Design thinking has a double advantage to work from the beginning with the idea of engagement of the end users of a solution in order to design it and relies on an iterative approach based on the development of prototypes to be tested in real contexts which feed and support the need of conducting experiments and deal with the process of failure and success in cities. Cities are becoming open laboratories in which to test different solutions.

³⁶ <http://www.rhonealpes.fr/576-schema-regional-developpement-economique.htm>

Participatory citizenship/ engagement

Cities should learn how to mobilise people and resources around strategic challenges. Given the scarcity of public resources, it does not make sense to make heavy investments in isolated physical projects that cannot provide evidence that they will make a clear contribution to integrated strategic goals. Human and material resources need to be combined and concentrated on the most important problems and the ones where cities realistically have the most ability to achieve change.

Stimulated by a series of citizen-driven projects (Barcelona Living lab, TSI Turin Social Innovation Project, Helsinki design Lab, Arhus Public Library to mention some of them), city leaders committed their administration to increase collaboration with the population in a somewhat opportunistic way, benefiting from citizen participation to deliver public services at a lower cost. This economic strategy in fact engages the city administration in a user-driven approach. Both internally and externally the change process is systematically based on stakeholder advisory groups, exchange with the population, experimenting with new forms of collaboration with citizens, taking risks by giving them assignments and so on. The city administration thereby reconnects with citizens, restarts from users' needs and finds itself in a better position to think up more appropriate administrative mechanisms and design more user-friendly and cost-efficient public services.

Subjects under study in this area are: how to build PPPs, Public Private People Partnerships; business models for public services; and forms of incentives for citizens partnerships.

The need is to better understand specific types of engagement activities and the particular functions they perform in developing and sustaining social innovations from the micro level to the meso and macro level.

Measurement of the impact of citizens engagement on society

Currently the field of innovation research has not produce scientific evidence on the impact of citizens engagement on society. The phenomenon is too recent and research on this subjects are still concentrated on experimenting co-creation approaches (like codesign and coproduction). There is a need to develop common impact indicators. There is a lack of research on how barriers have been overcome and how established social indicators such as poverty, social exclusion, and joblessness are being improved by social innovation solutions. Evidence of the benefits of participation for society and individuals is limited. There is thus a need to rigorously evaluate and understand the impact of citizen engagement on society and individuals.

The role of the public sector in promoting social innovation

The large number of social innovation cases studied or implemented in different EU projects: SIMPACT, TEPSIE, WILCO, Seismic, SI-DRIVE, LIPSE, My Neighbourhood, and Peripheria, suggest that the pub-

lic sector has an important role to play in directing experimentation with SI as well as in boosting, triggering and supporting it. The public sector can act as an innovative force in itself, but can also play a significant role in providing support and creating enabling framework conditions (designing innovative policy, providing financial support and non-financial support, creating infrastructure, services, networks, examples, enabling legal frameworks and disseminating practices and methods). It is then relevant to further explore how cities and regions can produce a positive ecosystem for SI.

Regional strategies that incorporate social innovation are only beginning to emerge. Many French regions already integrate social innovation in some form in their strategies for innovation and economic development, as a recent inquiry from *Avisé*³⁷ (Ingénierie et services pour entreprendre autrement) and the ARF (Association des Régions de France) shows. Most of them see social innovation linked to the social economy and/or work organisation, but also various forms of incubation, co-creation with citizens, initiatives in the health and care sector, etc. come in.

Navarra Modernais a regional plan that used a highly participatory model involving key regional actors to develop their strategy, with a focus on human capital. It combines technological and social innovation. More than 3,000 people were involved in consultations which included surveys of citizens, interviews with experts, consultation committees and talks with organisations such as trade unions and business representatives. They use the image of a tree to illustrate how their strategy works. The Basque Country shows how a region can use a wide range of approaches to achieve social innovation. When linked to 'traditional' technological innovations, it can find solutions in areas such as health, transport or dealing with the aged.

Promoting social innovation requires clear strategies and institutional support. Innobasque is a non-profit private company created in 2007 to coordinate and promote innovation across the Basque Country. It acts as a regional innovation partnership. The Board gathers 57 leading actors from the region. It includes the rectors of the three universities, the chief executive of the cooperative group Mondragon, representatives from three ministries as well as chief executives from leading enterprises in the region. Innobasque works at the policy level on many aspects of technological innovation but also brings in the general public through reflection groups and workshops such as its world café events that focus on ways to promote societal transformations. The OECD described Innobasque as leading work on social innovation and fostering collaborative action and joint research in the region³⁸.

6.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

³⁷ http://qui-sommes-nous.avisé.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/RA2015Avisé_Webplanche.pdf

³⁸ https://www.siceurope.eu/sites/default/files/uploads/documents/SOCIAL%20INNOVATION%20IN%20THE%20BASQUE%20COUNTRY_v6_0.pdf

The current state of research and knowledge production on SI in cities and regions can be considered as organised into 2 main strands: 1) the area of knowledge based on observation and description of the on-going phenomena; 2) the area of knowledge related to those design processes, methodologies and tools more suitable to ideate and produce sustainable SI.

In the first area there are different actors committed to producing knowledge and results by exploiting a case studies based approach. The aim of this kind of research is twofold: to conduct an ex-post analysis of the observed cases to produce ex post measurement of their impacts, to deliver guidelines and lessons learnt, to describe the evolution of SI phenomenon with respect to different criteria such as the welfare regime; the geographical location; and the typologies of SI to mention some of them. Within this area of knowledge, a special action is the one carried out by networks (like Eurocities, Eurotowns, Reves) that are producing a large number of case studies to support knowledge transfer and exchange among their cities and regions. Here the aim of this research activity is to discover and disseminate and amplify a positive example of SI to promote their diffusion and replication. The used methodologies vary depending on the aim of each specific research project: surveys, literature review and quantitative analysis are more present in research that aims to describe some or more aspects of SI in cities; case studies, interviews, secondary source analysis, and qualitative observations are more used in projects that aim to extrapolate knowledge and lessons learnt to support a further diffusion of SI.

Further research is required to produce detailed longitudinal case studies, based on a) recruiting a stratified and structured sample of initiatives; b) implementing specific quantitative and harmonised monitoring measures to track participation, contributions (including specific and joint finance), activities, outputs and outcomes from the initiatives; (changes in) linkages and joint activities among participants and between participants and third parties; and time-series data on progress towards project-specific and study-wide objectives at neighbourhood and/or (as appropriate) city level. This quantitative evidence should be complemented by interviews with individuals and businesses that have contributed to or benefited from initiatives. This will advance our understanding of the most important factors behind the success or failure of smart city initiatives.

The second area identifies a new role for research which is linked to the paradigm of open innovation and making.

The paradigm of open innovation suggests that SI in cities has to be designed and produced collaboratively; the idea of making suggests that researchers are involved in the design, experimentation and delivery of SI. If the open innovation paradigm has emerged in the domain of theories of innovation and in the last decade has gained an over exposition as the most productive approach to innovation, the idea of making in research is less known and practiced but it is the main research approach in the area of design that is usually referred to as action research. Today participatory design, design thinking and action research are the methodologies that are used to conduct pilots and experimentation of SI in cities.

People are co-producing the solutions they would like to benefit from in all dimensions of their daily life. Neighbourhood populations are inventing SIs that are taking the form of collaborative services available only thanks to the engagement of citizens in their production and delivery. These creative initiatives if supported through a process of long term design, experimentation and prototyping may develop into new successful businesses (Rizzo et al., 2015) based on the mechanism of co-production. These mechanisms of collaboration are today the basis for rethinking the delivery of public services and transforming the classic public sector offering into a complex collaborative process among different stockholders and actors.

The approach of participatory design challenges (Manzini & Rizzo) the traditional (shorter) design project format and is based on building long-term working relations between different stakeholders and tangible and intangible resources, so that experimentation and innovation can emerge from the continuous matchmaking of diverse groups, their needs and competences within specific contexts.

It is also important to mention here the relation between social innovation and cohesion policies (WILCO, 2014). For example, some early work on social innovation came out of urban studies itself as an interdisciplinary field. Singocom, funded under the fifth framework programme, is a good example of a project that focuses on the interdisciplinary tools of urban studies on social innovation. Social Polis as the Social Platform on Cities and Social Cohesion continues this tradition. The projects also exhibited little interest in working on theory, choosing instead to work on proactive experimentations. Research questions underlined by the research projects and products on SI in cities and regions touch some of the basic principles on how to develop sustainable and innovative urban and regional contexts:

- How can social innovation be integrated with the development of cities and the cities' tangible infrastructures?
- How can we design new policy for social innovation urban and regional ecosystems?
- What is participatory planning in the light of the new participatory citizens movements?
- How can social innovation be designed?
- How can we support collaborative processing within urban and regional contexts?
- What are the practices, drivers and roles played by cities in promoting social innovation?
- What are the main obstacles and barriers for cities to promote and make the most of social innovation?
- What steps have been undertaken to overcome those obstacles and barriers?
- How can cities replicate and scale up social innovation?

6.5 IMPACT

The impact of research on SI for the development of cities and regions is testified by the growing number of case studies of SI and by the proliferation of toolboxes, scientific papers and publications on participatory design/action research as an approach to develop SI in public sector and in cities. This production has had the positive effect of increasing the attention of cities and regions on the potential of social innovation and on the potentialities that participatory design and pilot approaches can have in support of the diffusion of SI as an asset of innovation.

In consequence of this dissemination impact it is possible to observe 2 other typologies of impact:

1. A change in the culture of the cities and regions management and employees. These new evidences and results have produced the diffusion of the culture of piloting, experimenting and using evidence-based approaches to innovate in cities and regions;
2. A new wave of investments. For example, it is possible to mention here the development of specific EU programmes, like URBACTII and CAPS, that experiment with social innovation in cities. Or another example can be found in the inclusion of the topic of SI in the larger debate of experimenting with new technologies in the development of smart city and smart region policy that include SI and citizens' engagement at the core of their action.

Moreover, research on cities and regions development and SI has to deal with some barriers and weakness that might prevent its mature development. The first and general difficulty that has to be mentioned is the fact that research in this field is quite often conducted on the field and through the development of real pilots. This implies the direct engagement of public authorities and different governmental levels in long terms experimentation that quite often cannot be sustainable for this kind of organisations. More specifically:

1. Regions and cities authorities and institutions quite often operate in conditions of scarcity of resources. This fact may prevent them in investing in innovation and experimentation since these activities are perceived as do not have an immediate impact on every days activity and emergency;
2. Regions and cities authorities and institution still need to develop a culture of innovation as a source of continuous learning and improvement of their performance and behaviours.

6.6 CONCLUSIONS

The intersection between cities and regions development and SI is already a well promising area of research and application. The convergence among the two themes has been strongly supported by different processes, among them:

1. The innovation in the way in which the study of the territories and their development in academic

context. Even though there are still resistances in including social innovation as a asset of change in the design of territorial and urban planning (and the fact that social innovation is never explicitly mention in the Urban Agenda for Europe) there are also many evidences of the fact that urban planners and cities designers are heavily experimenting with social innovation;

2. The massive investment of the EU on social cohesion and social innovation;
3. The new societal challenges that are emerging at territorial and cities level that are asking for innovative solutions like new product, services and processes to support fragile people that are not supported any more by classical welfare solution.

What is still lacking is a robust process of compression of the impact of these new waves of involvement of citizens in the development of their cities and territories. There is a need to frame, model, and measure the different co-creation mechanisms that are going on in urban and peripheral places and understand their impact on the development of a more sustainable society.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

7 Social Economy

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7.1 INTRODUCTION

Throughout the world, the social economy represents a main mover in terms of more stable and decent jobs' creation, social cohesion, local sustainable development and social innovation.

Social economy should not be equated with other concepts such as "social business" or "social entrepreneurship". At EU level, a widely recognised definition - used also by the EU level platform "Social Economy Europe" - is the one put forward by the European Parliament in its Resolution on the Social Economy, adopted in 2009. It highlights the common values of social economy enterprises that represent a diversity of sectors of activity and size:

- the primacy of democracy, social stakeholder participation and individual and social objectives over gain;
- the defence and implementation of the principles of solidarity and responsibility;
- the conjunction of the interests of its user members with the general interest;
- democratic control by its members;
- voluntary and open membership;
- management autonomy and independence in relation to public authorities;
- the allocation of the bulk of surpluses in pursuit of the aims of sustainable development and of service to its members in accordance with the general interest.³⁹

It is possible to identify the social economy community, in its broadest sense, as a diverse and multi-level ecosystem, made up of a myriad of actors, operating within and among European Member States, up to extend even abroad.

Research represents only one, yet extremely important, of the fields in which this community declines itself, contributing to the theoretical and empirical progress, thus, ultimately, to the concrete impact of the social economy sector on the real life of individuals through and towards a series of different "ideas" (products, services, models, processes) which can be linked to the concept of social innovation.

³⁹ European Parliament resolution of 19 February 2009 on Social Economy (2008/2250(INI))

A lot has been done by academic and institutional researchers to gather national, European and international facts and figures in order to identify the purpose of general interest of this economy and to characterize its peculiarities.

Social innovation emerges as a "quasi-concept" (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017) at the end of 20th century due to the crisis of the synergy between the market and state that had previously existed. It could also be the consequence of a somewhat forgotten crisis of a cultural nature. The latter consisted of the erosion of the ideology of progress: it criticized the lack of limits and excess of speed of the system for it to be sustainable and manifested itself through the new social movements, who questioned the remaining forms of domination in the welfare state. These dynamics over time became linked to changes in forms of public engagement, characterized by an emphasis on pragmatism, local action, concrete experiences, which in turn lead to a change of terminology.

Relying on a number of currents that put forward the concepts of national systems of innovation, local production systems or actor-network theory – there is a growing recognition that innovation is not just technological or organizational, but also inter-institutional in a given territory and thus is a deeply social process. Although most research funding has been channeled towards technological innovation, it is becoming widely accepted that social innovation is a complement to technology-driven solutions. Indeed, in technology-intensive areas such as energy, health care and transport the social dimension of innovation is seen as crucial (see also www.wilcoproject.eu).

It is important to point out that research in the field of social innovation *per se* is still in its early stages (European Commission, 2013), and this is one of the reasons why its analysis is frequently carried out alongside the social economy phenomenon. This somehow implies the acknowledgment of the ambivalent nature of social innovation as its constitutive feature (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). The documentation and analysis of the social and solidarity economy impacts' evaluation practices, in a social innovation perspective, including the trade-off between compliance and innovation, has consistently contributed to the development of social innovations in its practical aspects (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

Before 2008, social innovation practice was far more advanced than its theoretical skeleton. However, the financial and economic crisis that hit Europe and the whole world, displayed once more the ability of social economy actors to shape more self-reliant communities of people, as well as geographical and economic environments. This led to a widespread recognition of the greater resilience of a development model - a sustainable alternative to the dominant one – which not only tackles societal challenges in an innovative way, but does so *for* and *with* citizens. This, together with the adoption of the Europe 2020 strategy for a smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, is one more reason that greatly influenced the emergence of a renewed attention to the potential of social economy in terms of social innovation.

Research has been catching up in these last years, also thanks to increased interest (and investment) from research funding bodies, policy makers and other stakeholders, and it is widely acknowledged that social innovation research and practice need to be better linked through a mutual recognition of their different purposes in contemporary society (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

7.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

The thematic scope within the social economy research community seems to be focused on the ability of social economy and its entities to recognise both long-standing and new social needs and/or problems, and to address them through original solutions⁴⁰ emerging from new collaborations established among and within a variety of sectors (private sector, public sector or third sector) and scales (international, European, national, regional or local level).

In this context, the hybrid concept of social innovation will be treated from a dual perspective: on the one hand, it will be discussed as an input influencing a specific mechanism of governance (such as those characterising the social economy entities); on the other hand, it will consist rather in the result of the processes linked to the latter. Thus, in the first case, social innovation is considered as an independent variable, featured by a particular mode of action and social change. In the second case, it is taken into account as an output depending on specific governance processes. In any case, however, the concept of social innovation cannot be assigned to any paradigm within any single social science. This is positive for advancing science and exploring new avenues for research. However, it also causes plenty of repetition and overlap in some of the research already conducted, as well as recurring gaps that remain unaddressed (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Even if the research field analysing social innovation can and has drawn on several quite different disciplines, including economics, political science, sociology, social policy, and in fewer cases, cultural studies (European Commission, 2013), in our case, it is obviously at the intersection of a number of them that the investigation is carried out. This, always focusing on the primacy of individual and of social objective over capital though.

Within the social economy community, it is possible to identify a certain number of relevant actors, characterized by a particular dynamism and innovation in that research field which analyses the multiple facets of social economy, including its relations, in terms of causality and/or impact, with social innovation. The added value emerging from the research process among this community consists precisely in the building and sharing of a new and socially relevant knowledge, which is the product resulting from a diversified participation, and whose value is not therefore limited to the sum of the contributions of individual actors.

⁴⁰ In terms of products, technologies, processes, strategies, marketing methods and/or organisational models.

In order to give an overview of the composition of the research landscape, which animates and shapes the theoretical debate on the relation between social economy and social innovation, this chapter will particularly focus on the contribution of four national and international research networks covering a vast spectrum of countries, in Europe and beyond. These are:

- **EMES** (emes.net) - This international research network for social economy was founded in 1996 by an international group of scholars which launched the first research network devoted to social enterprise, supported by EU funding. In 2002, a hard core of researchers having reached an exceptional level of mutual understanding decided to leave this community to establish a non-profit association (ASBL under Belgian law).

EMES is made up of a multitude of established university research centres and individual researchers aiming at gradually building up an international corpus of theoretical and empirical knowledge, pluralistic in disciplines and methodologies, around a number of social economy-related concepts, among which social innovation.

The first research programme concerned “the emergence of social enterprises in Europe” (1996-2000). At that time, **EMES was composed of European university research centres and individual researchers**. Only in 2013, after many years of collaborative research and projects jointly conducted with researchers from other regions, EMES decided to open its membership and counts to date researchers from 5 continents of the world (emes.net/who-we-are/). Today, 12 institutional members take part in EMES, leading research centers acting together to carry out influential collaborative research, 229 individual researchers and PhD students from various disciplines, exchanging opportunities for joint publications and research initiatives, as well as a solid network of 8 international partners and “sisters organizations” supporting EMES’ mission around the world. Among those partners figures also Iris Network, the Italian national network of the institutions of research on social enterprise which will be treated below. The institutional members have a majority of seats in the Board of directors, which meets at least twice a year to discuss issues related with priority issues and to monitor the progress of the Network. The other two categories of individual members (researchers and PhD students) also have representatives appointed to the Board. Finally, in 2004 EMES has created a Coordination Unit composed of professional staff supporting its project activities.

- **Iris Network** (irisnetwork.it) - As previously mentioned, Iris is an Italian national network of research institutes on social enterprise. It conducts empirical and theoretical investigations to facilitate a thorough understanding of social enterprise organizations, stressing on their role and boosting their ability to act.

The network promotes reflection, analysis and exchange of information between research institutions, research organizations, universities, individual researchers, and between them and the social entrepreneurship world.

The 31 Iris' members belong to two categories:

- a) universities, departments, institutes, research and training centres with significant activities on social enterprise;
- b) social enterprises, their representative organizations and coordination, public or private bodies interested in the association's activity.

- **Euricse** (www.euricse.eu) - The European Research Institute on Cooperative and Social Enterprises belongs to the first category of Iris' members, with which it shares the headquarters in Trento (Italy). The Institute figures among the 12 EMES' institutional members, too.

Euricse was founded in 2008 by Cooperatives Europe, Federazione Trentina della Cooperazione, Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Trento e Rovereto, Province of Trento and the University of Trento.

The Institute's activities address issues of national and international (and in particular European) interest, and its approach favours openness and collaboration with other research centres, both at national and international level.

Euricse is a research centre designed to promote knowledge development and innovation in the field of cooperatives, social enterprises and non-profit organizations. The Institute's aim is to deepen the understanding of these actors and their impact on economic and social development, also in terms of innovation, furthering their growth and assisting them to work more effectively, also favouring fruitful influences within the social economy sector.

- **CIRIEC** (www.ciriec.ulg.ac.be) - The International Centre of Research and Information on the Public, Social and Cooperative Economy, originally called "International Centre of Research and Information on the Collective Economy", is a non-governmental international scientific organisation, founded in 1947 by a French economist teaching at the University of Geneva, Prof. E. Milhaud, who had founded in 1908 the *Annals of Collective Economy*⁴¹.

The International Centre of Research and Information on the Public, Social and Cooperatives Economy, today based in Liege (Belgium), brings together more than 150 experts active in public, social and cooperative economy. This network is coordinated by the International Scientific Council

⁴¹ The scientific journal that was the basis on which the association itself was then built in 1947.

and it has the support of two commissions, one devoted to public services and public enterprises, and the other to the social and cooperative economy.

The main aim of the organisation is to undertake and promote the collection of information, the publication of research works on economic sectors and to carry out activities oriented towards the provision of services of general interest. In this sense, the social economy sector is one of the most investigated fields.

CIRIEC membership comprises both individual and collective members⁴². Collective members are agencies, enterprises and organizations forming part of the public, cooperative and not-for-profit sectors of the economy and also of any bodies with an interest of a scientific or cultural nature in these economic activities. In countries with a national section⁴³, it is generally the latter which enjoy direct membership of the international association and are primarily concerned with research, publication and the organization of scientific events open to the public.

7.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

There exist a number of dominant topics, in terms of social innovation, within the abovementioned networks constituting the social economy community's research field: EMES, Iris, Euricse, CIRIEC. One can identify both convergences and peculiarities among these networks. From a general perspective, if it is true that the totality of the actors taken into account share a multidisciplinary approach enabling to holistically scrutinize the social innovation concept, and that the available documentation is the product of both proper research projects of the institutional and individual members of each network as well as of funding programmes; it is also evident that the focus investigating the relation between social economy and social innovation is sometimes oriented to the social economy sector as a whole, while others to contributions of specific social economy entities⁴⁴. It seems important to stress once more the fact that, even when considering the first case, the research world does not refer, to date, to social innovation as a concept independent from any mover (when analysing it as a dependent variable) or from wider governance processes (when referring to it as an independent variable). According to Moulaert et al. (2013), the thriving forces of many initiatives for social innovation are the dialectics between the satisfaction of human needs, the mobilization of resources for the local social economy and the organisational as well as institutional dynamics of civil society, including empowerment (further details at Scoppetta et al., 2014, p. 81). Thus, it seems consistent with this evidence to say that social innovation

⁴² Two collective members are currently part of the CIRIEC: INEK-PEO from Cyprus and the Turkish Cooperative Association from Ankara.

⁴³ Currently CIRIEC has 12 national sections in Argentina, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Colombia, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Portugal, Spain and Venezuela.

⁴⁴ Social economy entities are mostly micro, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), including cooperatives, mutual societies, non-profit associations, foundations and social enterprises. See also: http://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/social-economy/index_en.htm

can never be considered as a standing alone topic. In fact, an overarching research theme and focus that seems to emerge is social innovation's strong context dependence, which roots innovation and organizational activity in the political, economic and cultural context at urban and national levels and shape actors' strategies. However, there are internal factors that drive successful social innovation initiatives, e.g. managerial skills or knowledge of the field, maintaining collaborative networks to enhance strategies and minimize risks, ensuring public and financial support as well as to reduce risk when scaling to other geographical settings. Scaling seems to work best for ideas behind social innovation, rather than for finished products, due to the context-dependence of initiatives. Some new research builds on earlier assumptions that social innovation overlaps with social entrepreneurship, but is not the same. Neither does it see its origin confined to the third sector. However, it is important to remember that conceptual ambiguity exists with relation to social innovation, and not one definition of social innovation exists. Theory building of social innovation increasingly takes the importance of environments, appropriate business planning and networking into account. Work needs to be done to capture social innovation impact, which tends to be decentralized, short-lived and not necessarily linked to social innovation by practitioners (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). If it is true, by definition, that its products and processes are absolutely new as well as profoundly context related, hence social innovation can only be investigated with a relativistic and retrospective approach.

Within the **EMES** network, the theoretical and empirical knowledge concerning social innovation is built up considering the latter precisely as a social economy concept. Yet, social innovation does not integrate a focus area *per se* (see also emes.net/focus-areas). EMES' studies deal with social innovation mainly through social enterprises and other social economy entities, as emerges from publications and research projects. Hitherto, a hybrid concept such as Fair Trade appears itself as a social innovation when social enterprises' organisational model reinvents its ambitions from the economic, social and political point of view to achieve social and political aims (Huybrechts, 2012). Social enterprises appear as social innovation engines when their activities tackle social exclusion and unemployment of special categories rather than simply business as usual matters (Gardin et al., 2012). At the same time, local welfare systems developing specific methods and instruments able to manage social inequalities and needs are considered as innovative when they stimulate social cohesion (Evers et al., 2014). While some EMES' research works analyse a number of successful models of social enterprises emerging as individualistic and independent vectors of social innovation, other publications (as for example Gluns & Zimmer, 2013 - as well as McNeill, 2013) seem to be more focused on the social, political and economic structures shaping the (local) contexts in which social innovation takes roots, thus primarily stressing on the conditions determining its emergence. In this sense, a normative approach, complementing the institutional one, appears crucial for the network towards the effectiveness of the social economy organisations' social impact (Laville, 2001), thus also in terms of social innovation. The social innovation's context-dependence also emerges in the framework of the recently closed Social Innovation Europe project (www.siceurope.eu), for which EMES was in charge of the production of a research agenda on social innovation. In July 2016 the network published the result (Brandesen et al., 2016) of a multi-

stakeholders learning exercise. This collaboration made it possible to deeper explore the myriad of existing research approaches to social innovation across different social disciplines, in order to identify both repetitions and unmet needs, on the basis of 13 EU-wide comparative projects (ibid., p.8). It has allowed to identify some transversal core-elements for the reflection on social innovation research in Europe: in line with the strong context-dependence of social innovation, it especially emerges the fact that it usually⁴⁵ overlaps with social entrepreneurship, not being the same though. Further, even if it does not see its origin confined to the third sector, social innovation seems to be a main component of the third sector and some projects show how social innovations successfully deal with resource constraints adapting their strategies accordingly. Other EMES projects highlight the transformative results of co-production between bottom-up and public actors, particular in rural contexts, in health and the financial sector. These evidences appear particularly interesting in a research process focused on the relation between social innovation and the social economy sector, if we take into account the latter's governance model, which includes democratic power sharing of members and participation of external stakeholders. The same context suggests the importance of underlining the resistance towards social innovation caused by unfavourable policy contexts (laws, regulations, financial options).

Current societal challenges are rendering traditional concepts, frameworks and solutions obsolete. In this context, a major challenge for EMES is precisely to make new connections leading to the formulation of new ways to tackle these challenges, *inter alia*: the interplay of civil society/citizen-driven initiatives and actors coming from the private and public sector and the new "order" stemming from those new interactions; the demise of public expression/freedom of speech and the disappearance (via symbolic or *de facto* "invisibilization") of key actors from the public sphere, mostly under the rationale of security threats; the emergence of new institutions as vehicles for citizens' collective action, beyond the (new) "social movements" framework incorporating functions that had been traditionally separated: production, financing, circulation, lobbying; within the social and solidarity economy area itself I think that it would be necessary to make an effort to understand what brought it to such fragmentation level including different national contexts of emergence, uneven access to resources and thus representation, power plays preventing the articulation of joint actions and messages (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Even if primarily focused on Europe, EMES is more and more engaged in the enlargement of its research at a wider geographic level, via the extension of its membership to other regions in the world as well as through international partnerships (e.g. with the UNDP and research networks in Latin America and Eastern Asia).

The social enterprises, not the social economy sector as a whole, represent the dominant **Iris Network's** research topic. In that narrower ecosystem, social innovation is one of the taxonomic categories used when investigating these actors' impact in terms of general interest objectives. In this sense, social innovation is considered a development priority by the network. By the same token, Iris conducts both empirical analysis and theoretical studies which take the forms of reflections, analysis and ex-

⁴⁵According to the Agenda, the evidence on this is mixed and depends on the definition of social innovation.

change of experiences within a collaborative environment made up of research institutions, research organizations, universities, individual researchers, but also between them and the social entrepreneurship world, in order to facilitate a thorough understanding of social enterprise entities, stressing their role as social innovation movers and boosting their ability to act. The rationale moving this cross-sectoral approach emerges from the awareness that only the engagement of a plurality of stakeholders can lead to a holistic and deep understanding of the impact and the potential of these actors in terms of social innovation development processes. In accordance with this goal, in recent years Iris has set up a huge public database (irisnetwork.it/risorse/) of knowledge aiming at boosting innovation in the social enterprises' framework. Moreover, within this corpus one can identify a shift of focus over the years from the traditional non-profit area to initiatives emerging in the field of for profit entrepreneurship, whose eye looks with increasing interest at the production of social value.

As emerges from the **Euricse**'s document entitled *Guiding principles for the study of cooperative and social enterprises*⁴⁶, the European Research Institute “was created to (i) foster, through theoretical and empirical research, the understanding of the nature and potential of cooperatives and social enterprises (i.e., in addition to traditional cooperatives, all enterprise types engaged in the production of goods and services of collective interest or in the management of common resources); (ii) provide training consistent with the specificities of such organizations and the latest findings of research; and (iii) provide consulting services to cooperative and social enterprises and to their representative associations“. The activities and the scientific production of the Institute, managed toward and in collaboration with both the scholarly community and practitioners, are soundly oriented by the need to fill the gap caused by the under-evaluation of the role and importance of social economy organizations such as cooperatives as well as social enterprises by policy makers and the research world, stressing highly convincing aspects of these forms of enterprise. The main mover of Euricse's studies is represented by the contradiction between the results achieved by such entities, particularly during the recent economic and financial crisis, thanks to its resilience, and the predominant theoretical paradigm (in the form of its political translation), which keeps on shaping social and economic strategies that substantially nullify these evidences. As a consequence, the Institute aims to boost knowledge development and innovation for the field of cooperatives, social enterprises and non-profit organizations. Furthermore, it acts in order to deepen the understanding of these particular entities going beyond national specificities and to support them to work efficaciously towards the maximisation⁴⁷ of their impact on economic development and in terms of social innovation at the same time.

Research on social innovation seems to emerge, following Euricse's approach, from the consideration of a certain degree of overlap between social innovation and business innovation. However, in this

⁴⁶ http://www.euricse.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/1265989136_n3341.pdf

⁴⁷ Concerning the economic value deriving from the attention paid to society and sustainability as a whole, learn more about the concept of “new humanism” discussed by G. Vecchiato in *Benecomune, Verso un capitalismo solidale?*, (September 2010) - as well as *Benecomune, Come fare impresa per creare valore condiviso*, (May 2011).

case, the context-related method exhorts social innovation policy to focus on the subset of social innovation which does *not* overlap with business innovation (Borzaga & Bodini, 2012). The reason is that social innovations overlapping with business innovations tend to be profitable, while pure social innovations are not driven by a profit motive (ibid., p. 2), and thus need either to be subsidized or to be developed by enterprise types that are not motivated by profit maximization. Indeed, by focusing on the characteristics of different enterprise types, it has been found that not-for-profit enterprises with an explicit social mission are ideally suited to develop pure social innovation, even in the absence of public sector intervention.

Both Euricse and Iris network seem to have a number of hot topics on the agenda. These range from the analysis of bottom up dynamics resulting from the self-organization of (“artificial”) communities that manage to elaborate and test new solutions to systemic problems (environment, migration, etc.) against the failure of traditional institutions: state, market and traditional social economy; to the regeneration of buildings and public spaces as commons to manage various activities of “general Interest”; new emerging models of community based social enterprises; as well as models and measures of social impact (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

As far as **CIRIEC**’s main research field is concerned, it is focused on the general and collective interest both within the public economy and within the social and cooperative economy sectors. This research approach⁴⁸ results being quite varied and policy-oriented, and aims at providing integrated concepts and definitions. It shows the multiple intersections between economies and public, social and cooperative actions (including mixed systems). Moreover, it reflects and analyses specific topics such as, precisely, societal development and changes, also in terms of social innovation, as well as the efficiency of socio-economic architectures and processes. This research approach also takes into account the development of relations between a variety of stakeholders (e.g. the transformation in the role of the state; economic and democratic cooperation instead of competition, etc.) and topics related to employment, social exclusion, new social needs and new modes of delivering such services.

CIRIEC’s research can be considered tripartite: the first field, initiated in 1997 on occasion of the 50th anniversary of the CIRIEC, comprises cross-cutting studies covering public, social and cooperative economies. One can identify several trends within this first domain - in particular topics concerning the plural economy, thus the cooperation between the private, public and social economy sectors, but also the governance systems at the basis of social services of general interest. The second field concerns the public economy and the provision of services of general economic interest, but also the supply of social and health services (as well as any other services called “public”) by social economy organizations. The third domain concentrate itself on social and cooperative economy.

⁴⁸ Further information at *La recherche au CIRIEC* (2015), Centre International de Recherches et d’Information sur l’Economie Publique, Sociale et Coopérative, CIRIEC aisbl.

CIRIEC has a long tradition of reflection and analysis on the social economy sector as a whole which began with some pioneering studies focused on the understanding and promotion of this concept and its components (cooperatives, mutual societies, non-profit organizations, foundations), stressing one or the other aspect of the social economy field. Indeed, to cite only a very recent initiative, the 31st CIRIEC Congress (Reims, 21-23 September 2016) entitled “*Public policies and social and democratic issues of globalisation: what projects to be developed by the public, social and cooperative economy?*” has been an occasion to participate in a number of ateliers precisely focusing on the dynamics between social and solidarity economy and social innovation as a means towards the reduction of inequalities.

The hot topics currently emerging in CIRIEC's research area concern mainly the processes of interaction and co-construction between social and solidarity economy and territories; the analysis of the specific governance and organization models of social economy enterprises; the hybrid transformation of social economy enterprises whether into isomorphic or innovative entities; the elaboration of methods and indicators to assess the weight and added value of social and solidarity economy; the scrutiny on the reciprocal influence between public policies and social and solidarity economy; the weight of social economy networks in addressing global challenges; a new legal framework on social and solidarity economy (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

7.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

The research methods and roles within the designated social economy community are quite variegated and generally comprise both theoretical reflections and empirical analysis, thus contributing to an improvement in the understanding, also from a quantitative point of view, of the link between the social economy sector and the social innovation, rather than only collecting the already existing literature on the subject.

For a more complete framework, it seems also important to stress the crucial role played by practitioners in such research community. In fact, their contribution facilitates the generation of a specific knowledge having the power to challenge those traditional theoretical approaches that are normally applied to the understanding of economy and society (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

The **EMES** network certainly benefits from its both quantitatively and geographically vast experience and expertise in the third sector and social enterprises' domains. Indeed, since its inception in 1996, its individual and institutional members emerge from those having a high reputation in the sector, holding a leading role among a huge landscape of research centres and scholars. Mostly centered on Europe, EMES since then has primarily focused its research activity on five specific area: personal and social services, social enterprise, third sector, work integration, social innovation.

The EMES approach to research is characterized by a synergy among several disciplines from the human sciences and the combination of both theoretical and empirical methods, thus including the identification and management of indicators, suited to various specific cases/projects.

The network publishes the results of its research projects in the form of books, conference papers, member's publications and working papers – all downloadable free of charge to ensure their dissemination to the largest international audience. A major contribution of recent publication is the co-produced social innovation research agenda *Co-SIRA* (Brandesen et al., 2016), developed since 2014 by the EMES network and other stakeholders in the framework of the Social Innovation Europe project. A number of relevant topics have been selected by a core group of scholars on the basis of a series of hot topics having emerged during several international conferences, in order to overcome research repetitions and to effectively address a number of gaps by collecting and reviewing approaches typical in social innovation research field. Moreover, the coordinators of a dozen European projects on the topic of social innovation provided some inputs on research approaches, methods and open questions through online surveys and a discussion group launched via a social network. Finally, an expert group provided the final feedback.

The investigations carried out by **Iris Network** *come from*, and at the same time *feed*, the exchange of information between research centres, universities and individual researchers, but also between them and the social entrepreneurship world towards an “activated knowledge”⁴⁹. Iris conducts both empirical investigations and theoretical reflections. In this sense, in recent years the Italian network has built up a vast corpus of empirical papers, comments and best practices, mostly produced in the *Colloquio scientifico* and *Workshop on social enterprises*⁵⁰ contexts. The first consists in a scientific conference organized once per year in order to promote scientific analysis and reflections concerning innovative elements characterizing the current phase of development of social enterprises on the national scene. The event aims to deepen the knowledge of the social enterprises' features, using a context-related approach. The starting point consists in the analysis of the markets' characteristics and evolution, proceeding with the evaluation of a series of elements favouring the development of such enterprises: management, governance, policies. On the other hand, the *Workshop on social enterprise* is an occasion for these organisations to exchange sectoral best practices. With its plenary sessions, thematic workshops, tens of innovative good practices and speakers, and hundreds of entrepreneurs, the *Workshop on social enterprise* is the largest community on social enterprises' innovation in Italy. The meeting is mostly focused on bringing out Italian social enterprises' best experiences in terms of social innovation, with the aim to encourage fruitful exchanges between workers and other public and private actors wishing to support the development of this particular ecosystem.

⁴⁹ Thus development-oriented. See also <http://irisnetwork.it/rete/>

⁵⁰ The *Workshop on social enterprise* is a key event for organisations producing socially useful goods and services in various fields, in order to pursue objectives of public interest through the exchange of sectoral best practices.

Research is only one of **Euricse's** activities⁵¹. Concerning this field, Euricse conducts and supports theoretical and empirical research projects characterized by an interdisciplinary and comparative nature. Euricse cultivates an approach that fosters dialogue between different stakeholders, in particular researchers and practitioners, boosting their active participation. The activities are conducted including primarily theoretical and applied research and training, addressing issues of national, European and international interest to this sector, favouring openness and collaboration. The dissemination of researches and findings is carried out through publications, presentations, conferences and seminars oriented both to researchers and the general public.

Euricse focuses on all forms of private organizations and enterprises that pursue purposes other than profit, are characterized by participatory management models, and adopt a development approach that blends social and economic well-being. The Institute combines a variety of activities related to research in order not only to develop knowledge on this kind of enterprises, but also to create and promote ownership, governance and management models uniquely tailored to their characteristics. The peculiarity of this method consists in the inversion of the research strategy, in comparison to other centres analysing the same topics. Indeed, the Institute carries out its investigations prioritizing the development of new models and theories, based on the principles and values specifically featuring the organisations that represent the object of its study, hence cooperatives and social enterprises, rather than using theoretical and empirical tools developed for other purposes. The goal consists in the identification of the conditions which ensure – or inhibit – the emergence and the long term sustainability of the abovementioned entities, in order to promote their development (including the creation of new forms of social enterprise) and innovative impact. Euricse is committed to the practical application of the knowledge developed through its research. Its activity and scientific production aim to reduce the fragmentation in the research on cooperative and social enterprises, and to boost the visibility of this sector in the scientific and political debate.

The cross-sectoral and cross-disciplinary nature is particularly relevant also in **CIRIEC's** approach to research⁵². Its activity contributes both to a better understanding of the fields of study covered (mainly concerning the public, cooperative and social economy sectors) and to enable the exchange of ideas and knowledge to generate a common conceptual understanding. Indeed, the Institute's activities aim in the long run to encourage the epistemological progress of the general interest characterizing the public, as well as the social economy sector. In any case, CIRIEC recognizes a crucial importance to the fact of addressing phenomena and themes linked to these sectors from a perspective of complexity. In this sense, it seems relevant to document the mechanisms at the basis of the systems promoting social innovation and its structuring effects in terms of social transformation, while at the same time focusing

⁵¹ The Institute is also engaged in trainings, consulting and communication.

⁵² See also *Research within CIRIEC*, CIRIEC aisbl, Université de Liège http://www.ciriec.ulg.ac.be/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/rechercheEN_dec2015.pdf

on these systems from a multi-level approach, taking into account social relationships, collective actors, organizational and institutional dimensions (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

Two main types of investigation can be identified, featured by scientific rigor as much as by social relevance: the first type of investigation consists in a spontaneous internal research on topics chosen by the members of the international scientific bodies of the organization; the second type includes sponsored researches, for third parties, in response to calls for tender (including the EU institutions' requests for proposals).

CIRIEC's research is carried out by scientists and experts from various disciplines, sectors and countries. Indeed, the members of this multidisciplinary team come from both the international scientific bodies and the national sections. The periodic organization of meetings allows extensive discussions between scholars and experts from different cultures and backgrounds (economics, political science, history, sociology, management, etc.), each contributing with his/her knowledge and experiences to the improvement of the subject. Therefore, it seems pertinent to outline the variety of this research approach: the Institute carries out a research methodology which pays attention to the integrated and comparative definition of concepts as much as to the analytical reflection on selected themes, namely through quantitative assessments and evaluations.

7.5 IMPACT

In recent years, there has been an increase in the attention paid to entities contributing to develop an alternative economic system. Mostly because of the economic and financial crisis, both researchers and policy makers became more and more interested in the motivations, behaviours, principles (such as solidarity, reciprocity and direct participation in management), policies and governance mechanisms setting up and fostering the environment of these kind of organizations, which are quite different from the mainstream businesses. The features underpinning social economy organisations make their social role, in a variety of sectors and countries, commensurable – in terms of priority – to their economic performance. They often achieve economic and social outcomes that are better than those achieved by traditional enterprises and public institutions (Borzaga, 2009), also thanks to the degree of innovation characterising the social, educational, health and general interest goods and services they produce.

From a general perspective, the investigations conducted by the social economy research community, confirm the abovementioned tendency. The analyses are focused both on the contexts favouring or impeding the emergence of such alternatives, and on their performance, in terms of outcomes, good practices, social innovations, impact. Nevertheless, while the qualitative analysis' *corpus* appears quite rich, far fewer documents came to corroborate the framework from a quantitative perspective. Hence, besides the too descriptive nature of much of the research conducted on these topics, another weak-

ness contributing to the underestimation of the social economy sector's results consists in the still existing fragmentation within the research *aquis*, often limited to specific sectors or geographic areas.

As previously mentioned, since its creation in 1996, **EMES** has completed eight major research projects within its focus area (including the one more related to the link between the social economy sector and social innovation). During the years, the network has had a major impact and influence in the field of the Third sector and social enterprises. Today it benefits from the accumulated experience, expertise and reputation of all its members who are among the leading research centres and individual researchers in the field. One of the main results recently achieved consists in the publication, in July 2016, of the *Social innovation Research Agenda for Europe* (Brandsen et al., 2016), a deliverable co-produced in the framework of the Social Innovation Europe project⁵³.

As for **Iris**, the network has recently published a synthesis of 380 scientific papers taking the form of an infographic⁵⁴ showing the impact of its research activity within a taxonomy of themes linked to the social economy sector, including a generic "innovation". The idea emerged in the occasion of the 10th edition of the *Scientific Colloquium on social enterprise*, when Iris decided to reread and reclassify its papers, not only for an impact measurement need, but also to be able to focus on occurred shifts in regulation, policies and cultures underling the analysed subject. If on the one hand, the research appears quite advanced regarding the formal dimension and the management of the investigated thematic, a lot still needs to be done concerning the procedural nature and the policies linked to social enterprises. Similarly, there is still a gap between the insiders' needs and the state of art on the (social) innovation subject, despite a new tendency towards the convergence.

Probably the hugest activity in which **Euricse** is engaged, together with the International Co-operative Alliance (ICA), consists in an on-going project aiming to collect and integrate information about economic and financial situation, employment and membership base of more than 2000 cooperatives (with reference to the period 2010-2012) operating in different countries, in Europe and in the whole world. A key principle for the construction of this scientific database has been the attention paid to data quality. The database⁵⁵ will be made up of data collected from different administrative and statistical sources, in order to allow an in-depth analysis of the same figure as well as a clearer comparison between cooperatives and the for-profit sector. It seems also important to notice that the Institute's activities are organised at two levels: in fact, besides the European and global focus, Euricse has also been working intensely, since 2010, on the gathering and organization of statistical information about Italian cooperative enterprises. In Italy, it represents the first experience of this kind.

⁵³ For more information about the subject, please refer to the third section of this report, "Methods and role of research".

⁵⁴ Downloadable at: <http://irisnetwork.it/2016/06/impatto-ricerca-infografica-iris-network-colloquio-2016/>

⁵⁵ <http://www.euricse.eu/projects/banca-dati-sulla-cooperazione-a-livello-europeo-e-mondiale/>

Two peculiarities of the **CIRIEC** approach to research in the field of social economy and social innovation consist in its wide scope and policy-orientation. It is characterized by a tendency to integrate definitions and concepts delineated within the field, as well as by a geographical and sectoral comparative overview. The benefits deriving from being part of an integrated social innovation research community consist precisely in a more rapid dissemination of new research developments, as well as in the identification and consideration of different currents and paradigms of research in this field (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

The deep and global reflection on structural variables (technology, institutions, socio-economic system, legal and political framework) shaping a prosperous environment for the social economy sector as a whole and its entities, has made the CIRIEC a pioneer of the understanding and promotion of the social and cooperative economy concepts as well as one of the few *loci* worldwide to intellectually grasp all the economic issues related to collective and general interest. Hereby the network soundly contributes to the recognition and promotion of this sector of the economy.

Beyond the aforementioned networks, research on social economy and social innovation was and is shaped also by other academics and institutes/universities. Important contributions have been, for instance, the works of Marguerite Mendell from the Karl Polanyi Institute in Montreal on the Social and Solidarity economy with a particular focus on the *social economy and economic democracy, social finance and their contribution to local development*. A broad range of topics related to the *social economy, including links with broader civil society movements*, have been addressed by the International Society for Third Sector Research. *Social economy in the context of social service provision and civil economy* have been among the focus themes of Pier Luigi Sacco from IULM university, Milano. Other researchers such as Bruno Roelants (CECOP/CICOPA) or Gianfranco Marocchi (Social Change School Rome/London/Madrid) highlighted the *contribution specifically of social cooperatives to local development and social innovation*. Trebor Scholz from The New School/New York can be considered a leader regarding recent international research focusing on the link between the *digital economy and the potential of 'cooperative'⁵⁶ platforms*. These examples show once again the diversity of fields and research areas linked to the concept "social economy". Coupled with a sometimes fairly different historical, cultural and legal context from country to country and the hybrid forms of the emerging 'new economy', this diversity presents for the researcher at the same time source of inspiration, but also a real challenge when it comes to finding common terms and definitions.

⁵⁶ The term "cooperative" is used here in its wider meaning, the focus is not on a specific legal-form.

7.6 CONCLUSIONS

The present work shows that, even if in its early stages, the research addressing social innovation and its relationship with social economy represents a more and more vivid field of activity for a number of leading research centres and scholars at national, European and international level.

The four networks designated to represent the Social economy research community (EMES, Iris, Euricse and CIRIEC) embody, each of them with certain peculiarities, a variety of pioneering perspectives on social economy and its entities, which show them as vectors toward innovative models and strategies to tackle new and longstanding social problems and needs. Their work has, over the two last decades, soundly contributed to the theoretical and empirical progress of the social economy sector, boosting its visibility and the recognition of the importance, at various levels, of the urgent need for a socio-economical paradigm shift.

Nevertheless, much still needs to be done in order to corroborate this evidence with the strength that only data and empirical proofs can offer. In fact, a sounder use, control and systematization of statistics and comparative databases adapted to assess the impact of the social and solidarity economy could certainly offer a fuller and impactful orientation for policy makers. With this aim, also a deeper integration of evidences and results will be crucial to overcome the still existing sectoral and geographical fragmentation of the subject (e.g. including data in a joint case study database) as well as to show the added value of social economy in terms of social innovation.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

8 Sharing and Collaborative Economy

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8.1 INTRODUCTION

The rise of the sharing and collaborative economy is related to the financial crisis of 2008 and ensuing austerity measures, the enabling character of ICT developments – specifically Web 2.0 and a growing longing for social connectedness (Barnes & Mattsson, 2016; Cohen & Kietzmann, 2014; Schor, 2014). Especially in its beginnings, participants were motivated by its claim to provide economic (lower prices), social (more social contacts) and environmental (less resource use) benefits (Schor, 2014). With time, critiques were surging pointing to the perversities of certain forms of the sharing and collaborative economy, such as labour exploitation, exclusion, discrimination and rebound effects (Frenken & Schor, 2017; Nadeem et al., 2015).

This chapter maps the research landscape with regard to the 'Sharing and Collaborative Economy' – abbreviated in the following as SE/CE. In a first section, it outlines the contours of the research area, including its thematic scope, actors and geographical spread. The second section focuses on the actual research about the SE/CE along a number of issues, such as geography, subject areas, sectors, and its relation to social innovation. The main part focuses on the current and emerging research topics. The third section zooms in on the role of research in the SE/CE and the methods and theoretical frameworks used. The chapter ends with a short note on the impact and an outlook.

Methodology

For mapping the research landscape of the SE/CE, we used three main strategies: 1) a SCOPUS search for the most relevant articles of the last ten years, 2) results of an online survey answered by four experts in the field, and 3) a search for relevant grey literature.

Documents by year

Figure 1: Total number of documents for the SCOPUS search by year (Source: Scopus). *Note that our search ended mid-August 2016, the total number of publications in 2016 was 94

A SCOPUS search for publications as of 2007 to mid-August 2016 with the keywords: 'sharing economy', 'collaborative economy', 'collaborative consumption' and 'peer to peer economy' was performed. This search resulted in 115 articles, out of which 101 were relevant for the purposes here and had abstracts. These were sorted by relevance and the first 51 abstracts were analysed with regard to the following: year of publication, geographical focus, research topic, research aims, theories used, methodology used, empirical examples, sector and actors. The resulting mapping was complemented by the insights developed through reading seven overview articles in depth (Belk, 2014a; Belk, 2014b; Cheng, 2016; Dredge & Gyimothy, 2015; Frenken & Schor, 2017; Puschmann & Alt, 2016; Schor, 2014).

As the SE/CE is a very recent object of research, which has seen a steep increase in journal publications as of 2014 (see Figure 1), additional sources were necessary. A first source of insights were survey responses by four experts in the field of SE/CE (referred to anonymously as Respondent 1-4). They have answered questions with regards to research on social innovation and on the sharing and collaborative economy, including emerging hot topics, knowledge gaps and the role of researchers. Last, we used input from searching for and analysing grey literature, websites, blogs and workshop reports as the SE/CE.

8.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

This chapter focuses on the research area of the sharing and collaborative economy (SE/CE) and starts with the question of what the SE/CE actually is. There is to date not one solid definition of the SE/CE—rather as is common with emerging phenomena, there are **different attempts to solidify such a defi-**

inition and to structure practices and debates (e.g. Botsman, 2013; Schor, 2014; Frenken & Schor, 2017, Stokes et al., 2014). As put by Nadeem et al. (2015): *“The truth of the matter is that the sharing economy is a floating signifier for a diverse range of activities. Some are genuinely collaborative and communal, while others are hotly competitive and profit-driven. A good many others are suspended somewhere in between”*.

In an attempt to break down and define the most commonly used terms, Botsman (2013) seems to consider the collaborative economy as the overall broad umbrella, namely as *“an economy built on distributed networks of connected individuals and communities versus centralized institutions, transforming how we can produce, consume, finance and learn”*. Nested in this is collaborative consumption as *“an economic model based on sharing, swapping, trading, or renting products and services, enabling access over ownership”* (ibid.). Again nested therein seems to reside the Sharing Economy as *“an economic model based on sharing underutilized assets from spaces to skills to stuff for monetary or non-monetary benefits”* (ibid.).

Juxtaposed to this, Barnes and Mattsson (2016, p. 200) consider, collaborative consumption as *“embedded within the “sharing economy,” which involves access-based consumption of products or services that can be online or offline”*. According to these authors, collaborative consumption is *“the use of online marketplaces and social networking technologies to facilitate peer-to-peer sharing of resources (such as space, money, goods, skills and services) between individuals, who may be both suppliers and consumers”* (Barnes & Mattsson, 2016, p. 200). – Thus being much closer to Botsman’s definition of the sharing economy. Others reject the broad definition of Botsman and consider collaborative consumption to be *“people coordinating the acquisition and distribution of a resource for a fee or other compensation”* (Belk, 2014a, p. 1597).

Closely related to Belk’s definition of collaborative consumption, Frenken & Schor (2017, p. 2-3) define the sharing economy as: *“Consumers granting each other temporary access to under-utilized physical assets (“idle capacity”), possibly for money”*. This definition makes it possible to delineate the sharing economy from related platform economies, such as the on-demand economy (which is not about idle capacity), the second-hand economy (which is not about temporary access) and the product-service economy (which is not about other consumers offering a service or good).

In an earlier attempt to structure the debate, Schor (2014) distinguished between four broad categories of sharing economy activities, namely 1) recirculation of goods, 2) increased utilization of durable assets (such as a spare room or household goods), 3) exchange of services (originating in time bank), and 4) sharing of productive assets or space enabling production (a historical form are cooperatives). The platforms active in any of the four categories can be distinguished by their market orientation (for-profit vs. non-profit) and their market structure (peer-to-peer vs. business-to-peer) (Schor, 2014) but also by offering their activities offline or online.

What these definitions touch upon is a differentiation between:

- Utilization and access vs. ownership
- Idle capacity vs. on-demand services
- Market orientation – for profit vs. non-profit
- Market structure – peer-to-peer vs business-to-peer vs government-to-peer
- Role of the internet – offline vs online

For this chapter, we have not opted for a guiding definition, but rather have relied on the attribution done by others; e.g. we have searched for articles using the keyword sharing economy, collaborative economy, collaborative consumption and peer-to-peer economy. We find SE/CE initiatives in **different sectors**. PwC (2016) in their recent analysis of the SE have focussed on the following ones: accommodation, transportation, household services, professional services and finance. Puschmann & Alt (2016, p. 94) show SE/CE business models in food, finance, mobility, logistics, work, education and others.

There is **not one network or community representing the SE/CE** – rather there are a number of actors active with regard to this topic. Important network-like actors are OuiShare, an organization fostering the establishment of a collaborative society by connecting people, organizations and ideas around fairness, openness, and trust. It is active in research, community organization, professional services, and education. Another one is NESTA, an independent UK-based charity, who is active through practical programmes, policy and research, partnerships in a variety of sectors and investment. Also collaborativeeconomy.org is a network bringing together initiatives mainly based in the Netherlands. An overview of numerous institutions active in the SE/CE is provided in a table in Appendix A. It is by no means exhaustive but provides insights with regards to the diversity of kind of actors (market, public or third sector), the services they provide, when and where they were founded and their geographical coverage. There is a great variety when it comes to the type of activities undertaken by the different initiatives. From the most known housing/tourism initiatives, like AirBnB, Bla Bla Car, or investment platforms, like Kickstarter, to the exchange of tools and knowledge sharing, DIY initiatives for manufacturing or 3D printing; from time banks and news exchange platforms, to initiatives focusing on education, and sustainable living and all the way to food exchange between neighbours, SE/CE initiatives and networks have an abundance of products and/or services to offer.

The majority of SE/CE initiatives originate in the US, and more specifically, a significant number of the most successful networks can be traced back to San Francisco. These initiatives have expanded their operation to principally Europe, but also go beyond, reaching to Australia, Canada, and numerous countries in Asia, Latin America and Africa. Europe seems to be catching up as regards the networks emerging and people's participation in them (Bright, 2015; Schor, 2014). For instance, the toolsharing platform Peerby operates in the Netherlands, while the homesharing platform Guest to Guest, expanded its operation from France to Italy, Spain, UK, and Australia. Other initiatives like Behomm (a housing exchange community for creatives and design lovers) from Barcelona, Spain, or Streetbank from the UK (DIY initiative with the ambition to boost local communities by encouraging people to get to know

their neighbours by lending and sharing any kind of household items), have expanded their operation globally. Numerous SE/CE initiatives that started in Asia also spread globally. An example is *Tujia*, a house sharing network, which emerged in China in 2011, or *9flats* network, a peer-to-peer online property rental company for private accommodations, which started in Singapore and is currently active in 104 countries.

8.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

This section focuses on mapping the research about the sharing and collaborative economy (SE/CE) – describing the sectors covered, the geographical location of the research, the use of the concept of social innovation before it dives into delineating the main research topics of the SE/CE research.

Sectors and geography of SE/CE research

There are two main **sectors** standing out in research about the SE/CE. On the one hand, there is ‘Tourism & Hospitality’ closely related to ‘Housing & Accommodation’ – with a prominent case being AirBnB. On the other hand, there is ‘Mobility & Transportation’ with a prominent case being Uber. The main cross-sector collaboration concerns the crossover of ICT with traditional sectors, such as the ones mentioned above: this facilitation is considered a defining or at least facilitating factor for the current sharing practices (Belk, 2010; 2014a/b; Frenken & Schor, 2017; Schor, 2014).

Geographically, the main body of research is done in the United States, followed by the UK, Austria and Germany as top three in Europe (see Table 2). This corresponds also with findings by Cheng, who states “*To date, sharing economy research has been conducted from a Western perspective and in Western regions. Less attention has been paid to emerging regions, which concurrently enjoy rapid growth of SE in their own regions and present their unique group dynamics (Tolkach et al., 2015)*” (Cheng, 2016, p. 67).

Documents by country/territory

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories

Figure 2: The top countries represented in search results by number of documents (Source: Scopus)

The overwhelming majority of the research articles treats/studies the concept as a global phenomenon, without linking it to a specific geographical context. For example, Belk (2014a) compares sharing and collaborative consumption as universal phenomena born in the internet age. However, there are exceptions, such as articles focusing on specific cities or building on cases from different continents. For instance, McNeill (2016) focuses on the urban policy tensions associated with the evolution of new SE firms in the city of San Francisco, which have aggressively challenged the municipal regulations as regards the taxi and property rental fields. Tussyadiah & Pesonen (2016) alternatively explore the market characteristics and the factors that drive and hinder the use of P2P accommodation building on responses from travellers residing in the United States and Finland. Yet, NESTA (2015b) suggests that a majority of studies focuses on cities or the urban (e.g. 'sharing cities' or urban neighbourhoods), this is not (yet) reflected in the published articles we reviewed. A focus on cities is considered promising "due to high density of population with relatively high levels of income, which leads to abundant pools of underutilised assets, and due to the rapidly developing ICT sector, which increases connectivity between the users of sharing platforms" (Lund University, 2016).

Social innovation in SE/CE research

Our analysis suggests that scholars involved in the wide field of SE/CE research do not relate to the concept of social innovation explicitly. From the 50 reviewed abstracts, only four (Manzo & Ramella, 2015; Martin et al., 2015; Martin & Upham, 2016; Martin, 2016) are explicitly using the term social innovation, either as a title or as a keyword.

Of these Martin (and co-authors) use the term "grassroots social innovations", referring back to the definition of Seyfang and Smith (2007) (Martin et al., 2015; Martin & Upham, 2016; Martin, 2016). As

such, the authors take a normative approach since they associate social innovation with “*networks of activists and organisations generating novel bottom–up solutions for sustainable development; solutions that respond to the local situation and the interests and values of the communities involved*” (Seyfang & Smith, 2007, p. 585 – emphasis added). Yet, when discussing the way SE is framed within the online SE discourse, the scholar finds a variety of contradictory framings “*ranging from a potential pathway to sustainability, to a nightmarish form of neoliberalism*” (Martin, 2016, p.149)

When it comes to the openness and inclusivity of the concept, the scholars note that grassroots innovation in the context of the SE extends beyond digital innovations, in order to include “*citizen driven social innovations... including, for example: cohousing, cooperative organisations, community currencies and local food provision*” (Martin, 2016, p. 154; Martin et al, 2015). Pointing to the fact that social innovation is a broader, more inclusive term.

Being asked for the contribution of the SE/CE to the development of social innovations in practice, Respondent 2 (2017) outlines that the CE can be considered as a framework comparable to social innovation, however using different means to reach similar ends: “*The collaborative economy can be understood as a framework, which sits side by side with social innovation, but that is focussed on achieving that through other means – with a particular focus on more economic and technological innovations that take social innovation into consideration, rather than inherently aim at social innovation. However, the social consequences of, and interactions within, the collaborative economy are not often considered in enough detail and with enough critical perspective, which weakens the practical realisations of the collaborative economy.*” She continues outlining that SE/CE can relate social innovation to market logics: “*On the other hand, the collaborative economy is a way in which social innovation can be brought much closer to its economic, productive and civic partners – thus a way in which the social innovation community can realise that those spheres are important areas of social action.*”

Current and emerging research topics incl. knowledge gaps

With increasing publications on the SE/CE, there are also a number of overview articles appearing attempting to structure and cluster the SE/CE as such (Belk, 2014a, Botsman, 2013; John, 2013; Schor, 2014; Frenken & Schor, 2017) and others attempting to structure the research about SE/CE. Exemplary for the latter, Cheng (2016) provides an overview of academic publications on the SE between 2010 and 2015 and used content analysis to distinguish between three broad research foci. These include 1) SE’s business models and its impacts, 2) Nature of SE relates to understanding sharing as an alternative consumption practice, and finally 3) SE’s sustainability development focusing on the relation between SE and sustainability.

Based on the abstract analysis, we cluster the research about the SE/CE in four areas, namely 1) aspects of framing, 2) individual aspects, 3) organisational and governance aspects and 4) contextual analysis. These clusters are not meant to be mutually exclusive, rather and necessarily they overlap

and some of these overlaps are discussed. In the following, we outline these four clusters, highlighting current and emerging research topics as well as knowledge gaps. As the research area is relatively new, current and emerging research topics overlap.

Framing

Not surprisingly for such an emerging research area, a large number of the articles engages in its framing delineating the topic, discussing and reconceptualising basic concepts or positioning the SE/CE against similar concepts.

Delineating the SE/CE. There are continuous efforts to define and frame the SE/CE or provide typologies thereof – see also section I (incl. Belk, 2014a, Botsman, 2013; John, 2013; Schor, 2014; Frenken & Schor, 2017; Dredge & Gyimothy, 2015). Dredge & Gyimothy (2015, p. 7), using a genealogic approach, reveal 17 terms, which “*often frame the sharing economy as a hybrid, digitally facilitated, alternative economic model embedded in (or rediscovering) deep-rooted cultural, moral and ecological rationales*”. A common denominator is that utilization and accessibility to goods and services are prioritized over ownership (cf. Schor & Fitzmaurice, 2015). Schor (2014) suggests that platforms active in the SE/CE can be distinguished by their market orientation (for-profit vs. non-profit) and their market structure (peer-to-peer vs. business-to-peer) but also by offering their activities offline or online. She distinguishes between four broad categories of sharing economy activities, namely 1) recirculation of goods, 2) increased utilization of durable assets, 3) exchange of services and 4) sharing of productive assets or space enabling production. Frenken & Schor (2017, p. 7) put a historical embedding of these activities up for further research: “*What types of sharing economies have historically existed across cultures and epochs, and what can we learn from the economics, governance and impacts of such initiatives and practices in the light of current day sharing economy platforms?*”

Basic concepts of the SE/CE are re-conceptualised and discussed. This includes the actual concept of ‘sharing’ (Belk, 2014b; John, 2013; Kennedy, 2016). An authoritative voice in this regard is the anthropologist Belk (2014b), who distinguishes sharing (such as intentional online sharing of ephemera, online-facilitated offline sharing, peer-to-peer online sharing and online facilitated hospitality) from pseudo-sharing practices (such as long-term renting and leasing, online-facilitated barter economies, short-term rental and online sites ‘sharing’ your data). His distinction is based on the presence of profit motives in the latter activities. Respondent 1 (2017) considers the basic nature of sharing, its changes within kinship groups, neighbourhoods, and more broadly as emerging research topics. Other concepts include ‘nonownership’ (Ndubisi et al., 2016) reciprocity (Pais & Provasi, 2015), labour (Söderberg, 2016 – specifically the limits of labour process theory) but also concepts such as value, labour and capital. The latter three were discussed during the first Ouishare collaborative economy research workshop at ESCP in Paris, where “*value is being discussed with regards to trust, social capital, job creation, and the creation and measurement of non-monetary value. Issues on labour are being investigated in association to capital, and new forms of work such as co-working and distributed peer-to-peer collaboration.*”

Finally, a number of studies are investigating how the collaborative economy might redefine the notion of capital, particularly from a paradigm shift that focuses on abundance rather than scarcity.” (NESTA, 2015b).

SE/CE is positioned against other concepts. This positioning of course also includes definitional questions. Botsman (2013) positions the SE against the collaborative economy, collaborative consumption, and the peer economy – also outlining their commonalities, namely distributed power, disruptive drivers and innovative and efficient asset utilization. Frenken & Schor (2017) provide a definition and an analytical framework, which allows distinguishing the sharing economy from related forms of platform economies, such as the on-demand economy (which is not about idle capacity), the second-hand economy (which is about permanent rather than temporary access) and the product-service economy (which is about companies rather than other consumers offering a service or good). Other concepts against which the SE/CE is positioned include the concept of sustainability-rooted anticonsumption (Seegebarth et al., 2016), sustainable economic growth (Bonciu & Balgar, 2016), the fourth industrial revolution, which refers to “*ICT-based convergence industries*” (Chung and Kim, 2016), generalized exchange (Whitham & Clarke, 2016), or circular economy (Hobson & Lynch, 2016). Such positioning against and interplay with other concepts is also the focus of emerging research, including the interplay between the sharing economy and the circular economy (Respondent 4, 2017), between SE/CE and social entrepreneurship (Respondent 3, 2017), SE/CE as social innovation (Respondent 3, 2017) and a focus on commons and peer to peer, which exist beyond the collaborative economy but have become increasingly connected (Respondent 2, 2017). The SE/CE practices are also used to **develop other concepts further**, such as ‘evasive entrepreneurship’, which is a “*profit-driven business activity in the market aimed at circumventing the existing institutional framework by using innovations to exploit contradictions in that framework*” (Elert & Henrekson, 2016). Other examples are ‘info-liberalism’, a neologism “*to capture the affective motions of online sharing and its links to neoliberal capitalism*” (Banning, 2016) or ‘virtual-social-physical convergence’ (Fox, 2016) and ‘offer network’ (Heylighen, 2016). The latter is “*an architecture for a future economic system based on the matching of offers and demands without the intermediate of money*”.

There are numerous studies **detailing specific SE/CE activities as such**. These provide overviews of specific SE/CE services such as P-2-P rentals (Richard and Cleveland, 2016) or specific finance models, such as ‘loan-based crowdfunding’ (Roig Hernando, 2016), practices such as photo sharing (Lobinger, 2016) or actors, such as the sharing practices of religious organisations (Freni, 2015).

SE/CE in Context

A number of studies analyses the role of the wider context with which SE/CE initiatives are interacting. These are focusing on understanding the rise of the SE/CE in relation to context factors as well as on the impact of the SE/CE initiative on their context.

Factors for the current rise of SE/CE initiatives. Cheng (2016, p. 60) outlines the following: “*This rapid growth of SE (sharing economy) in the past decade is strongly related to social-economic conditions in pursuit of better value distribution of the supply chain (Gansky, 2010), reduction of ecological impacts (Schor & Fitzmaurice, 2015), technology advancement and ultimately users’ changing attitudes towards product ownership and the need for social connection (Botsman and Rogers, 2010)*”. Also Barns & Mattsson’ (2016) Delphi study focused on understanding the drivers and inhibitors of the development of collaborative consumption.

Specific markets within which organisations operate. A number of studies contextualises SE/CE initiatives in a specific market. (Teubner & Flath, 2015) analyses the structure and economics of electronic ride sharing markets and provide recommendations to platform operations enhancing their business opportunities. To increase our understanding of collaborative consumption in tourism and hospitality, Tussyadiah & Pesonen (2016) explore the market characteristics and factors that drive and hinder the use of P2P accommodation. Locating such markets in a specific geographical context, McNeill (2016) investigates how labour, housing and public transport markets of San Francisco have been reshaped by venture capital and technology.

Specificities of the sharing economy in various geographical, cultural and socio-political contexts are a related knowledge gap (Respondent 4, 2017; Frenken, 2016), including non-Western context (Cheng, 2016). Next to understanding the different versions of SE/CE in different contexts, another question is to understand why SE/CE initiatives are more successful in some contexts than others. An interesting study in this regard is, done by Manzo & Ramella (2015) aims to understand the surprising degree of FabLabs in Italy by understanding characteristics of this context, such as human capital surplus and deficit of collective goods. Thus the question to pose here is at which places SE/CE crystallizes and what the role of cities therein is (NESTA, 2015b; Respondent 4, 2017). Exploring the related question of the upscaling of an SE initiative (i.e. its expansion of customer base and/or move to new geographies), Grinevich et al. (2015) found that “*upscaling patterns of sharing economy businesses are only partially sector specific, and are not entirely attributable to particular type of sharing activity*”.

Regulation. The issue of regulation of the SE/CE – and its local, national or supra-national specificities – is considered an emerging hot topic (Respondent 2, 2017; Respondent 3, 2017; Frenken & Schor, 2017; Dredge & Gyimothy, 2015). First studies are done, for example Miller (2016) analyses existing regulations of the short term rental market and developing more appropriate regulatory responses through a “*markets-based mechanism, transferable sharing rights, which is better suited to internalize externalities in the short-term rental market*”. Examining the historical context in which agricultural labour regulations in California took shape as well as their uneven and under-enforcement, Sowerwine et al. (2015) highlight that these discriminate against Southeast Asia farms but also against other labour-sharing arrangements relying on volunteerism as in the sharing economy. More generally, a knowledge gap to date is a lack of understanding of the role of institutions in the sharing economy and how gov-

ernments can facilitate the institutionalisation of sharing economy initiatives (Respondent 4, 2017; Cheng, 2016).

Analysis and assessments of the impact of the SE/CE activities. The SE/CE has started off with a promising narrative regarding its positive social, economic and ecologic impacts. Participants are motivated by such economic (lower costs), social (more social contacts), and ecological (less resource intensive) promises (Schor, 2014). However, critiques have been uttered amongst others on the SE for exploiting labourers, providing poor labour conditions, evading regulations, and exclusion of groups. Analysing online sharing economy discourse, Martin (2016) shows the co-option of the SE discourse by dominant actors. He argues, “[a]lthough a critique of hyper-consumption was central to emergence of the sharing economy niche (2), it has been successfully reframed by regime actors as purely an economic opportunity (1)”. Rather than as development, Richardson (2015) suggests that the positioning of the SE as part of the capitalist economy *and* as an alternative happens simultaneously necessitating a focus on its performative aspects, thus on what it does rather than what it is, and therewith “*suspending it as a space for both opportunity and critique*”. In terms of **economic potential**, Fremstad (2016) aims to understand the current and potential value of sharing items across households, while Oses Fernandez et al. (2016) develop “*a method to monitor the alternative accommodation market based on data collected from Airbnb*”. The impact of SE/CE initiatives on incumbent businesses (and their response) (Respondent 4, 2017; Cheng, 2016) and on various sector regulations contexts (Cheng, 2016) are pertinent research questions. Others concern the benefits and detriments of the for-profit sharing economy (Eichhorst & Spermann, 2016; Respondent 1, 2017; Respondent 4, 2017). Such research should focus on **ecological impacts** (Schor, 2014) and more general sustainability impacts and potentials (Respondent 4, 2017). An initial assessment by Frenken & Schor (2017, p. 4) points to the fact that “*the alleged sustainability benefits of the sharing economy are, however, much more complex than initially assumed*” – amongst others taking account of direct and broader effects, externalities, ripple down and rebound effects. Evaluating environmental, economic and social impacts of SE/CE initiatives helps to identify which ones have the potential to contribute to sustainable development (Respondent 4, 2017; NESTA, 2015b). Next to environmental concerns, this also includes **social impacts** such as on inequality (Schor et al., 2016; Nadeem et al., 2015), issues of inclusion and a focus on minorities (NESTA, 2015b) and the sharing economy for the BoP (Respondent 3, 2017). To understand such impacts and potentials, there is a need for more standardised **measurement and evaluation** methods (Cheng, 2016). An important cue for the impact is pointed out by Respondent 2 (2017), who notes, that “*Much of the research, understandably, focuses on dynamics internal to platforms and collaborative initiatives, however, there is a shortage of theoretical work exploring the interconnections between all these disparate yet connected movements. How are we to understand these developments? What really is going on at a macro-level, and how is that expressed at meso and micro levels.*”

Organisational and governance aspects in the SE/CE

We also differentiated a third cluster of studies, focusing on the organisational and governance aspects of SE/CE initiatives. In his overview article, Cheng (2016, p. 67) considers this as a 'meso' level, which *"focuses largely on SE [sharing economy] firm's operating practices in addressing the ambiguous nature of encounters in SE"*.

Some studies aim to understand the **implications of business models for the broader context and vice versa**. Henten & Windekilde (2016) discuss business models of sharing platforms and the implications thereof for the industry structure, while Kopnina (2015) scrutinizes the potential of business-level solutions and production systems to support broader societal changes towards sustainability. Aiming to understand how the context may inspire business models, Pisano et al. (2015) analyses broader trends to develop a framework to inspire new business models. Martin et al. (2015) develops a conceptual model (looking at causes, processes and outcomes) of the dynamics of grassroots organisations becoming more commercially-oriented. More **internally oriented**, other studies suggest specific management principles for organisations apt for the sharing economy (Lichtenthaler, 2016) or examine the regulation of access to communities (Hartl et al., 2016).

In terms of **business models**, there are major differences regarding the question whether initiatives are operating according to a for-profit or non-profit logic, or whether they offer services or goods on a peer-to-peer or business-to-peer basis (Schor, 2014). There is also the difference whether start-ups or incumbents are driving these initiatives (Puschmann & Alt, 2016). Further research should address *"where tension points between models exist and how they are or are not resolved"* but also the *"relationship between rhetoric and practice – both on a micro and macro level – to uncover contradictions and areas where practitioners might be working against their stated positions"* (Respondent 2, 2017). The study into (new) business models including ownership and governance structures and models is just emerging (Respondent 3, 2017; Respondent 4, 2017; Cheng, 2016). It is closely related to the search for alternatives to 'for-profit' platforms (Frenken, 2016) and includes the platform cooperative movements and a general push for less hierarchical governance and more distributed and collective ownership (Respondent 2, 2017; Respondent 3, 2017). Exemplary, Como et al. (2016) investigate the potential interaction between the collaborative economy and cooperative companies. Another emerging research focus is on distributed autonomous organizations (DAOs) & corporations (DACs) (Respondent 1, 2017) and associated technological decentralisation in particular related to innovations in blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies (Respondent 1-3, 2017). Respondent 2 (2017) also points to the need for more work *"that explores ways in which narratives for alternative futures are developed, along what lines of cohesion and what lines of difference, to better make sense of where commonalities can be leveraged, and where differences are in need of being recognised"*.

Individuals and their role(s) in the SE/CE

There is some focus on the individuals and/or the role of individual actors in the SE/CE. Studies dive into the motives of individuals for internet-mediated sharing (Bucher et al., 2016) and the demographic make-up of CE participants (Stokes et al. 2014). Also factors for guest satisfaction have been researched (Tussyadiah, 2016). Others focus on digital representations, and for example, the role of trust as inferred from host pictures in deciding whether or not to make a booking on AirBnB (Ert et al., 2016) or personal profile descriptions and their relation with reputation (Pera et al., 2016). More generally, Gullstrand et al. (2016) investigate consumer attitudes towards alternative consumption models.

In his overview article, Cheng (2016) contents that there are also studies, which take a user-centric approach and investigate how users adopt SE/CE. Related to this cluster, a focus on user motivations in the sharing economy has been identified as an emerging topic (Respondent 4, 2017). Identified knowledge gaps include the following:

- Research investigating how SE negatively/positively transforms individuals (Cheng, 2016)
- Research into how SE redefines the roles of consumers and suppliers compared with those of the conventional market (Cheng, 2016)
- Insights into characteristics and behaviour of entrepreneurs (Cheng, 2016)
- Insights into how older generations are interacting with SE/CE (rather than the current focus on youth/millennials) (NESTA, 2015b)

8.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

The role of research in the SE/CE is not exclusively taken up by academics – on the contrary much of the early research has been done by SE/CE actors, such as Ouishare or NESTA. As put by Dredge and Gyimothy (2015, p. 6), “*there appears to be a significant body of ‘grey’ research that is generated by the protagonists of collaborative consumption, and there is little independent scholarly research on the topic*”. As shown in Figure 1, as of 2016 scholarly publications on the SE/CE increase significantly.

The phenomena of the SE/CE is approached by researchers from very different disciplinary backgrounds, which is reflected in a **wealth of different theoretical approaches**. Approaching the SE/CE from psychology, we find amongst others theory of planned behaviour or motivation theory being used by studies looking into the different motives behind internet-mediated sharing as well as their role in shaping attitudes towards sharing one's possessions in commercialized as well as non-commercialized settings (Bucher et al., 2016). On another note, Gullstrand et al. (2016) look into consumer attitudes towards alternative consumption models focusing on furniture and home products. From the social sciences, we find the use of practice theory, concepts from political economy as well as transition theory.

The aim is to analyse inequality within these types of economic arrangements (Schor et al., 2016), to investigate the role of technology and venture capital next to political strategies in urban development (McNeill, 2016) or to problematize the concept of sharing and its use in networked culture in relation to other social theories of exchange (Kennedy, 2016). From the field of organisational research, we find case studies used to elaborate limits of current labour process theory (Söderberg, 2016) or an investigation into the extent to which transaction cost theory can be used to explain changing industrial structures (Henten & Windekilde, 2016). It seems that especially organisational and business related research is looking into testing the limits of existing theories to understand the new SE/CE phenomena.

In his overview of the SE literature, Cheng (2016) identifies a number of research streams that provide the theoretical foundation for SE research, including:

- Lifestyle and Social Movement: Conceptualisation of lifestyle movement as a primary means to foster social change (e.g. Laamanen et al., 2015)
- Consumption Practice: Theoretical appraisal of alternative consumption practice (e.g. Bardhi & Eckhardt, 2012)
- Sharing Paradigm: Conceptualisation of sharing as a theoretical construct (e.g. Belk, 2014b)
- Trust: Trust as social and economic construct (e.g. Möhlmann, 2015)
- Innovation: Theory of social and disruptive innovation (e.g. Martin and Upham, 2015)

Cheng's co-citation analysis shows that streams 1, 2 and 3 are well connected, while streams 4 and 5 are isolated. He outlines "*current sharing economy literature is predominantly investigated from sociological perspectives in conceptualizing sharing (Belk, 2014) and advocating lifestyle and social movement towards moral economy (Molz, 2013) and mobility paradigm (Cohen and Kietzmann, 2014), economic perspectives in articulating its growth and impacts on consumption practices (Richardson, 2015) and framing social or disruptive innovation (Guttentag, 2015), social-technological transition perspective towards sustainability (Martin et al., 2015) and consumer behaviour perspectives, e.g. trust building, risk aversion (Santana and Parigi, 2015), and travel pattern (Tussyadiah and Pesonen, 2015)*" (Cheng, 2016, p. 68). However, in our research, we did not find much support for the 'predominant' use of e.g. a transitions perspective and Cheng, somewhat contradicting himself, contends that "*Despite the gradually changing focus (e.g. sustainability) and increasing engagement with different disciplinary perspectives (e.g. social-technological transition perspectives) beyond economics, scholarship in this field is immature compared with many other areas*" (Cheng, 2016, p. 68). He considers that there are opportunities for the field in tying together the different knowledge streams and in integrating "*other relevant theories, such as social presence theory, and multiple-level analysis through disciplinary, multi-disciplinary, interdisciplinary, trans-disciplinary and contextual field with SE research*" (Cheng, 2016, p. 68).

Research on SE/CE can be divided into **different subject areas**. As can be seen from Figure 3, the main subject areas are 'business, management and accounting' and the 'social sciences'.

However, the figure also indicates that one article can be part of more than one subject area. For example, Martin & Upham’s (2016) article on grassroots social innovation is considered part of the subject areas energy and environmental sciences. Some of these subject areas can in turn be associated with specific fields or disciplines (such as Social Sciences, or Psychology). Every discipline comes with its research perspective, including research questions and aims. Reporting from a workshop of researchers on the CE in 2015, NESTA (2015b) found that it is an “*incredibly interdisciplinary*” endeavour, “*blending expertise from domains such as economics and marketing, computer science, geography, cultural studies, sociology, philosophy, organisational studies, management, innovation, Internet law, and urbanism and planning*”.

Documents by subject area

Figure 3: The top 10 subject areas represented in search results (Source: Scopus)

Due to the wealth of disciplines by which the topic is studied, we also find a **wide variety of methods** being used – both quantitative and qualitative (as also outlined by Nesta, 2015b). Most of the papers include a literature review of some kind. The aim of the studies relying solely on literature reviews is to provide an overview of the field (e.g. Cheng, 2016) or to establish a conceptual framework (e.g. Frenken & Schor, 2017). Most often, literature reviews/overview establish the state of the art and are complemented by other research methods. There is no obvious pattern to be found, while there are numerous case studies (Söderberg, 2016; Ndubisi et al., 2016; Sowerwine et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2015), we also find (controlled) experiments (Ert et al., 2016), scenarios (Richard & Cleveland, 2016), or more specific methods such as exploratory factor analysis (Heo, 2016).

The empirical data is collected using a broad pallet of methods, including interviews (also Delphi), surveys, participant observation, archives and documents (primary and secondary documentation, online

and offline). For data analysis, we find co-citation analysis and content analysis (Cheng, 2016), or exploratory factor analyses (17).

Transdisciplinary methods were not mentioned in the analysed abstracts. Methods and approaches to study the SE/CE have been identified as emergent research topic (Respondent 4, 2017).

There are different **activities that researchers engage in regarding the SE/CE topic**. Based on the survey input by four experts and some grey literature, we suggest distinguishing the following:

1. Develop knowledge, concepts and critiques regarding the SE/CE
 - Develop theoretical insights and futuristic treatments. (Respondent 1, 2017)
 - Critically analyse the non-sharing aspects of the Sharing Economy (Respondent 1, 2017)
 - Provide critical perspectives on social consequences of the SE (Respondent 2, 2017)
 - Ensure independent, credible, and analytically sound research (NESTA, 2015a)
2. Develop material for practitioners
 - Develop communication material that targets practitioners, including practitioner handbooks, films, blogs, newspaper articles and other popular science publications (SIC expert survey, 2017).
3. Supervise students
 - Supervise MSc and PhD student projects in which the students collaborate directly with societal actors, and often help them address their problems and knowledge needs (Respondent 4, 2017)
4. Provide spaces for knowledge co-creation
 - Organise practitioner workshops and events with representatives from city councils, businesses, community groups and other societal actors, to facilitate knowledge co-creation and exchange (Respondent 4, 2017)
 - Create spaces (NESTA, 2015a)
5. Support SE/CE actors in their knowledge needs
 - Feed back the results of studies to companies they collaborate with (e.g. insights used as consumer research) (Respondent 3, 2017)
 - Engage and inform stakeholders, to adapt and inform business models (NESTA, 2015a)
 - Support growth and development of SE/CE organisations (NESTA, 2015a)
 - Support ad-hoc demands (NESTA, 2015a)
6. Evaluate impact
 - Demonstrate impact grounded in evidence (NESTA, 2015a)

In 2015, a workshop by NESTA focused on how research can support the collaborative economy to make meaningful impact. A number of opportunities were identified for improving collaboration between researchers and organisations in the collaborative economy, these are (NESTA, 2015a):

- *Meeting halfway - research and practice are not unrelated:* Recognising that the activities are interrelated; researchers should rethink the way they communicate their results and organisation should include research and evaluation throughout their processes.
- *Ways of working together:* Indicating different ways of collaboration such as in-house research, external research or advisory relationships as well as their dis/advantages.
- *Open and transparent data:* Making data publicly available can lead to greater insights on the impact of the SE/CE.
- *Research funding:* research funding models need to be more open and flexible allowing for longer-term engagement as well as responsive research outputs.
- *Sustaining cooperation:* Having spaces allowing for exchange between different researchers and practitioners.

Figure 5: Picture @ NESTA workshop 2015 (Source: NESTA, 2015b)

8.5 IMPACT

As outlined above, the Sharing and Collaborative Economy is a recent research area and the first impacts of this topic on the research landscape are starting to become visible.

Publications: The number of peer-reviewed academic publications related to the SE/CE grew exponentially during the last years. These publications are heterogeneous in terms of disciplines and subject areas.

Conferences: Next to showing impact in terms of peer-reviewed articles, we can also trace the first steps towards an institutionalisation of the research area through an increase in the number of conferences dedicated to the topic. In the meanwhile, the 4th International Workshop on the Sharing Economy is hosted by Lund University on 15-16 June 2017, following up on earlier editions in Utrecht (June 2016) and other places. When accepting the Chair of Innovation Studies at Utrecht University, Koen Frenken dedicated his inaugural speech to “New inequalities in the sharing economy” (Frenken, 2016).

Wider reach: The Sharing Economy does reach beyond the first movers. Also institutions such as the EU are becoming increasingly interested in the phenomenon, with the European Parliament requesting insights on social and economic impact as well as regulation of the collaborative economy. (Sundararajan, 2017).

However, for research about the impacts of the sharing economy to flourish, what is needed is access to the data held by the platforms, which are reluctant to share it (Frenken & Schor 2017).

8.6 CONCLUSIONS

While the research on the SE/CE is increasing and highly dynamic, the area as such is considered to stand at a crossroad. While it started with high ambitions regarding its possible positive effects on our societies including social, economic and environmental – these are threatened to be overtaken by high venture capitalism and by monopolized markets. With the enforcement of regulations proving difficult and SE/CE initiatives not sharing their data, an act paramount to understand the impact of the SE/CE, alternative platforms are being founded (Frenken & Schor, 2017). Those platforms are cooperative based or crowd-sourced – users retain the rights to their data and do not have to pay margins to a commercial platform operator (see also Johnson 2016). The cooperative model has potential as business model for the collaborative economy. Cooperatives Europe and the LAMA Development and Cooperation Agency are carrying out an exploratory study on sharing economy models and innovation in cooperative companies (Como et al., 2016).

Frenken & Schor (2017, p. 7) remain optimistic when they outline that, “*More generally, the initial fear that platforms may naturally grow into monopolies as has happened with search engine and social media platforms may turn out to be ill-founded*”. As sharing markets are local rather than global markets, a critical mass of consumers is within reach. As put by the call for papers for the 4th International Workshop on the Sharing Economy: “*The sharing economy is a global phenomenon and it seems to be here to stay*” (Lund University, 2016).

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

9 Community Led Innovation

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9.1 INTRODUCTION

Community-led social innovations are efforts led by groups of citizens arising from a common recognition of the problems to be addressed. Community innovators frequently face major challenges when trying to implement their solutions. Pathways to policy makers or through institutions are often not well trodden. Frequently people feel a lack of ability to negotiate the processes needed to take their solutions further. However community innovators are uniquely placed to help solve social problems. They have a level of contextual understanding and insight that is invaluable to social innovation.

Many of the social challenges that communities face are shared in common, and networks of community-led initiatives provide a compounded benefit. They foster a community-based solution but they also allow for community innovators to learn from others, to share knowledge and to look to others for solutions to the challenges that they face. This is a vital dimension to this area. From a research perspective we have found that there are gaps in our understanding about community-led innovation. Whilst many academics and research groups work on community engagement, movement building and collective action there is a degree to which the innovation aspects of this are under-developed. Work by some projects, such as SI-DRIVE, may have relevance to this field however they were frequently not designed to look at this issue and therefore insights into community-led innovation are incidental. Dedicated work on community-led innovation is increasingly being done however there is significant room for such research to develop further.

We also find that there is a need among those involved in community-led innovation to build stronger links between community innovators and other relevant actors such as public sector institutions social economy actors and social innovation intermediaries, this might include facilitating the sharing of the tools and methods that are used to drive our understanding of community-led Innovation. It is important to note that we conceive of community-led innovation as being distinct from community involvement in innovation. We would define community-led social innovation as specifically: *Innovation that is developed, set-up, run, or owned by the community for the benefit of the community.*

9.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

The field of community-led innovation is about grassroots networks: organisations that grow out of and are embedded within their community, and seek to tackle everyday challenges that they experience. If we break-down our definition of community-led innovation into its composite parts we can clarify what this networks aims to include. Firstly we need to understand what we mean by community. Work by identified factors including a "sense of place", "sharing common interests and perspectives" and "joint action" that brings people together or "social ties" such as family and friends. (MacQueen, 2001, p. 1931) MacQueen defines community as:

"A group of people with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, share common perspectives, and engage in joint action in geographical locations or settings" (ibid., p. 1932)

By this definition, community-led social innovations may be those which emerge from people living in a specific geographic location (e.g. an urban city, a small rural villages, or specific settings such as bars, parks, clinics). But it may also include people who are from the same population (e.g. older people), as well as people with the same profession or those who share a common experience e.g. health condition, ethnic or religious group.

However we would challenge the assumption that a community may only be geographically-based and include communities that are not necessarily bound by place. This allows us to consider transient communities such as refugees. As such, regarding this area, we define a community as:

A group of people with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, share common perspectives, and engage in joint action.

Having defined community, we need to clarify what would count as *community-led*. For this we look at definitions of *community participation*, which is widely discussed across a range of literature focused on issues from healthcare to young people. Community participation can vary by degree. Participation falls into a continuum ranging from negligible or *co-opted* – "in which community members serve as token representatives with no part in making decisions" to *collective action* – "in which local people initiate action, set the agenda, and work towards a commonly defined goal" (Hauser, 2002).

Community-led social innovation is driven by the belief that "the wisdom to solve intractable social problems lies within the community" (Singhal, 2010). When defining community-led social innovation we can look to other forms of community activities which tackle the challenges and problems the communities face. For example *community development* is a familiar concept and is discussed more frequently than *innovation*. Community development is "essentially a bottom up approach, of supporting and empowering people to take action with others in their community. It is based on the belief that people can develop their skills and knowledge to make a difference which will benefit others in their community" (Thompson, 2014).

Social innovation often recognises exploits and coordinates assets and resources which would otherwise be wasted, under-used or not used at all in order to tackle social problems. In some cases, these assets and resources can be latent (such as the skills that communities have at their disposal), intangible (finance) and/or physical (buildings and physical spaces). (The Young Foundation, 2012) Community-led social innovation involves people with direct experience of the problems working together to maximise these assets more effectively.

From this perspective communities have been firmly embedded within discourses around social innovation which have often emphasised the desirability of *bottom-up* or grassroots solutions. Because com-

munity-led innovation is defined by the role of the community or of community actors it is also frequently associated with ideas such as *user-led design* and with research around *loci of innovation and actors*. It can also be said to be associated with certain kinds of actions. The categories below outline forms of community action which are associated with community-led innovation. Importantly these forms of action are not always social innovation, rather they provide forums for social innovation.

Community-led voluntary action	Community-led voluntary service is when a community organises in order to provide social provision for others on a voluntary basis. Importantly this can be very informal and amount simply to an ‘innovative practice’. In some circumstances this might be as ‘small’ as an individual finding an innovative way to tackle a neighbour’s loneliness. On the other side this might be highly organised through voluntary service organisations, for example a national network providing support for new parents.
Community-led collaboration	Community-led innovation can be present in the relationships that communities build with public services. This can include the use of collaborative working groups to inform public service delivery and policy. Examples of organisations facilitating this type of collaborative innovation include Local Trust and Expert Patients who support hospitals and health providers.
Community-led charity	These are charities set up by local people in order to serve the needs of their community. They do not necessarily have to remain tied exclusively to their community, however, and can be seen to scale beyond the circumstances where they were developed, however they should maintain close ties with the communities in which they work. For example the Hastings Pier Charity who bought the town’s near-derelict pier through a community share offer and are now involved in supporting regeneration across the town.
Community-led social enterprise	An organisation trading for social purpose with profits usually reinvested rather than going to shareholders. It is an organisation started, run or owned by a community of identity as well as for a community (Locality, 2016). It can take a number of legal forms including limited company, community interest company, co-operative, and community benefit society. Examples of key areas where there is significant activity in this kind of community-led innovation include energy cooperatives and community cafes. Brixton Village, for example was a new initiative in South London which saw the reclamation of the Brixton Arcade for community based shops, cafes and stalls. (The Young Foundation, 2012)
Community-led social movements	These are campaigns and actions that are powered by social media. They can be short-term and often start as spontaneous response to highly topical issues and challenges. Examples are Black Lives Matter,

	Refugees Welcome. Platforms like Avaaz, 38 Degrees, Change.org play a key role in supporting the growth of these movements.
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Table 1: Forms of community action associated with community-led innovation

There is a broad array of networks that are relevant to the area of community-led innovation. Many of these were set up in recognition that many communities were working in similar ways or were learning from one another in order to solve similar problems. Some of these were set up in order to foster community movements or community-led innovation. They frequently aim to spread movements broadly (e.g. the Transition Town network). In some cases these networks have developed out of an attempt to address a *wicked problem* (e.g. the Nyeleni Network) whereas in other cases networks have developed out of an understanding of the power of communities to find appropriate and context specific solutions to intractable problems (e.g. VCSEs).

Below we give examples of the kinds of networks that currently link together groups of people who conduct work that is relevant to the field of community-led innovation. The networks can be grouped into two broad categories defined by the approach that they take to fostering community-led innovation.

1. Networks of organisations with the same sector focus. There are many organisations that work on sector specific problems and many of these are organised into networks to help spread and promote work on particular societal challenges. Particular issues where there has been an attempt by the academic community to understand community led Innovation include sustainability; food-growing and food sovereignty and climate change (Scott-Cato & Hillier, 2010). These represent a local challenge, resistance or as Salamon terms, a "global associational revolution". (Salamon et al., 1999) Other topics of more *traditional* concern to communities include health and wellbeing, employment and social inclusion and safety. Examples of these kinds of networks can be found in Table 2 below.

Network	Location	Description
Nyeleni Network	Global/ Europe	A global movement for food sovereignty
ECOLISE	Europe	Coalition of community-led initiatives on sustainability and climate change. Includes international, national and sometimes regional networks of community-based initiatives.

The Global Eco-village Network	Global	An organisation which attempts to empower citizens and communities to design and implement their own pathways to a sustainable future.
Transition Towns Network	Global (but with 50% of all initiatives in UK)	A rapidly spreading transnational grassroots network which includes both active and non-active local transition initiatives.
MetropolisNet	Europe	A network of different types of organisations developing and implementing local strategies for employment and social inclusion in a number of European cities.
Incredible Edible Network (IEN)	UK	An umbrella organisation for Incredible Edible Groups whose focus is on growing produce and working together as a community.
The University of the Third Age (U3A)	UK	A movement of retired and semi-retired people to come together and learn together. There are local volunteer-run manifestations of what is a national group.
London Safer Future Communities voluntary, community and social enterprise Network (London SFC VCSE Network)	London, UK	A forum for VCSE organisations with an interest in criminal justice, crime prevention and/or community safety issues. (LVSC, 2017)
ENAR (European Network Against Racism)	Brussels	An anti-racism network that combines advocacy for racial equality and facilitating cooperation among civil society anti-racism actors in Europe.

Table 2: Examples of sector specific CLI networks

2. Networks of organisations with similar approaches. These organisations aim to link organisations that have similar needs, requirements or approaches. They often provide a *hub* or a route for members of the public to find out what is going on among more disparate organisations. In some cases they can help by sharing knowledge or offering support (including funds) to organisations that work to serve community needs. Examples of organisational types are RCOs (Refugee Community Or-

ganisations)⁵⁷ and VCSEs (voluntary, community and social enterprise) organisations in the UK. Examples of these networks can be found in Table 3 below.

Network	Location	Description
European Volunteer Centre (Centre européen du volontariat, CEV)	Europe	Network of over 80 national, regional and local volunteer centres and volunteer support agencies across Europe. Its vision is for a Europe in which volunteering is central in building a cohesive and inclusive society based on solidarity and active citizenship.
The Maker Movement	Global	A showcase of invention, creativity and resourcefulness and celebration of the Maker Movement. Mini Maker Faires are independently produced celebrations of local maker culture. Their program provides tools and resources to help others to make a Maker Faire event.
Amplify		Amplify is a programme that works in a number of locations across the UK which seeks to unlock the latent potential for change through social innovation.
Scottish Refugee Policy Forum	Scotland	A federation of Refugee Community Organisations (RCOs).
International Federation of Settlements and Neighbourhood Centres (IFS)	Global	An association of national, regional and local organisations working to strengthen communities around the world. It's more than 10,000 members include multi-purpose community-based organisations from across the globe.
VONNE (Voluntary Organisations' Network North East)	North East England	The support body for the voluntary, community and social enterprise (VCSE) sector in the North East of England. Represent over 800 members from across the region.
LVSC (Voluntary and Community Action for London)	London, UK	The collaborative leader and support of London's VCSE sector.
The Big Local and	England	Provides support for social entrepreneurs working in local

⁵⁷ RCOs are organisations run by refugees and for them. The work of RCOs is broad and can include everything from organising events, drop-ins or information sessions for members, to raising the public's and policy makers' awareness about issues affecting refugees.

Un.Ltd Star People		communities to develop solutions to need in the places that they live, work and volunteer. This includes one-to-one support, expert advice and resources. The Star People programme represents a new approach to place-based working, supporting individuals in Big Local areas.
FabLabs	Global	A global network of local labs, enabling invention by providing access to tools for digital fabrication. Fab labs are available as a community resource.
Locality	UK	Network that helps people set up locally owned or locally run organisations
Ashoka	Global	Finds, selects and supports the world's leading social entrepreneurs.
SEED Winnipeg	Canada	Aims to help low-income groups establish economically viable enterprise through loans and training programs.

Table 3: Examples of approach based networks

It is essential to note that of the two categories of network described above there can be an overlap. As such it is important that these two types of networks are brought together so that they might be able to learn from each other. It is important to build on the work that community innovators are doing, to share good practice and knowledge and to ensure that pathways are in place so that when communities decide to innovate there are pathways available to help them do this. Community-led innovation, of course springs from communities, however evidence from the networks already working in this space suggests that there is a role for networks to foster, support and spread practices from around the world, to open new possibilities for community innovators.

9.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

Research topics relevant to this network tend to fall under five broad questions. These are:

1. *What do we mean by community and community-led social innovation?*
 - a. What is a community?
 - b. How does action occur within communities?
 - c. What counts as community-led innovation?
 - d. How can different types of funding foster different kinds of community-led innovation?

2. *What are the barriers and drivers of community-led social innovation?*

- a. What are the key drivers of community-led innovation projects?
- b. What barriers to community-led innovation exist, for example, in policy, the market etc.?
- c. How can policy instruments be used to facilitate community-led innovations?
- d. How do regulatory frameworks impact upon community-led innovation?
- e. Within which communities/types of communities is community-led innovation more likely to emerge?
- f. What are the key characteristics and skills that facilitators of community-led innovation have and need?
- g. What are the key challenges that community-led innovation projects face?
- h. What are the opportunities and threats presented by wider socio-economic and political contexts?

3. *What support do community-led innovations need?*

- i. What do they need to be supported to start?
- j. How do you build community capacity?
- k. How do they need to be supported to scale and grow?
- l. Should they be supported to scale or would this be counter to their local nature?

4. *What does the community-led social innovation ecosystem look like?*

- a. What networking activities exist in the community-led innovation sector?
- b. Where are the gaps in the community-led social innovation ecosystem?
- c. How should we enable a community-led social innovation ecosystem?
- d. How do emerging online community-led innovations collaborate? What does their support network look like?

5. *What are the impacts of community-led innovations?*

- a. How do we evaluate and effectively monitor community-led social innovations?
- b. What does success look like?
- c. What are the benefits of community-led innovations?

Whilst so-called *bottom-up* innovation has been a much explored topic within social innovation research there are limitations to the extent to which research has been able to really understand the ways in which communities engage in the development of social innovation. Work by Moulaert notes that one of the difficulties in utilising terms that define actions as *bottom up* or *community-led* is the extent to which realities are actually more complicated. (Moulaert et al., 2010) This does need to be noted and examining the actualities of actor relationships within this field is a key dimension to creating greater understanding of how community-led innovation happens and what it means.

The disparate nature of these innovators, their different focuses means that there is significant scope for research to play a positive role in defining the benefits and the processes of community-led innovation and for investigating how best to foster it in order to engender positive social change.

Community innovators frequently do not label themselves as innovators. As such research around communities has tended to focus on other aspects of community change, such as community-led local development (CLLD). SIX explains that CLLD is about putting "people at the centre of policy-making" (SIX, 2017). Community-led innovation goes further than this and looks beyond co-design to opportunities for communities to take hold of processes and innovate themselves.

At the EU level there has been less research on community-led innovation than at national and regional levels. The tendency of EU projects has been to look at community-led local development approaches to community empowerment, this can be seen in projects such as INNOSI and in the commitment of the EU to the promotion of the LEADER method through rural development projects. There has been significantly less of a focus on projects which facilitate or seek out examples of what we would refer to as community-led innovation. However there are some EU projects that have tangential relevance. The theoretical basis of the EU funded SI-DRIVE project, for example, does have some relevance to the community-led innovation project, given its focus on social practices.

Within some research institutions there is a growing degree of focus on community-led innovation this can be seen in the work of the Grassroots Innovation Project led by Gill Seyfang at the University of East Anglia, who leads work on *grassroots innovation* with a specific focus on sustainability, and Adrian Smith of the University of Sussex who has a focus on technology and innovation studies. This work frequently uses the language of *grassroots innovation movements* rather than community-led innovation (Fressoli et al., 2014) and often has a focus on issues of sustainability and development. The Young Foundation too, through its work on projects such as the Places Programme seeks to develop theories that explore the ways in which communities and actors within communities come to innovate (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Developing theoretical dimensions of our understanding of what constitutes community-led innovation and how we can work to support it. This comes in this case from a position which uses an ethnographic research base to understand community innovation, its roots and its meanings.

Of the more programmatic research much of this appears to be done by organisations who have a specific interest in community-led innovation or who are implementing programmes related to community-led innovation. This work is frequently done with the aim of understanding to inform the development of future innovations, and help organisations who wish to work with them to better engage and support community-led social innovations. In other circumstances those with a focus on social innovation find that they are necessarily drawn to an exploration of the role of the community.

By example, in the UK, ChangeUp was a government funded programme launched in 2004 which "promised to transform the voluntary sector's infrastructure." (Third Sector, 2011) Although the programme was abandoned a decade later, during ChangeUp's existence it funded research by organisations such as the Charities Evaluation Services and the Federation for Community Development Learning (FCDL). These research projects included reports exploring Refugee Community Organisations (RCOs) looking at what they are, how they originate and work, how to set them up, and how and why to work with them, specifically local infrastructure organisations. Other organisations funding research relevant to community led-innovation include: the National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO) which has been involved in research around active participation (Brodie et al., 2011; Brodie et al, 2009); the Institute for Voluntary Action Research (IVAR); and UnLtd.

From a more sector specific approach there is a significant amount of research that is currently occurring in community-led energy and sustainability projects (Walker, 2008; Seyfang, 2010; Seyfang et al., 2013). Other research already conducted on community energy projects includes the development of wind technology in Denmark, the solar collector do-it yourself movement in Austria, and car sharing in Switzerland (Ornetzeder & Rohrer, 2013). Their analysis focuses among other things on: structural conditions and resources of origin; motivations of those actors involved; learning processes and outcomes. The subject of the research bears clear resemblance to analyses conducted as part of social innovation research but does not necessarily relate itself to the body of social innovation research.

Interestingly many of those who are conducting this kind of research are not necessarily using the language of social innovation or looking at implications of their work beyond their own sector. Importantly there may also be a role for social innovation research to energise these fields. Work by Feola and Nunes looking at grassroots innovative solutions for climate change adaptation and mitigation states that: "little evidence exists on replication, international comparisons are rare, and research tends to overlook discontinued responses in favour of successful ones" (Feola & Nunes, 2013). The focus on the processes of scaling and replication within social innovation may help these fields to understand how they can go about increasing their impacts.

9.4 METHODS AND ROLE OF RESEARCH

The theoretical basis for community-led innovation is currently underdeveloped and therefore much of the theoretical work relevant to community-led innovation comes from across community-based disciplines (e.g. community studies, community organising, movement building etc.) and from social innovation generally.

There is work that needs to be done to bring together research on community action with research on social innovation (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Community is frequently explored, particularly, in three broad ways, sometimes simultaneously:

1. *Place*: A place based approach to considering community is drawn from work by thinkers such as Michael Young and Peter Willmott (Wilmot, 1986; Young & Willmott). The place based approach is highly influential in the field of community studies (and locality studies) and frequently chooses to conceptualise localities or geographical communities as *ecosystems*, it frequently concentrates on issues of division of labour, social structures and actions. This literature has frequently also been linked to peace studies
2. *Practice*: A community of practice is a community of people who share a common interest or identity. They do not have to be tied to any particular place but rather can share some degree of *sameness* or *interest* that facilitates their collectivity. Communities of practice have been theorised by academics like anthropologist Jean Lave and educationalist Etienne Wenger (Wenger et al., 2002). Wenger theorised communities of interest as having three distinct dimensions (Wenger, 1998) mutual engagement, joint enterprise, and shared repertoire. Through these stages a community establishes norms, builds relationships, creates shared understanding and then builds common resource.
3. *Affinity*: Suggests that community that is built through "social affinity"(Vela-McConnell, 1999). This approach sees a general understanding of connectedness translated through empathy into active recognition. It can be a far looser definition of community which theorises a notion of 'social cohesion'.

Within these understandings of community there is an array of literature considering different dimensions and approaches to understanding how communities constitute, build, and act. From the perspective of community-led innovation however, the theoretical basis is still underdeveloped.

From the innovation field there are a number of theoretical frameworks which could provide a basis for understanding community-led innovation from social practice theory(Howaldt et al., 2014) to strategic niche management theory (Seyfang et al., 2012). In the field of sustainable development multi-level perspective (MLP) has traction as a way of understanding the relationships between macro-level structures and micro-level actors⁵⁸. However whilst these theoretical directions can provide routes for understanding community-led innovation more work needs to be done to develop theories tailored for understanding community-led development specifically.

This can be considered a clear research gap for the area of community-led innovation.

It can be difficult to look at methodological approaches to community-led innovation because where it is explored it is often through prisms that would not necessarily recognise the term *community-led innova-*

⁵⁸ Geels, F. W. (2011). The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environmental innovation and societal transitions*, 1(1), 24-40.

tion. However it is possible to identify a number of different methodological approaches from the very participatory to the highly quantitative.

Ethnographic Approach:

The traditions of community studies, borne out of the work of people like Michael Young, frequently utilise ethnographic approaches to understanding the dynamics of communities and community-led innovation. This approach tries to understand not just action but also the meaning of action and therefore can be useful for helping us to understand how community-led innovation manifests: the drivers, and barriers that can stand in its way.

Participatory Approach:

Whilst many different approaches are used to study community-led innovation, frequently, approaches used to measure community-led social innovation tend to align closely with the ethos of community-led innovation, in that it is participatory and inclusive of the community. This often means that research methods are chosen that allow research to be *of* and *by* the community and not, as is more traditional, *on* and *to* the community. Examples of these methods include community-led action research; where the community defines and carries out the research to gather evidence and make recommendations for change⁵⁹ and community-based participatory research (CBPR). CBPR is a partnership approach to research that equitably involves actors like community members, organisational representatives, and researchers in all aspects of the research process and in which all partners contribute expertise and share decision making and ownership. CBPR can include participatory evaluation. Participatory Approaches can also manifest in participatory action research (PAR) and through the use of peer researchers.

Strategic Learning Approaches

Another form that programme evaluation can take is a strategic learning approach to evidence gathering through delivery partners. This is a non-participatory qualitative approach to research which is not just about measuring numbers but about understanding processes and ecosystems. Strategic Learning uses evaluation to help organisations or groups to learn quickly from their work. In this sense it can bear similarities to PAR. The approach integrates evaluation and critical evaluative analysis into decision making processes and allows for ongoing reflection and the modification of action.

Case-study approaches:

Community-led innovation, like other forms of social innovation, can be difficult to understand broadly because of the dispersed nature of innovation and the difficulty, therefore in building a generalisable

⁵⁹ Scottish Community Development Centre 'Community-led Action Research'. Available online at: <http://www.scdc.org.uk/what/community-led-action-research/>

evidence base. As such case study approaches are sometimes utilised in order to try and understand how to foster community-led innovation or in order to understand the ways in which community-led innovation manifest. Case study approaches can also be used in order to provide a kind of journey based evaluation of progress or support.

Quantitative approaches

Whilst community-led innovation can sometimes lend itself to more qualitative research this is a field where quantitative research is also done. This can manifest in a number of different methods including surveys, quasi-experiments and even RCTs, meta-analysis and systematic review. These are frequently used in the exploration and evaluation of specific programmes or kinds of programmes. For example, Seyfang et al. (2013) conducted an independent, UK-wide survey of community energy projects. This was to investigate the objectives, origins and development of these groups across the UK, their activities in general and their networking activities as a sector. Feola and Nunes also used an online survey in their research into the Transition Movement. This was to uncover general patterns of success and failure in grassroots innovations in 24 countries (n=276). They conducted data analysis to test the effect of internal and contextual factors of success as drawn from the existing literature, as well as to identify clusters of transition initiatives with similar internal and contextual factor configurations. They found that "geographical locations matter with regard to where transition initiatives take root and the extent of their success, and 'place attachment' may have a role in the diffusion of successful initiatives"(Feola & Nunes). They suggest that longitudinal comparative studies may be able to "advance understanding in this regard, as well as inform the changing nature of the definition of success at different stages of grassroots innovation development, and the dynamic nature of local and global linkages"(ibid.).

Reflecting the diversity of methodological approaches to community-led innovation research there are numerous methods that can be used. However in this section we will explore a selection that is particularly relevant. Using peer researchers can be a common method in the field of community-led innovation research. The aim of this method is to recruit and train researchers from the study population to become community action researchers. The use of peer researchers carries both benefits and drawbacks. On the one hand, peer researchers have an understanding of meaning in their communities that is often difficult or time consuming for an outside researcher to replicate. On the other hand, there are drawbacks to this level of *embeddedness*, for example there may be certain social, cultural or political dimensions that are rendered invisible to the peer researcher through their *normalcy*. This can help to create biases and it is frequently the case that peer researchers should be managed in ways that allow for exploration of these tensions. Research conducted by peer researchers can require an entirely different form of analysis to research conducted by outside researchers.

The methods and tools employed by community-led action research need to be appropriate and engaging for the community concerned. Example methodologies would include "drawings, photography, video diaries; drop in sessions and story dialogue; these methods being used in conjunction with or instead of

traditional methods such as questionnaires⁶⁰. However more standard methods such as surveys using score-carding are also used.

Other methods commonly used include the secondary analysis of Census and publicly available survey data. This may be used to compare, for example, a local area's health or wellbeing indicators against national level. Publicly available survey data may also be used to highlight and inform issues of local concern. For example Youth Link, a project which aimed to empower New Mexico's young people in public policymaking members conducted secondary analysis of KIDS Count data from the state Department of Health. They also developed, implemented, and analysed surveys over the years to better understand the concerns of youth (Minkler et al., n.d.).

9.5 IMPACT

Issues around measuring impact frequently concern issues of authenticity: are these activities genuinely *community-led*? Community-led innovation relies on the capacity of individuals within the community, who often may not have the skills to make change happen. The impact and success of community-led innovation "tends to be directly related to the ability of the community to develop and incorporate innovative practices"⁶¹. Less experienced/more deprived communities are therefore likely to face greater barriers to innovating. They may require additional support (or *hand-holding*) to do so and this then brings into question whether it is truly community-led.

The potential impact of community-led innovation is not limited to the tangible benefits associated with tackling the single issue of focus; it can extend to a number of other wider benefits for the community and project participants. Feola and Nunes, for example, measure the success of a grassroots innovation in terms of "social connectivity, empowerment, and environmental impact"(Feola & Nunes, 2014). The process of innovating can also result in building the capacity of community members, through the development of an array of soft skills, particularly as communities often face complex challenges and therefore require creative solutions that are feasible even with limited resources⁶².

However, there is the associated difficulty in measuring these added social values which do not necessarily lend themselves to more traditional matrices, things that are easily countable. The impact and effect of increasing an individual or community's sense of empowerment, for example, tends to be diffuse and not easy to metricise. One of the challenges therefore remains around exactly what we should be evaluating and how to do this. Measuring outputs is therefore likely to be more straightforward than identifying and measuring wider social impacts.

⁶⁰ Scottish Community Development Centre 'Community-led Action Research'. Available online at: <http://www.scdc.org.uk/what/community-led-action-research/>

⁶¹ <http://www3.carleton.ca/cedtap/conference/cednetreport.pdf>

⁶² <http://www3.carleton.ca/cedtap/conference/cednetreport.pdf>

In the case of community renewable energy projects, for example, the displacement of fossil fuel consumption with the increased generation of renewable energy is relatively straightforward to measure. However, the "range of social impacts which may result in additional positive sustainability outcomes" (Rogers et al., 2012) is less so. When these impacts are investigated it is frequently using more qualitative methods. Boyle et al. (2006) used peer researchers to help "assess the impact of a co-production approach in terms of whether and how it:

- Affected participants' self-esteem, confidence and well-being
- Strengthened social capital and social networks
- Generated new opportunities for personal development" (Boyle et al., 2006)

To understand the impact of these they primarily conducted "interpretative phenomenological analysis, which meant listening to people telling their own stories, comparing them and analysing them". This, they argue, helped them to discover "some of the subtleties of co-production and community development of this kind" (Boyle et al., 2006) often missed by using statistical and more objective approaches. However, it inevitably also means that it is not possible to reach clear conclusions about causality. This is one of the pitfalls of this kind of research, "because it avoids numbers, it is hard for the findings to come as a surprise to researchers" (ibid., p. 3).

9.6 CONCLUSIONS

Community-led social innovation refers to those innovative actions that communities take in order to create socially positive outcomes. Despite the focus around *grassroots* social innovation and in particular on the dynamics of various actors involved in the process of innovators the research landscape around community-led social innovation is dispersed. For this reason this cannot be said to be a cohesive field of social innovation research and the literature is highly diffused among a number of different disciplines and approaches. However there are a number of fields where community-led social innovation is not only visible but growing and thanks to the work of research institutions such as the Young Foundation (formerly the Institute of Community Studies) work is being done in order to understand how to support community innovators, through, for example accelerator models.

In part because of the diffuse nature of this area there are a number of areas where the research landscape can appear thin. This is particularly around the theory and in our understanding of the processes of community-led innovation. We hope that through network activities we can encourage the emergence of a field of community-led innovation study and that this in turn will help us to address some of these research gaps.

Attempts within the SIC project to engage a *Community-Led Innovation Network* will not aim to include cooperatives. We feel that the *Social Economy* network may be better placed to consider cooperatives. However where cooperatives are clear examples of community-led innovation we will engage with them, whilst recognising that they will also be engaging with the *Social Economy* network. This also offers an excellent opportunity for fruitful collaboration between the *Community-Led Development Network* and the *Social Economy Network*.

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**SOCIAL
INNOVATION
COMMUNITY**

10 Corporate Social Innovation

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10.1 INTRODUCTION

Today, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a common and in a lot of large companies used concept to increase their impact on environmental and social issues. Since the mid-1990s, when CSR was still a new and not so well received concept, it has come a long way. Back then, CSR had the reputation of being a risk for a company, especially in terms of profit maximisation. It has been Milton Friedman (1970) who positioned that businesses have the mere purpose to maximise shareholders' value, and that this constitutes the main responsibility of any given corporation. Management, thus, has neither the right to use shareowners' money nor the required democratic legitimacy to pursue broader goals that would go beyond the business' primary function. However, Friedman (1970) also mentioned that managers as employees of stockowner must stay "[...] within the rules of the game [...]" (Friedman, 1970, p. 33) while adhering to its fiduciary duty. That has drastically changed and nowadays it has become essential for many enterprises and MNCs to take on social and environmental responsibility (Crets & Celer, 2013, p. 77).

In academia, the discussion on whether Corporate Social Innovation (CSI) constitutes a more developed form of CSR, being more strategically anchored within a business's core operating functions, or whether CSI represents a new strand of research. Social innovation or innovation as a whole is increasingly playing a part for corporates and businesses and the importance will grow further in the near future due to the fact that society expects corporations to act in a responsible manner.

10.2 NETWORKS AND THEMATIC SCOPE

The networks and actors in CSI are businesses and, which further can be recognised as a direct driver of social innovation. Moreover, they also act as facilitators through their increasing number of cross-sector collaborations, which are often driven by new approaches to corporate philanthropy and social responsibility, process and product innovation, and the concept of creating shared value. In the table below, three selected networks that play a vital role for advancing the case of CSI are listed. These networks represent and support organisations and individuals dealing with Corporate Social Innovation. Due to a lack of scientific networks in this field, no examples can be presented in this table.

Network	Description and Objectives
Enterprise Europe	"The Enterprise Europe Network is the world's largest support network for small and medium sized businesses (SMEs) with international ambitions. It

<p>Network (international)</p>	<p>has 3,000 experts across 600 member organisations in more than 60 countries. Member organisations include chambers of commerce and industry, technology centres, and research institutes.” The Enterprise Europe Network was launched in February 2008 by the European Commission and will be running from 2014 until 2020. They support SMEs across the fields Partnership, Advisory and Innovation. The innovation support, amongst other things includes: advising to access fundings and finding the right technology to improve the innovation.</p>
<p>European Business Network for Corporate Social Responsibility (BE)</p>	<p>CSR Europe is an international non for profit organisation, headquartered in Belgium. It is organised as a membership network, having two types of members - corporate members and national partner organisations - who are represented in the organisation's governing bodies. It further receives support from the European Commission. Currently there are around 50 corporate members (e.g. BASF, CocaCola, Danone, IBM, VW ...) as well as 45 national partner organisations (e.g. BITC. MVO Nederlands, UPJ, econsense). Its network is engaging with more than 10'000 companies and key stakeholders, for purposes of awareness raising, capacity building, and CSR promotion / support.</p> <p>According to the CSR Europe website (2016), its mission can be summarised to the following ambitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - support companies in building sustainable competitiveness by providing a platform for innovation - Foster cooperation / collaboration between businesses and their respective stakeholders - strengthening Europe's global CSR position through engagement with EU institutions and other international players. <p>Through these activities, CSR Europe hopes to contribute to the EU's 2020 strategy “[...] for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth.” (ibid.)</p>
<p>industriAll Europe (CHE)</p>	<p>IndustriALL Global Union represents 50 million workers in 140 countries in the mining, energy and manufacturing sectors and describes itself as “[...] a force in global solidarity taking up the fight for better working conditions and</p>

	<p>trade union rights around the world” (IndustriAll, 2015).</p> <p>Founded in 2012, the organization brings together affiliates of several former global union federations, e.g. International Metalworkers' Federation, International Federation of Chemical, Energy, Mine and General Workers' Unions and International Textiles Garment and Leather Workers' Federation. Thus, the Union represents workers from a variety of sectors.</p> <p>The global Union stresses that it “[...] fights for another model of globalization and a new economic and social model that puts people first, based on democracy and social justice.” (IndustriAll, 2015).</p> <p>IndustriALL strives to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build stronger unions - Organize and increase union membership - Fight for trade union rights - Fight against precarious work (including contract and agency labour) - Build union power to confront global capital - Promote industrial policy and sustainability - Promote social justice and globalization - Ensure equal rights and women’s participation - Create safe workplaces - Improve democracy and inclusiveness
<p>The European Business Ethics Network (EBEN)</p>	<p>Founded 1987 in Brussels, the European Business Ethics Network (EBEN) can be considered the only international network which is wholly committed to the promotion of ethical business conduct in industry, public and voluntary sector as well as in academia. Members therefore include business people, public administration manager as well as academics and are representing the interests (in business ethics) from four different sectors. The network consists of up to 800 people, which are operating in groups in over</p>

	<p>40 countries. Moreover, 18 national Networks exist, for instance in Germany, Poland, the Netherlands, Spain, the UK and are being developed in Estonia, Turkey and France. Its mission is "to promote ethics and excellence in businesses, to increase awareness about ethical challenges in the global marketplace and to enable dialogue on the role of business in society" (EBEN, 2017). The networks activities include (academic) conferences, doctoral workshops, organization of various interests groups, and the provision of different platforms to exchange knowledge and best practices.</p>
<p>The Academy of Business in Society</p>	<p>The Academy of Business in Society (ABIS) was founded in 2002 at INSEAD by five leading global companies, leading European Business Schools well as with support of the European Commission. Nowadays, it is a network consisting of over 130 companies, business schools, NGOs, Networks and other institutions across the globe, aiming at the promotion of sustainable business practices through encouraging partnerships, learning and research. Thereby, ABIS can be considered a reference point organizations and businesses which are seeking access to research and best practices in corporate social responsibility, sustainability, and governance issues (ABIS, 2017a). Activities include the organization of an annual colloquium related to global corporate responsibility and sustainability issues, the hosting of forums that detail how to bring ABIS knowledge into action, international roundtables etc (ABIS, 2017b). Moreover, ABIS is co-creator of the UN's global compact "Principles for Responsible Management Education".</p>

Table 1: Networks of Corporate Social Innovation

Another important actor (but not a network) in the field of researching responsible business conduct, shared value and corporate social innovation is the Center for Social Innovation at Stanford University. Its connection to social innovation, and its role as a network actor when discussing corporate social innovations are twofold. First and foremost, Stanford University has an established research centre on social innovation, located in its graduate school of business. Within this research centre "[...] future leaders [become educated on] social and environmental change." (Stanford Graduate School of Business, 2016). The centre's mission statement explicates that it aims at bringing social and environmental change to the world. This will be done "[...] through research, education, and experiential learning [...]" as well as individual capacity-building. The centre conducts a variety of research in the field of social innovation, such as responsible supply chain management and innovations related to global health. Moreover, it developed a certificate program. Students studying at the centre become eligible for a certificate in public management and social innovation, which acknowledges a student's capacity in ad-

addressing societal challenges. Moreover, the Stanford University publishes the Stanford Social Innovation Review (SSIR). The magazine appears quarterly and is accessible either through its designated website or in a printed version. It is published by the Stanford Centre on Philanthropy and Civil Society. The review aims at informing the public – through webinars, articles, conferences etc. – about practices in and theories related to social innovations. The official slogan states that it wants to inform and inspire “leaders of social change”.

10.3 RESEARCH TOPICS

Social innovation is an overarching topic in Corporate Social Innovation. As in most social innovation communities, there is no set definition for social innovation. The World Economic Forum’s Global Agenda Council on social innovation defines social innovation as “the application of innovative, practical, sustainable, market-based approaches to benefit society in general, and low-income or underserved populations in particular” (World Economic Forum, 2016, p. 5).

Another common definition is from the European Commission: “Social innovations are new ideas that meet social needs, create social relationships and form new collaborations. These innovations can be products, services or models addressing unmet needs more effectively” (EU-Commission, 2016). The INSEAD Social Innovation Centre in France defines social innovation as the “[...] introduction of new business models and market-based mechanisms that deliver sustainable economic, environmental and social prosperity” (INSEAD, 2016).

A research focus regarding social innovation is the relation between Corporate Social Responsibility and Corporate social innovation. Social innovation is understood differently in corporate discussions, which might obstruct the development of it in corporate businesses. “While some see it as the next big thing after CSR or CSR 3.0, for others it is simply a new term for CSR” (Osburg, 2013, p. 13). Thomas Osburg states further, that social innovation is not the next CSR, because the concept of social innovation adds social value to their goal, which is beyond the traditional Corporate Social Responsibility. Furthermore, he refers to Googins and says, that the role of CSR is to support business in areas like basic citizenship duties or in maintaining its licence to operate and that is why innovation has never been a part of CSR (Osburg, 2013, p. 17-18). He stresses (2012) that most enterprises are no “social entrepreneurs as such and most likely will not be in the future. The CSR concept has moved on from voluntary contributions beyond the core business to an integral part of all business processes in the last years. If we think longer term, fostering and implementing true social innovations with a clear impact for both the company and society is the logical next step and maybe the ultimate proof of a company’s responsible business operations with value creation for all” (ibid.).

As it has been noted, the concept of Corporate Social Innovation is relatively new within the academic debate. It is unclear whether CSI constitutes a new form of corporate social responsibility or whether CSI rather should be viewed as a new set of strategies through which corporations attempt to live up to their responsibilities and obligations towards society at large. Several authors have outlined the set of variables that would make CSI different from CSR, however clear research implications are lacking.

According to Mirvis et al. (2016) and the WEF (2016), the main aspects differentiating CSR from CSI are concerned with:

- CSI strategies are generally aligned with a firm's overall innovation and business strategy. Therefore, CSI is not characterized by a philanthropic intent but a strategic investment.
- CSI requires that companies engage in societally relevant Research & Development thereby contributing not only manpower and money but other corporate assets as well. Thus, it can be argued that a business' core assets are leveraged in order to produce social innovations.
- CSI are usually managed from within a firm's core functions. Thereby, collaboration across different functions seems to be an important characteristic.
- Moreover, the aspect of co-creation with internal and external partners to find solutions for societal ills becomes inevitable to CSI.
- Whereas CSR is often viewed as a function of a company's reputation management, CSI further focuses on creating new sources of revenue.

Many leading business schools (e.g. European Business School, INSEAD and Stanford) have created centres for social innovation. These business schools are leading research nowadays in social innovation and are working together with universities and leading companies. The research focuses on social innovation to drive Corporate Sustainability. (Osburg, 2013, p. 19-20).

There are a lot of research studies regarding the relationship between firm profitability and Corporate Social Responsibility. It has been confirmed that there is a positive but highly variable relationship between them. There are quite a few benefits for companies if they implement Corporate Social Responsibility policies, e.g. improve the relationship with customers and suppliers, differentiate themselves from competitors, win new business, and are viewed more positively by the public and the media (Carroll, 2015, p. 89).

Jared Tham (2010) created a graph which reveals the benefits of twinning innovation with corporate responsibility (Tham, 2010, p. 49):

Table 2: Twinning innovation with CSR

Tham further states that “social enterprises have been the torchbearers for social innovation” (Tham, 2010, p. 50), but they do not have the resources to unlock their potential, like big corporates or businesses, who can get the business returns and the social/ environmental return on investment on a much larger scale. Therefore, social enterprises or smaller corporates and business in general, need an incentive to invest in social innovation.

Creating Shared Value is one of the most recent concepts in Corporate Social Innovation and Responsibility, introduced by Porter and Kramer, as well as the Bottom-of-the Pyramid approach by Prahalad (BoP).

Creating Shared Value

The concept of creating shared value, or short CSV, was introduced by the two economists M. Porter and M. Kramer in 2011. Referring to the concept of corporate social responsibility, the two authors stress that a single aim, may it be of an economic, environmental or of a social nature (Moczadlo, 2015), is no longer sufficient, therefore Porter and Kramer propose an extension of the CSR concept. For them, corporate social responsibility as such has been applied more or less in the fashion of marketing and reputation management (Ibid.) in which the costs involved to start CSR initiatives are considered expenses that are necessary if a business wants to cope with external pressures.

In this retrospect, they introduce their conception of creating shared value. CSV holds that business success is not only dependent upon profit maximization, but on societal well-being and prosperity. Businesses operations in a specific social context and the prosperity of that context are interrelated and

necessary for successful business conduct (von Liel & Lütge, 2015). Social engagement and socially responsible behaviour are considered to impact positively on a company's competitiveness if the "CSR" or "CSV" strategy becomes core to, thus embedded in, the overall business strategy (von Liel & Lütge, 2015; Porter & Kramer, 2011).

With the integration of social issues into business processes, aspects of innovation management, productivity, long-term competitiveness as well as the development of new markets and growth opportunities can be enhanced (3). With that, the value created is shared between society and the corporation. Porter and Kramer propose three options through which shared value can be created (Porter & Kramer, 2011).

First of all, companies could focus on reconceiving products and markets. By introducing innovative solutions to social problems, companies' competitiveness can be enhanced. The development of new products as well as by tapping into underdeveloped or non-traditional markets, companies have the opportunity to do so. Another strategy is related to the redefinition of productivity in the value chain. Numerous opportunities to create shared value are available with that strategy, this is due to the fact that societal problems can cause economic costs to a firm's value chain. The value chain can be redefined e.g. through optimising energy consumption, improved logistic systems, reduced resource usages as well as coordinated sourcing models.

The last approach to achieve shared value is labeled enabling local cluster development. Through the development of clusters, meaning the surrounding framework condition consisting of businesses and institutions, corporations' market positioning can be enhanced. Elements of cluster development are related to the support of local suppliers as well as projects aimed at improving education and infrastructure.

Creating shared value entails embedding a social mission in the corporate culture and channeling resources to the development of innovations that can help solve social problems (Pfitzer et al., 2013, p. 4). CSV is relatively new and only time will tell, if it will stick in practice, because the idea of CSV has always been an integral part of modern CSR and it is up to businesses, if a new term is needed (Carroll, 2015, p. 95). According to the authors van Liel and Lütge (2015), the CSV concept has been discussed controversially within academia. Aspects that are regarded as positive are related to the fact that CSV clearly focuses on integration of social goals into corporate strategy. CSV therefore can be considered an offensive business strategy that aims at improving societal situations. Moreover, the authors are stressing the direct appeal towards state authorities that are in charge of designing favorable 'ecosystems' or conditions in which such business strategies can flourish. It is argued that in contrast to CSR, CSV proposes a more holistic approach, integrating different exiting approaches towards responsible business conduct and sustainable development.

Bottom-of-the Pyramid

C. K. Prahalad coined the term “Bottom of the pyramid”, or alternatively “base of the pyramid” to indicate that a large share of potential consumers are living in poverty. The BoP consists of over four billion people who have less than two Dollars per day available, totaling in an aggregated income of 12.5 trillion US\$ (Prahalad, 2012). These consumers have been ignored by the private sector for a long time, however, according to Prahalad they rather should be considered as affluent consumers which should become recipient of radically adapted and novel products and services (Schuster & Holtbrügge, 2015).

By targeting BoP markets, companies could positively contribute to the eradication of poverty and at the same time develop and access markets for the future, as formerly excluded people become part of business activities (ibid.). With that, BoP could constitute a paradigm shift in business perceptions in which the people living at the BoP are no longer considered recipients of foreign aid and charitable givings, but as a part of the global market economy. It can be noted, that the BoP approach generally rests on the assumption of mutual value creation (London, 2012).

However, BoP markets differ significantly from traditional western markets. It is assumed that they are characterised by a low individual purchasing power, limited set of market information, inefficient regulatory environments, poor infrastructures and a lack of access to financial products and services (Schuster & Holtbrügge, 2015, p. 42). Therefore, the development of novel products and services becomes inevitable for businesses, if they want to operate in BoP markets, as traditional business approaches would not work in such markets. Therefore, it becomes important to analyse the needs of the BoP and to support the peoples’ transaction ability through the integration of poorer consumers in the value chain. Prahalad proposed twelve business principles that become necessary for companies conducting business in this segment. These are (Prahalad, 2009, p. 49):

- Create a new price performance envelop of products and services
- Blend existing technologies with newer technologies
- Solutions developed must be scalable and transferable across different countries
- Innovations created must focus on resource conservation, therefore a reduction in resource intensity becomes key
- Product development should start from a perspective on functionality (for BoP customers) instead a perspective on form
- Also process innovations become important in BoP markets as infrastructure (e.g. for logistics) are not as well developed in BoP markets as in developed markets. Moreover, accessing and educating BoP market customers could become a difficult task

- By taking into account the skills levels possessed in BoP markets, a deskilling of work might become critical
- Educate customers on product usage, as already mentioned, is important. However, this can become challenging as BoP market customers often have no access to traditional education channels
- It must be ensured that products also work in hostile environments
- As the customer base might be quite heterogenic, research on interfaces is important
- Methods must be developed in order to ensure that the innovative products and services also reach the targeted customer group
- Lastly, a focus on the broad architecture of the system.

In a recent work, Kolk, Rivera-Santos and Rufin (2013) came to the conclusion that by now, the social, economic and (especially) the environmental impact of BoP approaches in developing countries is still only partly approved by academia. This is can be due to the wide array of impact measures that exist and are in use for evaluating the Impact of BoP measures.

10.4 METHODS & ROLE OF RESEARCH

There are a lot of knowledge gaps in the field of Corporate Social Innovation and Responsibility. The role of research is to fill these gaps in the upcoming time. We have a good understanding why corporates engage in CSR, what the results of the engagements are, and under which conditions these results are likely to be observed. However, research needs to be conducted for the processes and mechanisms through which CSR actions and policies lead to separate outcomes. Almost all studies focus on only one of the three levels of analysis (institutional, organizational, individual) in CSR research, instead of taking a multilevel approach. Such an approach would be capable of integrating different conceptual streams, e.g. institutional and psychological theories. Furthermore, not much is researched about CSR and CSI from the perspective of the individuals. CSR takes place at the organizational level of analysis, but individual actors take actions that lead to CSR, so they need to be focused on aswell (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012, pp. 952-953).

In regards of research methods, both quantitative and qualitative are used to progress in the field of social innovation in corporates and businesses. An example for a quantitative study is an empirical analysis from Marcus Wagner (2010) who linked social innovation with corporate social performance and the role that family firms play in this. The first of his two hypothesis is: "There is a positive association of corporate social performance and innovation with high social benefits" (Wagner, 2010, p. 585).

To confirm or to falsify his hypothesis he used four different databases (Compustat, Worldscope Disclosure, BankerOne and the ratings of CSR and environmental management activities carried out by KLD). He discovered that there is a significant positive association indicating that Corporate Social Performance could drive innovation with high social benefits (Wagner, 2010).

Quantitative methods are more dominant than qualitative methods in the research field of Corporate Social Innovation (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012, pp. 952-953). Qualitative analysis are mostly used to complement quantitative findings by drawing theoretical inferences with other studies and methods (Nga & Shamuganathan, 2010, p. 268).

10.5 IMPACT

Currently, the topic of Corporate Social Innovation is not ranking high on the academic agenda. According to an expert some efforts are recognisable but outcomes generated by research has not yet well contributed to businesses' taking off the issue. The expert stated further that no new researchers are entering the field and the ones already engaged are digging deeper into the topic, becoming even more theoretical and less valuable for practitioners (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). According to a second expert there is still a disconnect between social innovation research and the vast CSR research community (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017).

Another expert shares similar impressions regarding the progression of CSI. It needs to be discussed and seen, whether social innovation can survive as a concept in corporate businesses, even when it is regarded as a part of CSR. Social innovation still remains unknown among most stakeholders. The expert further explains that the CSI community is fragmented among practitioners, but not among the researchers (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Nevertheless, in a recent article Jürgen Howaldt (2016) explains that CSI is an opportunity for corporate businesses to deal with the development of new business areas. The concept of social innovation might encourage corporate businesses to conceive new innovation strategies to take advantage of the potentials that lie within CSI (Howaldt, 2016).

10.6 CONCLUSIONS

Corporate Social Innovation is a relatively new field for corporate businesses. As seen above, it has a lot of potential and might become more relevant in the future. It is interconnected with Corporate Social Responsibility, but there is no mutual opinion about it.

Unfortunately CSI has a tough time taking off as a research area in the last couple of years. CSI as a research field is stagnating for the time being. According to an expert, CSI as such often is not recognised as a single research objective, instead the concept is often used under the overall research agenda of the shared value approach (SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey, 2017). Even though CSI experienced some upheaval among the research community, when it comes to the application of the concept among practitioners and businesses, the concept rather remains undervalued and unrecognised by the business sector.

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11 Conclusions and Outlook

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Thanks to a growing number of projects, conferences, research initiatives and increasing collaborative efforts, in recent years, the area of social innovation has emerged as a research field. On the one hand, this research field is strongly linked to practice, as far as its thematic scope is concerned. Many research projects deal with very concrete practical issues in areas, such as education, health care or mobility. On the other hand, both social innovation research and practice themselves are still two relatively fragmented areas with insufficiently connected actors and networks. Therefore, one central purpose of this report has been to make more visible the potential of social innovation as a transdisciplinary field of action.

Diversity in social innovation research and practice enriches the debate and the development of the research field. However, it makes community building a challenging task. The report has confirmed that many of those who work on social innovation research still do not necessarily recognise themselves as part of this community. Actually, often they do not consider themselves as researchers in the field of social innovation. In this regard, the SIC Research Landscape Expert Survey allowed for some very useful insights, making clear important differences between the various thematic areas.

At the same time, the findings of the report show that in all thematic areas under review there are ongoing processes of community building. Sometimes, this can be directly observed through creation of networks. Such networks can be purely academic, but often they are hybrid, involving actors from different societal sectors. While this may be a certain challenge when trying to structure the highly fragmented research field of social innovation, we must acknowledge that this is part of the social innovation reality. This reality also means that social innovation research and practice are closely intertwined and this link is crucial in order to understand research in this area. Hence, in order to support creation and development of inclusive networks in different areas of social innovation strong involvement of both is needed.

Thus, another important result of the report is that in recent years research on social innovation has generated a lot of valuable knowledge in order to help meeting societal challenges. At the same time, as the report reveals, the impact of this work is not always as high as it could be. One reason for this is that the field of social innovation is still very much characterised by operating in silos. By drawing the picture of SIC Research Landscape, we have tried to identify links which would help to support the formation of a community of researchers who would know each other and would work on joint research initiatives, but also to better connect social innovation research and practice.

One central finding of the report refers to the **Research on Concepts and Theories** of social innovation. The formation of this research strand as an autonomous field within social innovation research has been crucial for the development of the area as a whole. A community of researchers has emerged in this field, generally well connected to actors and communities in practice and policy. It is also directly linked to diverse thematic areas, labelled as networks, presented in the following eight chapters of this

report. Only through further work on conceptual clarity and theoretical foundation of social innovation it will be possible to establish social innovation research as a solid scientific area.

In the area of **Public Sector Innovation**, the need for implementation of new methods and approaches to policy-making and public policies has been highlighted. The focus on co-creation and co-design methodologies to find innovative solutions to social problems and needs can build a positive change in the governance model of the public sector and the ways in which it generates public value with and for the people. A governance network of this nature should be open to a wide range of actors, agents, and organisations, from public servants, policymakers and practitioners, to social innovators, public institutions, non-profit organizations, service users (citizens), social entrepreneurs, etc. Horizontal approaches are better than unilateral top-down or bottom-up perspectives.

An important finding in the chapter on **Digital Social Innovation** has been that one area of societal challenges that appears strikingly disconnected from digital social innovation is the ICT sector itself. The more political projects are seeing challenges in the dominance of commercial platforms (that are mostly US-based) and the current asymmetrical and volatile divisions of labour and power between European, US-based and Chinese information and communication technology and platform providers. These tensions in the political economy may create risks to European sustainable and inclusive growth as well as opportunities. Connecting discussions on social innovation with those on contemporary political economies would provide deeper insight into the genesis of needs and challenges to social innovation.

Reflecting on a potential '**Intermediaries Network**', the authors of the corresponding chapter conclude that, from a research perspective, one of its key functions will be to broaden the pool of people who are engaging with social innovation ideas and helping to widen our understanding of who intermediaries are. This network directly addresses the criticism that social innovation sometimes operates within a 'silo culture'. It will help to build links and share tools, methods and approaches in order to foster knowledge. This network will enrich the social innovation research landscape of the future by incorporating new theoretical ideas and fresh models of working. In addition, we hope that by sharing the processes, tools and methods of social innovation beyond the 'usual suspects' could spread the benefits of social innovation to new sectors and new actors.

While the area of **Social Economy** and its relationship with social innovation represents a more and more vivid field of activity for a number of leading research centres and scholars, much still needs to be done in order to corroborate this evidence with the strength that only data and empirical proofs can offer. In fact, a sounder use, control and systematization of statistics and comparative databases adapted to assess the impact of the social and solidarity economy could certainly offer a fuller and more orientation for policy-makers. With this aim, also a deeper integration of evidences and results will be crucial to overcome the still existing sectoral and geographical fragmentation of the subject (e.g. includ-

ing data in a joint case study database) as well as to show the added value of social economy in terms of social innovation.

The intersection between **Cities and Regions Development** and social innovation is already a well promising area of research and application. The convergence among the two themes has been strongly supported by different processes. What is still lacking is a robust process of compression of the impact of these new waves of involvement of citizens in the development of their cities and territories. There is a need to frame, model, and measure the different co-creation mechanisms that are going on in urban and peripheral places and understand their impact on the development of a more sustainable society.

While the research on the **Collaborative and Sharing Economy** is increasing and highly dynamic, the area as such is considered to stand at a crossroad. In its beginnings, participants were motivated by its claim to provide economic, social and environmental benefits. With time, critiques have been surging pointing to the perversities of certain forms of the sharing and collaborative economy, such as labour exploitation, exclusion, discrimination and rebound effects. Hence, building an inclusive community in terms of a network in this highly heterogeneous and dynamic area results as a very demanding task.

Despite the focus around 'grassroots' social innovation, research in the area of **Community-led Innovation** is dispersed. For this reason, this cannot be said to be a cohesive field of social innovation research and the literature is highly diffused among a number of different disciplines and approaches. However there are a number of fields where community-led social innovation is not only visible but growing, also and thanks to the work of research institutions who have helped to understand how to support community innovators (e.g. through accelerator models). In part because of the diffuse nature of this area, the research landscape can appear thin, particularly around the theory and the understanding of the processes of community-led innovation. Therefore, through network activities emergence of a field of community-led innovation study should be encouraged, in turn helping us to address some of these research gaps.

Corporate Social Innovation is a relatively new field for corporate businesses. It has a lot of potential to become more relevant in the future in both research and practice. Even though CSI experienced some upheaval among the research community, when it comes to the application of the concept among practitioners and businesses, the concept rather remains undervalued and unrecognised by the business sector. Hence, it is also an important task for social innovation research to better connect its work to practice in order to further develop Corporate Social Innovation as one of the key elements of the social innovation ecosystem.

Altogether, we can say that despite its fragmentation, the international social innovation research landscape offers a great potential regarding the building of an inclusive social innovation research community which would transcend European borders and research disciplines. If we want to make use of this potential different measures should be designed and introduced. Some of them are already addressed

by the project Social Innovation Community (SIC), other methods still need to be developed. What is clear is that there is a need for more opportunities for researchers to work on the topic of social innovation. In recent years, many promising initiatives have contributed to the formation of the area of social innovation as a research field and as a whole. In the European Union, funding provided by the European Commission has been crucial for this development. Hence, further funding opportunities will largely determine the future of social innovation and its research.

There is an ongoing task for the community to facilitate interaction among all those who are part of it and also with those who maybe do not consider themselves yet 'members' of the social innovation community (in this regard, the Expert Survey was also particularly important). This includes connecting to unusual suspects as well as researchers and practitioners who work in this field but do not focus on social innovation explicitly. In order to advance towards such a community, a key task in the upcoming years will be to work together on different kinds of projects, organise events and other spaces for exchange as well as create opportunities for publishing and diffusing research results.

APPENDIX: A (non-exhaustive) overview of actors of the Sharing and Collaborative Economy

Name	Short description	Founded	Coverage (HQ, operations)	Link	Types of services	Sector
Kind of actor: Market						
Turo (formerly Relay Rides)	Peer-to-peer carsharing. Allows private car owners to rent out their vehicles via online interface.	2009	HQ: San Francisco Operations: United States	https://turo.com/	Carsharing	Mobility
Zimride	Largest rideshare program in the US. Connects inter-city drivers and passengers via social networking.	2007	HQ: San Francisco Operations: United States	https://zimride.com/	Ridesharing	Mobility
Uber/UberX	American worldwide online transportation network company. Offers services through the Uber app.	2009	HQ: San Francisco Operations: 66 countries worldwide (507 cities)	https://www.uber.com/	Cabservice	Mobility
Lyft	American transportation network company (peer-to-peer ridesharing). Services can be booked through the Lyft mobile app.	2012	HQ: San Francisco Operations: United States, 9 cities in south-east Asia	https://www.lyft.com/	Cabservice	Mobility
Couchsurfing International Inc.	Hospitality service and social networking site. Members of the platform can 'surf' on couches through staying at another member's home, meet other members or join couchsurfing events.	2003 (non-profit service) 2011 (for-profit corporation)	HQ: San Francisco Operations: Worldwide (200.000+ cities)	https://www.couchsurfing.com/	Homesharing	Tourism
Task Rabbit	Online and mobile marketplace offering freelance labor services. Customers can buy specific services at pre-determined prices	2008	HQ: San Francisco Operations: 18 US cities, London	https://www.taskrabbit.com/	General Services (e.g. cleaning, moving, delivery)	Services
Zaarly	Service platform matching home service businesses with local demand.	2011	HQ: San Francisco Operations: 7 US cities	https://zaarly.com/	Home service	Services
Kickstarter	Public-benefit corporation offering a global crowdfunding platform focusing primarily on creativity. Members can pledge money for projects and receive tangible rewards for their commitment at a later stage of the project.	2009	HQ: New York City Operations: Worldwide	https://www.kickstarter.com/	Crowdfunding	Investment
AirBnB	Peer-to-peer online homestay network offering accommodation to	2008	HQ: San Francisco Operations: Worldwide (191 countries,	https://www.airbnb.com/	Homereating	Tourism

	customers. Property owners can rent out their residential properties to their individually determined prices.		34 000 cities)			
Peerby	Peer-to-peer sharing website offering the rental of tools. Members can offer their tools for rental, which will be delivered to other members for limited periods of time.	2011	HQ: Amsterdam Operations: Netherlands	https://go.peerby.com/	Toolsharing	Rental
Lending Club	Peer-to-peer lending company enabling peers to list their offerings as securities with the Security and Exchange Commission and offering loan trading.	2006	HQ: San Francisco, USA Operations: USA	https://www.lendingclub.com/	Loans	Finance
Zip Car	World's largest car-sharing company	2000	HQ: Boston Operations: US, UK, Austria, Canada, France, Spain, Belgium	http://www.zipcar.com/	Carsharing	Mobility
9flats	Peer-to-peer online property rental company for private accommodations. Property owners can rent out their residential properties to their individually determined prices. The website uses a collaborative consumption model to ensure most effective resource sharing.	2010	HQ: Singapore Operations: Worldwide (2012: 104 countries)	https://www.9flats.com/	Homereating	Rental
HomeExchange.com	Home exchange network connecting travelers and thereby allowing them to swap homes around the world	1992	HQ: Hermosa Beach, US Operations: Worldwide	https://www.homeexchange.com/en/	Homesharing	Tourism
Tujia.com	Online platform offering vacation rentals at private households primarily in tourist locations.	2011	HQ: Beijing, China Operations	http://tujia.com	Homesharing	Tourism
Kind of actor: State						
Hubway	Bicycle sharing service in Boston. Offers bike docking stations around the city (that can be located via an online map) where bikes can be picked up and returned by customers.	2011	HQ: Boston Operations: Boston	https://www.thehubway.com/	Bikesharing	Mobility
Divvy Bikes	Bicycle sharing service in Chicago. Offers bike docking stations around the city (that can be located via an online map) where bikes can be picked up and returned	2013	HQ: Chicago Operations: Chicago	https://www.divvybikes.com/	Bikesharing	Mobility

by customers.						
Kind of actor: 3 rd sector						
Streetbank	Neighborhood sharing website with the goal of boosting local communities by encouraging people to get to know their neighbors. Members can lend and share any kind of household items with other members.	2010	HQ: London Operations: World-wide	https://www.streetbank.com/	General sharing of goods	DIY
Share Some Sugar	Does not exist anymore (closed 2011)					
TimeBanks USA	Reciprocity-based work trading system in which hours are the currency of the transactions: One hour of work done by one member can be bought with one hour of work by another member. TimeBanks USA works towards expanding the knowledge in the field of timebanking and its impact on individuals and communities	1995	HQ: Washington, USA Operations: USA	http://timebanks.org/	General Services	Service
Makerspace (UK)	Community owned and run workshop in Newcastle Upon Tyne (UK). It is a meeting place for anyone who is interested in working on a technical or mechanical construction project. Members pay fees to cover the costs for new tools and materials.	-	HQ and operations: Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK (<i>concept spread globally</i>)	http://www.makerspace.org.uk/	Manufacturing, Knowledge-sharing	DIY
Toronto Tool Library	Multiple shops in the city of Toronto, where members can lend 5000+ tools for an annual fee. Danforth location also offers a makerspace with a variety of tools and 3D printers.	2012	HQ and operations: Toronto, Canada	http://torontotoollibrary.com/	Toolsharing	DIY
Feastly	Peer-to-peer online marketplace connecting cooks and consumers ('eaters').	2013	HQ: New York City Operations: USA	https://eatfeastly.com/	Social Dining	Food
Behomm	Home exchange community for creatives and design lovers	-	HQ: Barcelona Operations: World-wide	https://www.behomm.com/	Home exchange	Tourism
Be welcome	Online based hospitality exchange service run by the non-profit organization BeVolunteer	2007	HQ: Rennes, France Operations: World-wide (150 countries)	http://www.bewelcome.org/	Homestay	Tourism
Guest to guest	Peer-to-peer online home exchange service connecting individuals who	2011	HQ: Paris Operations: France, Italy, Spain, Austral-	https://www.guesttoguest.c	Homesha-	Rental

	wish to exchange their homes for short or long stays. If exchange is non-reciprocal, members can pay the hosts in 'Guest-point' currency.		ia, London	om/		
Trustroots	Online hospitality exchange organization for travelers. Member can see other member's location and host them, share stories or just connect.	2014	HQ: United Kingdom Operations: Worldwide	https://www.trustroots.org/	Homestay, Social network	Tourism
Warm showers	Online hospitality exchange organization for touring cyclists. Online service connects members and enables cyclists to find free accommodation at website members, or to take a break at other member's places (e.g. to take a shower).	1993	HQ: - Operations: Worldwide	https://www.warmshowers.org/	Homestay	Tourism
European Sharing Economy Coalition	Pan-European network to campaign and advocate for EU policies in support of the sharing economy	2015	-	http://www.eurofreelancers.eu/european-sharing-economy-coalition/	Lobbying	Politics
Collaborative Consumption	Online resource for collaborative consumption worldwide and network for the (global) community. Collects news and general content on collaborative consumption and produces original content	-	Operations: Worldwide (except Antarctica)	http://www.collaborativeconsumption.com/	Knowledgesharing	Social Network
Nesta	Independent charity, focusing on the increase in innovation capacity of the UK. Active through practical programmes, policy and research, partnerships in a variety of sectors and investment.	1998	HQ: London Operations: United Kingdom	http://www.nesta.org.uk/	Lobbying, Research	Philanthropy
OuiShare	Organization fostering the establishment of a collaborative society by connecting people, organizations and ideas around fairness, openness, and trust. Active in research, community organization, professional services, and education	2012	HQ: Paris Operations: Europe	http://oui.share.net/en	Knowledgesharing, Lobbying, Research	Network

Shareable (including Shareable USA, Sharing Cities)	Non-profit news, action and connection hub for the sharing transformation.	2009		http://www.shareable.net/	News, Knowledge-sharing	Network
Global Ecovillage Network	Global association of people and communities dedicated to sustainable living. The goal is to restoring the environment.	1991	HQ: Multiple continental offices in Europe, Asia, South and North America Operations: Worldwide	http://gen.ecovillage.org/	Sustainable living	Network
Transition Network (example of transition towns)	Knowledge base that was set up to develop and spread the concept of transition towns. Transition towns are grassroots community projects aiming to reduce humanity's potentially negative impact on the environment and the economy through self-sufficiency.	2006-2007	HQ: UK Operations: Worldwide	https://transitionnetwork.org/	Sustainable living	Network
Hackerspaces	Community-operated places, where individuals can share their interest in working with technology, work on DIY projects and exchange knowledge. There are many hackerspaces around the world, therefore we will not mention a particular organization.	-	-	-		DIY
FabLab Foundation	Having emerged from MIT's Center for Bits & Atoms Network, this organization facilitates and supports the development of the international fab lab network. Fab labs are small-scale workshops offering the opportunity for anyone to create own goods with the help of computer-controlled tools.	2009	HQ: Boston Operations: Worldwide	http://www.fabfoundation.org/	Manufacturing, Knowledge-sharing	DIY
RepRap(.org)	General-purpose self-replicating 3D printer. RepRap.org is a community project focusing on creating a knowledge base for 3D printing and for the RepRap machines in particular.	-	-	http://reprap.org/	Manufacturing, Knowledge-sharing	DIY
Neighbor-Goods	Online community facilitating the sharing of goods amongst friends and neighbors.	2009	HQ: Los Angeles, USA Operations: USA	http://neighborgoods.net/	Toolsharing	DIY/Network
Peer2peer	Peer2Peer is an educa-	2009	HQ: Hoofddorp, NL	https://pe	Online-	Educa-

	tional concept with the idea that students interact with each other to attain educational goals. P2PU.org offers an online space for students to work together on certain topics		Operations: Netherlands	er2peer-edu.nl/	education	tion
FreeCycle Network	Comprises 5000+ groups worldwide, Freecycle is a network of individuals who are sharing their goods for free within their communities to avoid waste	2003	HQ: Tucson, USA Operations: Worldwide	https://www.freecycle.org/	Sustainable living	Network